

Fr Stan Swamy SJ
April 26, 1937 - July 5, 2021

**CHALLENGES AND TASKS
FOR THE ASIAN CHURCH**

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Challenges and Tasks
for the Asian Church

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Editorial

Challenges and Tasks for the Asian Church

Fr Stan Swamy SJ, died on Monday, July 5, 2021 as a martyr and tribal activist. He in hi person symbolises the challenges and tasks of the Asian Church..

The personal opinion of Julio Ribeiro, a retired IPS officer, former Mumbai Police commissioner and DGP, Gujarat and Punjab is noteworthy: “Stan Swamy lived a life of service to the poor and oppressed. He paid for his commitment.”

He thinks that citizens of this ancient land who have a heart will shed a genuine tear or two. There will be many more like him who would truly grieve, some vocal but mostly silent mourners whose cerebral dislike for injustice rankles in their guts. According to him the great majority of the mourners cannot be accused of even a whiff of parochial feelings.

The Case Against Stan

Why was this tribal rights activist thrown into jail? First, for ‘pro-Maoist’ leanings! Then, he is supposed to have plotted with other Leftist intellectuals to overthrow the State that the Maoists do not recognise. He is even supposed to have plotted to assassinate Prime Minister Modi! The evidence to prove these serious charges are allegedly on the computer that the National Investigation Agency seized. The evidence has not been brought before a court, except, I presume, in the form of case diaries of

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investigation shown to trial magistrates for the purpose of ensuring that Stan Swamy was kept in jail under the draconian Unlawful Activities (Prevention) Act, which was amended in 2019 to make it impossible for those charged of ‘terrorism’ to be released on bail.

Rona Wilson, another co-accused in the Bhima-Koregaon ‘conspiracy’ case, had allegedly been provided with a pen drive that, according to the NIA, contained the main evidence of guilt. Wilson’s defence team sent that piece of explosive evidence to a leading forensic expert in Boston, Massachusetts, US. The expert opined that the evidence was inserted on Wilson’s computer very cleverly over a period of a few years through malware (Ribeiro, 2021).

This opinion was sent to other experts in the US by *The Washington Post*, who ratified it. The Boston expert said that he had never encountered such a neat and clever insertion of false evidence on a computer in his many years of work. It is a mystery that can be solved only if the government wishes to establish the truth. At the moment, its minions are sticking to their guns. Their experts, they say, have given their opinion and they will not consider contrary views of extra-territorial experts who they do not recognise.

The Stain of Stan

This stand condemns the 15 other accused currently in jail without trial, a concept abhorrent to jurisprudence in the free world. For a government that is eager to put away Left-wing activists who slow down development by insisting on the rights of the indigenous tribes as mandated by law, the stakes obviously are high. Tribal lands cannot be utilised for exploitation, especially if they are located in reserved forests. These laws are legislated by governments that do not lay any store in enforcing the laws they themselves enact. In fact, to the contrary, they expect these laws to be breached and, in the process, line their own pockets and fill the coffers of the government.

According to Ribeiro, Stan Swamy was a stumbling block to such grand designs. He explained the law to the tribals and actively advocated their cause. An alert and empowered community is an enigma that the government, any government, would be keen to remove from its path. The means to this end, diabolical and patently criminal, appears to have been employed (Ribeiro, 2021).

He challenges us to look into account the possibility of false evidence being deliberately introduced on computers via malware. The Boston expert opined he had never come across such ingenuity in his long career exposing cybercrime. Obviously, we have a genius, albeit evil, here in our country. That genius should have been used to counter our hostile neighbours to our west and east. If we do really have such a genius in our midst, the government should exploit the advantage, but not against its own citizens who are out to help the helpless and the historically excluded.

While paying homage to Stan Swamy, Ribeiro feels the need to pay my homage to Jesus who laid down his life for his friends. No greater love can a man have than that. His “Jesuit order enforces its law on obedience very strictly. The Catholic Church frowns on Communism; Maoist philosophy is anathema to it. It was impossible for Fr. Stan, for any Jesuit for that matter, to defy that injunction, that too for many years. It is ridiculous for the government to make us believe that Stan Swamy could have been involved in a conspiracy to kill the prime minister,” asserts Ribeiro (2021).

Ribeiro concludes the article: “Fr. Stan Swamy, lived a life of service to the poor and the oppressed. And he paid for his commitment” (Ribeiro, 2021). Is the Asian Church ready to follow the path of Stan, and more that of his Lord?

The articles in this issue of *Jnanadeepa* reflect on various aspects of the crucial challenges that the Asian Church faces. Some of the articles trace hope in dialogue, fraternity and solidarity with all people of good will.

The Editor

Reference

Ribeiro, J. (2021, July 6). *Stan Swamy lived a life of service to the poor and oppressed. He paid for his commitment.* <https://theprint.in/opinion/stan-swamy-lived-a-life-of-service-to-the-poor-and-oppressed-he-paid-for-his-commitment/690439/>

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Current Trends and Future Tasks of Christian Theology of Asia: In Celebration of the 50th Anniversary of the Foundation of the FABC

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Abstract: This essay begins with a brief assessment of the theological legacy of the Federation of Asian Bishops' Conferences in terms of a triple dialogue (with the Asian poor, cultures, and religions) and contextual theology. It then surveys eight common features of Asian Christianity, namely, foreign character, colonial heritage, dehumanizing poverty, ecological destruction, minority status, Communist and socialist governments, ubiquitous migration, and anti-woman ideology. Next, it points to eight contemporary theological trends in response to these eight commonalities. It concludes with an examination of one of these eight trends, namely, interreligious dialogue, with reference to Pope Francis's teaching on this theme.

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Keywords: The FABC, Dialogue, Contextual Theology, Asian Christianity, Pope Francis.

This article discusses the current trends and the future tasks of Asian Christian theology. By way of introduction, in celebration of the 50th anniversary of the founding of the FABC, I briefly assess its theological legacy and its impact on the way theology is being done in Asia today. In light of these achievements, I next outline the current trends in Asian theology and discuss its future orientations. In the final part, I focus on an especially urgent task for the Asian Churches, namely, interreligious dialogue, by examining the teaching of Pope Francis on this theme.¹

The Theological Legacy of the FABC

Fifty years, a long time in a person's life, is but a blip on the Church's two-thousand-year-long historical radar. Yet, the FABC's golden jubilee marks a momentous event in the history of Asian Catholicism, worthy of thankful and joyful celebration, for the impact it has had on the Asian Catholic Churches. As its website states, the FABC is a voluntary association of episcopal conferences in South, East, Southeast, and Central Asia, whose purpose is to

¹ This is a revised article based on an online presentation to Bishops and theologians on the occasion of the 50th anniversary of the founding of Federation of Asian Bishop's Conference (FABC). Allow me to begin by expressing my deepest thanks to Rev. Dr. Francis Gonsalves, SJ, Executive Secretary of the Commission for Theology & Doctrine of the Conference of Catholic Bishops of India, for the kind invitation to address you today. I have been to India twice and on both occasions have been deeply edified by its rich and varied cultures and the profound religiosity of its people. Theologically, I gratefully acknowledge my indebtedness to the Federation of the Asian Bishops' Conferences, the 50th anniversary of which we are celebrating, to Indian Catholic theologians, in particular Raimon Panikkar, the Belgian Jacques Dupuis, Michael Amaladoss, Francis D'Sa, Felix Wilfred, and to the Sri Lankan Jesuit Aloysius Pieris. I dedicate my humble lecture to the memory of the many Indian victims of Covid-19, especially those who selflessly sacrificed their lives to the service of the sick and the dying.

foster among its members solidarity and co-responsibility for the welfare of the Church and society in Asia and to promote and defend the common good. On the occasion of the 50th anniversary of the Asian Bishop's Meeting in Manila in 1970, which was the beginning of the FABC, its Central Secretariat brought out a collection of the Final Statements of all the eleven Plenary Assemblies of the FABC that were held so far and the statements of the 1970 Asian Bishops' Meeting.²

Here is not the place to narrate the FABC's historical development and evaluate its pastoral and theological achievements as well as the significance of the hundreds of "Papers" published by its various Offices.³ The most groundbreaking concept of their theology, in my judgment, is the understanding of the Church's mission as dialogue, indeed a triple dialogue: dialogue with the Asian poor (liberation and integral development), dialogue with Asian cultures (inculturation), and dialogue with the believers of other religions (interreligious encounter).⁴ All the theological statements of the FABC may be viewed as but variations on this leitmotif, by enlarging the category of the poor to include not only the economically poor but also the victims of political oppression, the culturally marginalized, the Dalits, the Adivasis, ethnic and religious minorities, subjugated women and exploited children, migrants, and the ecological destruction of Earth itself; by exploring the diverse ways in which the Christian faith can be expressed employing the various elements of Asian cultures including philosophy, the plastic arts, music, dance, and architecture; and by

² See Vimal Tirimanna (ed.), *Fifty Years of Asian Pastoral Guidance*. Hong Kong: FABC Central Secretariat, 2020.

³ For a brief history and evaluation of the FABC, see Jonathan Tan, *The Federation of Asian Bishops' Conferences (FABC): Bearing Witness to the Gospel and the Reign of God in Asia* (Minneapolis: Fortress Press, 2021). See also the many writings on the FABC by James H. Kroeger.

⁴ This triple dialogue was first explicitly mentioned at the FABC's First Plenary Assembly in 1974. See Vimal Titimanna, 5-8.

undertaking dialogue with Asian religions such as Hinduism, Buddhism, the Chinese religious traditions, and Islam through common living, collaboration for the common welfare of society, theological discussion, and sharing religious experiences. The concrete and specific modalities of liberation, inculturation, and interreligious encounter may be different, depending on who the poor, cultures, and religions are in various places and at different times, but dialogue as the way to fulfill Christian mission in Asia remains the *cantus firmus* of the FABC's polyphonic theological composition.

In addition to this thematic unity, the most radical and game-changing shift in the FABC's theology as *fides quaerens intellectum* is its adoption of "contexts" as the resources and the starting point of theological reflection.⁵ Contexts are not simply the milieus in which theology is done, as was the case with Western classical, say, Thomas Aquinas's, theology; rather they are the "signs of the time" that serve as the hermeneutical lens to interpret Scripture and Tradition. Of course, Scripture and Tradition are used to shed light on the signs of the times but conversely, the signs of the time shape the interpretation of these Christian sources. Thus, there is no doubt in the FABC's documents about where, when, and how theology is done and who are its agents. Significantly, all its statements invariably begin with an exposition of the socio-political, economic, cultural, and religious contexts and only then proceed to elucidate the Christian message in the light of and for these contexts. Adopting this theological methodology, I now highlight some salient features of the contexts in which I think Asian Christian theology should be elaborated.

⁵ On this understanding of "context," see Franz-Josef Eilers, ed., *For All the Peoples of Asia: Federation of Asian Bishops' Conference Documents from 1997 to 2001*, vol. 3. Quezon City, The Philippines: Claretian Publications, 2002, 355-364.

Contextual Elements of Asian Christianity

Culturally, there are two dominant cultures in Asia, the Indic and the Sinic, the former predominantly in South Asia, and the latter predominantly in Northeast and Southeast Asia, but both cultures are present in all three regions of Asia. Politically, while there are democratic countries such as India, South Korea, Japan, Thailand, the Philippines, Malaysia, and Indonesia, their democracy has been very fragile, especially in the last four countries, as extremist groups emerged as an alternative to electoral politics. Religious freedom is also threatened by authoritarian, one-party, and/or military governments such as China, North Korea, Vietnam, Myanmar, Laos, and Brunei. To elaborate a Christian theology appropriate to Asia as a whole it is helpful to highlight some key common elements of Christianities in the three regions even though it is necessary to pay close attention to the socio-political, economic, cultural, and religious contexts in which Christianity exists, not only in each of the three regions but also in each country.⁶

First, it has often been said that Christianity in Asia was and remains a foreign religion that was imported by Western missionaries. Historically, this is true of Christianity in all three regions of Asia. Christianity was brought to Asia by missionaries from Portugal (India, China, Macau, Vietnam, and Timor-Leste), Spain (the Philippines), the Netherlands (Taiwan and Indonesia), Britain (India, Hong Kong, Malaysia, and Singapore), France (Vietnam, Cambodia, Laos, and Thailand), and the United States (South Korea, Myanmar, and the Philippines). Perhaps the point of the observation about the foreign character of Christianity is that

⁶ For excellent surveys of Christianity in Asia, see Kenneth R. Ross, Daniel Jeyaraj, and Todd M. Johnson, eds., *Christianity in South and Central Asia* (Edinburgh: University of Edinburgh Press, 2019) and Kenneth R. Ross, Francis D. Alvarez, and Todd M. Johnson, eds., *Christianity in East and Southeast Asia*. Edinburgh: University of Edinburgh Press, 2020.

Christianity has not been thoroughly indigenized into the local cultures and contexts like other Asian religions and that some Christian denominations are currently still dependent on foreign financial aid and administrative authorities and do not subscribe to the Three-Self Principles, namely, self-governing, self-supporting, and self-propagating. This is especially true of the Catholic Church, with its organizational and juridical ties to the Vatican City State.

Secondly, connected with the foreignness of Christianity is the historical alliance between Christianity and colonialism in Asia. Missionaries from Portugal, Spain, Britain, France, and the United States came to evangelize Asian countries with the financial and political support of their colonizing countries. No doubt the Catholic Church benefited much from this arrangement; indeed, without the assistance of the Iberian empires, it would be very unlikely that the Church could have carried out its evangelizing mission in the new worlds of Latin America and Asia. Asian Christians must honestly acknowledge the colonial legacy of their Churches and the many privileges accrued to them, especially in terms of education, health care, and social services, as the best schools, universities, hospitals, and social institutions in their countries are owned or administered by Christians.

The third common feature of Asian Christianity is its existence amidst overwhelming poverty. While South Korea, Taiwan, Hong Kong, and Singapore are the four economic ‘Asian Tigers’ thanks to their rapid economic growth and an improved standard of living, and although Indonesia, Malaysia, Thailand, and Vietnam have recently reached the status of economic ‘Tiger Cubs,’ there are still millions of Asians living below poverty level, subsisting on less than US\$ 1.90 a day, and having little access to education, health care, and social services. Massive poverty is also worsened by the endemic corruption and graft by kleptocratic governments that steal public funds earmarked for the betterment of the living standards in their countries. Furthermore, while globalization has raised the

living standards in several Asian countries, its neoliberal market economy has widened the gap between the rich and the poor. This new form of colonialism is no less destructive of human dignity and human rights than the old one. Indeed, neocolonialism is more dangerous as its impact is not as visible as the old-time colonizers' occupation of their lands and exploitation of their natural resources. One of the most pernicious effects of the neoliberal economy is consumerism, which is the siren's song to youth and enslaves the consumers as they accumulate more and more things.

The fourth common element is ecological degradation in many Asian countries. There is an urgent need for Asian Christians to grasp the causal connection between the release of greenhouse gases (carbon dioxide, methane, nitrogen oxides, and others) into the atmosphere, the depletion of the ozone layer, global warming, the melting of the polar ice, the rise of the sea level on the one hand and human activities such as the burning of fossil fuel (coal, petroleum, and gas), deforestation, the dumping of industrial and nuclear waste and chemical products, and the increasing use of fertilizers, insecticides, fungicides, herbicides and agrottoxins on the other. The common tendency to attribute ecological destruction and natural disasters to divine punishment must be resisted. In addition, many Asian countries, for example, Indonesia and the Philippines, are located in the 'ring of fire,' with devastating volcanic eruptions. Furthermore, countries with a high percentage of their population living near rivers and the coastlines are frequent victims of the effects of climate change such as tsunamis, floods, and droughts that destroy the poor's livelihood and force them to migrate.

The fifth common feature of Christianity is its minority status in all Asian countries, except the Philippines and Timor-Leste. Asian Christians exist in Muslim-majority (Pakistan, Bangladesh, Malaysia, Indonesia, and Brunei), Hindu-majority (India), and Buddhist majority (South Korea, Thailand, Cambodia, Laos, Vietnam, and Sri Lanka) countries. This minority status makes

dialogue with the followers of other religions an existential imperative for Asian Christians. I will return to this issue in the last part of my lecture.

The sixth common feature of some Asian countries is co-existence with Communism. In self-declared Communist countries such as China, Vietnam, and North Korea, Christianity is no longer targeted for eradication as such but the Churches must be registered with the government, and their activities are regulated and restricted under the pretext of “national security” and “social unity.” In China, in particular, the Catholic Church must deal with the problem of two parallel Churches, the so-called official or registered Church and the underground or unregistered Church, especially the thorny issue of the nomination and ordination of bishops. In authoritarian countries, often under military regimes, religious repression and violations of human rights are committed not in the name of ideology but to maintain the government’s absolute power. In Muslim-majority countries such as Pakistan, Brunei, Indonesia, and Malaysia, religious freedom is constitutionally guaranteed but in practice, legal restrictions on religious practices are put in place against Christians. Even in democratic countries such as India, Malaysia, and Indonesia, especially when right-wing political movements and religious extremists are in power, there are the blasphemy law and prohibitions against conversion from Islam and Hinduism, the use of the term Allah for the Christian God, the distribution of bibles, missionary activities, and public celebration of Christian feasts.

The seventh common feature of Asian countries is ubiquitous migration. In the last fifty years, Asia has massively entered the global migration age. Rapid economic growth, the impact of globalization, social transformations, international and civil wars, and ecological disasters have accelerated the rate of migration of Asians from Asian countries to non-Asian countries, to other Asian countries (international migrants), and also within each country (internally displaced persons), especially due to the movement of

people from rural areas to the cities in search of work (urbanization). From the end of World War II and the dismantling of British, French, Dutch, and Japanese colonial empires to 1973, there were waves of returning colonists, often with their families of colonial subjects, to their respective countries, especially from Indonesia to Holland, from Vietnam to France, from Timor-Leste to Portugal, and from India to Britain. Also during these three decades, there were protracted wars in Korea and Vietnam that caused millions of people to leave the north for the south. During 1975-1989, after the oil boom, the Gulf region emerged as the new migration destination for Asian migrants, especially from India, Pakistan, and the Philippines. The end of the Vietnam War, with the victory of Communist North Vietnam over South Vietnam in 1975, saw hundreds of thousands of Vietnamese, Cambodians, and Laotians migrate to the U.S., Canada, Australia, and European countries. During 1989-2008, the increasing demand for lower-and higher-skilled workers in the Gulf region attracted a large number of Asian migrants. Also, there was intra-regional migration from poorer Southeast Asian countries like Indonesia, Vietnam, and the Philippines to richer Southeast Asian countries like Malaysia, Singapore, and Thailand and East Asian countries such as China, Japan, South Korea, and Taiwan. Since 2008 there has been an acceleration of extra-regional migration, especially from Indonesia and Myanmar, to the Gulf, North America, and Europe, and intra-regional migration, especially to East Asia and some countries of Southeast Asia. Recently there has been a forced displacement of Rohingyas from Myanmar and Uyghurs in Northwest China.

The eighth common feature of Asian countries is the oppressed status of women, economically, socio-politically, culturally, and religiously. Though significant improvements in women's condition have been made in several countries thanks to their struggle for equal rights, there are still severe restrictions based on their gender in education, employment, political rights, and religious functions, especially in Muslim-majority countries and

those with patriarchal cultures. The Christian Churches in Asia as a whole have exacerbated this anti-woman ethos with their male-dominated structures and practices.

Future Asian Theologies: Tasks and Orientations

Christian theology is the critical and systematic understanding of Jesus' message about the reign of God as it is communicated and lived by the Church in different times and places. There are thus two constitutive elements in the making of theology, one that is constant and permanent, namely, Jesus' message, and the other by nature changeable and varied, namely, its transmission and practice by Christians in various contexts. Of course, Jesus' message itself, though permanent and constant, is not a context-free reality descending straight from heaven as it were; rather, like the eternal Son of God made flesh as a Jew in Palestine, his message, as recorded in the New Testament, is already contextualized in different cultures, namely, Jewish and Greek. Consequently, it is more accurate to understand theology as an intercontextual or intercultural critical study of the encounter between the cultures in which Jesus' message has been embodied and the new cultures in which it is to be inculturated again. There are in theology both the transcendent or universal message of Jesus about the reign of God and the historicized or particular realization of that message at different times and in various locations throughout the world.

Doing theology in this way involves three interrelated steps. The first step, which may be called the "socio-analytic mediation" of the theological discipline, seeks to ascertain the empirical facts as they are, as objectively and as truthfully as possible, as the context for theology, as I have done above. The second step, which may be called the "hermeneutical mediation," interprets the empirical data in the light of the Bible and Christian Tradition; and vice versa, it interprets the Bible and the Christian Tradition in the light of the empirical data obtained in the socio-analytic mediation to yield a theological hypothesis or theory. The third step, the "practical

mediation,” seeks to embody the theological answer in the practice of the Christian community, which practice, in turn, generates new data for the socio-analytic mediation, and the processes of theological hermeneutic mediation and practical mediation begin all over again.⁷ In what follows, it is not of course possible to elaborate the hermeneutical and practical mediations of an Asian theology in detail. I will only indicate some of the tasks and orientations of such a theology in the light of the data discussed above.

First, the widespread and dehumanizing poverty in several Asian countries must be the constant concern of Asian Churches. This poverty has been exacerbated by neocolonialist globalization, government corruption, anti-democratic militaristic regime, increasing urbanization, and ecological degradation, which prevent social, political, and economic projects from attaining their goals of bringing about well-being to the most marginalized citizens. The work of abolishing poverty in favour of justice and integral development has been repeatedly advocated by the FABC as an intrinsic part of the mission of the Church and must be a fundamental theme of Asian theology.⁸

Second, connected with poverty is the issue of migration. Several Asian countries are countries of emigration, especially Pakistan, Nepal, the Philippines, Vietnam, Indonesia, and Myanmar. Churches must set up programs to prepare emigrants before their departure, connect with them while they are abroad, and assist the families that are left behind. Emigration cannot be eliminated, but efforts must be made by both the government and the Churches to reduce the “culture of emigration,” the feminization of labour export, sex trafficking, and the misuse of remittances in the

⁷ On this triple mediation, see Peter C. Phan, *Christianity with an Asian Face: Asian American Theology in the Making*. Maryknoll, N.Y.: Orbis Books, 2004. 26-46.

⁸ See in particular the works of Aloysius Pieris, Michael Amaladoss, and Felix Wilfred.

emigration countries. Theologically, a theology of migration must be elaborated in which God is shown to be the Primordial Migrant, Jesus the Paradigmatic Migrant, the Holy Spirit the Power of Migration, and the Church as a community of migrants.⁹

Third, the work to make Christianity a truly Asian religion through comprehensive inculturation or contextualization, already well underway in several countries, for example, India, South Korea, and the Philippines, should be assiduously continued and expanded to all aspects of the church life in all countries. Here theology has an irreplaceable role. Beyond classical resources such as philosophy and religion, such theological inculturation must take into account the socio-political and economic contexts, cultural artefacts, and digital social media. In this way, Asian Christianity can effectively shed its colonial heritage and its foreign character. While Protestants, Evangelicals, and Pentecostals devote their resources to translating the Bible into hundreds of local languages, Catholics focus on adapting the liturgy and worship to the local cultures, making use of indigenous music, song, dance, rituals, practices of popular religion, and customs. A theology of inculturation must be developed in which the relation between the Gospel and culture is carefully analysed, the dynamic equivalences between the Christian beliefs and the beliefs of other religions are explored, and the ways to express and live the Christian faith in different local contexts are put into practice.¹⁰

Fourth, the nature of the Christian mission must be thoroughly reconceived. Mission or evangelism is understood and practiced

⁹ See Peter C. Phan, ed., *Christian Theology in the Age of Migration: Implications for World Christianity*. Lanham: Lexington Books, 2020 and the many writings of Gemma T. Cruz.

¹⁰ The literature by Asian theologians on inculturation is immense. Beside the works of Pieris, Amaladoss, Wilfred, and many others, see Peter C. Phan, *In Our Own Tongues: Perspectives from Asia on Mission and Inculturation* Maryknoll, N.Y.: Orbis Books, 2004.

very differently by Christians in Asia. Evangelicals, Pentecostals/Charismatics, and Independents understand mission as consisting mainly in preaching to non-Christians with the ultimate goal of converting and baptizing them. As mentioned above, this kind of mission is prohibited in some Muslim-majority countries. On the other hand, other Churches understand mission as bearing witness, by word and deed, to the Christian faith with the goal not primarily to convert non-Christian individuals, though this is not excluded, but to bring the reality and values of God's kingdom to the world. Christian mission is not only *missio ad gentes*, with non-Christians as the objects of the Christian's evangelism but also, and above all, *missio inter gentes*, that is, a mutual mission to one another, with Christians and non-Christians "converting" one another toward the kingdom of God, and *missio cum gentibus*, that is, mission carried by Christians together with non-Christians for the coming of the reign of God. This dialogue is particularly urgent between Christians and Muslims in Asia as both religions are forecast to be the two major religions in Asia. A peaceful relation between the two groups is essential for the well-being of Asia, especially in countries such as India, Thailand, the Philippines, and Indonesia.¹¹

Fifth, given the enormous growth of Evangelicals, Pentecostals/Charismatics, and Independents in Asia, a robust theology of the Holy Spirit (pneumatology) is urgently needed, not only for the dialogue between them and the other branches of Christianity (ecumenical dialogue) but also for a positive appreciation of the role of non-Christian religions in God's plan of salvation (interreligious dialogue). In Catholic theology, in Asia as well as elsewhere, a Christocentric, even Christonomic theology has been developed extensively; as a result, an exclusivist approach is usually adopted in the theology of religion. To redress the balance, a

¹¹ On this understanding of mission, see Peter C. Phan, *The Joy of Religious Pluralism: A Personal Journey*. Maryknoll, N.Y.: Orbis Books, 2017, 129-164.

pneumatological Christology or Christological pneumatology is urgently needed to acknowledge the salvific presence of God in non-Christian religions. In this way, St. Irenaeus’s celebrated image of God the Father (*Theos*) acting in the world always with two hands, the Word (*Logos*) and the Spirit (*Pneuma*), and not one *or* the other, is made into the leitmotif of Christian theology.¹²

Sixth, the widespread destruction of the environment in almost all Asian countries by both natural catastrophes and human abuses of natural resources which produces climate change and global warming urgently calls for a comprehensive theology of creation and ecology that moves beyond “natural” and human/social” ecology to “integral” ecology. In this respect, Pope Francis’s encyclical *Laudato Si’* is a magna carta that provides rich insights on solidarity, sustainability, and subsidiarity; on the links among ecology, migration, economics, and politics; on capitalism, consumerism, and the “throwaway culture”; on work and human relationships; on technology, energy, and recycling; and on food and water.¹³

Seventh, interreligious dialogue must be seriously undertaken in Christian-majority as well as Christian-minority countries. This is done in four areas, as frequently advocated by the FABC, namely, sharing daily life, collaboration for the common good, theological reflection, and sharing spiritual experiences. This interreligious dialogue not only promotes a deeper understanding and acceptance of the religious “Other” but is also an effective means to reduce religious extremism, radicalism, and violence in Asia. A theology of interreligious dialogue must go beyond the three paradigms of

¹² On a Christology and pneumatology on the basis of Irenaeus’s metaphor of the “two hands” of God, see Peter C. Phan, *The Joy of Religious Pluralism*, 51-74.

¹³ On an ecological theology for Asia based on Pope Francis’s *Laudato Si’*, see Peter C. Phan, *Asian Christianities: History, Theology, Practice* Maryknoll, N.Y.: Orbis Books, 2018. 288-302.

exclusivism, inclusivism, and pluralism in which Christianity is taken as the norm to evaluate the truth and value of other religions which are judged to be true and holy only to the extent they conform to Christianity, to be “fulfilled” by it, or as merely stepping-stones to Christianity. Rather, the dialogue among the religions must be a sincere, respectful, and humble undertaking to witness truthfully to others what one believes and practices without claiming that one’s religion is the only true one or the best, a claim that is epistemologically impossible to prove, and with readiness to share with others the truths and values of one’s religion, to learn from the truths and practices of the religions of the partners-in-dialogue, to correct the errors and deficiencies of one’s religion, and to be complemented and enriched by others.¹⁴

Eighth, though a vibrant feminist theology has been developed in Asia, especially in India, the Philippines, and Korea, it is far from gaining widespread acceptance and has not been made an integral part of the theological curriculum in almost all Christian denominations, notably the Catholic, Orthodox, Evangelical, and Pentecostal Churches. The necessity of feminist theology for Asia is made all the more urgent by the fact Church life is nurtured by a large number of female workers, though mostly in subordinate positions. Such feminist theology should not derive its inspiration only from Western theories but also from abundant Asian resources, both cultural and religious.¹⁵

In sum, a Christian theology that is appropriate for South, Northeast, and Southeast Asia must begin from their contemporary socio-political, economic, cultural, and religious contexts and the common

¹⁴ On this concept of interreligious dialogue, see Peter C. Phan, *Being Religious Interreligiously: Asian Perspectives on Interfaith Dialogue*. Maryknoll, N.Y.: Orbis Books, 2004.

¹⁵ See Kwok Pui-lan, *Introducing Asian Feminist Theology* (Cleveland: Pilgrim Press, 2000) and *Post Colonial Imagination & Feminist Theology*. Louisville, KY: Westminster John Knox Press, 2005.

challenges that these contexts pose to Christianity. Christian theology interprets these data in the light of the Gospel and the Gospel in the light of these data. I contend that to meet the challenges of Asia today contemporary Asian theology must develop a theology of liberation, migration, inculturation, mission, the Holy Spirit, ecology interreligious dialogue and feminist theology. I have also indicated the main outlines and orientations of these eight theologies, with the full awareness that they should be adapted to the particular conditions of each region and each country. I am deeply aware that I am not proposing new paths for Asian theology but simply systematizing the approaches and ideas of Asian theologians, more for the benefit of theologians of other continents, especially the West, who may still resist them.¹⁶

Pope Francis and Interreligious Encounter

With the election of a new pope there inevitably arises, at least among Catholics, the hope that he will bring needed changes in the Church, or the fear that he will deviate from the unchangeable Tradition. What kinds of changes, or fears, are harboured depend of course on the ones who hope or fear, and on the kind of pope who is elected. In 2013, hopes and fears were heightened by the fact that Jorge Bergoglio is the first Jesuit and the first South American to be elected to the papacy. On the right, there was anxiety that he might not pursue the restorationist program of his two predecessors, John Paul II and Benedict XVI, and will enact instead the Latin American liberal agenda. On the left, it was hoped that Francis would complete the unfinished businesses of Vatican II, including the reform of the Roman Curia, optional priestly celibacy, ordination of women, and various issues of sexual ethics. In addition, the new pope is expected to resolve urgent recent problems such as clerical sex abuse, gay

¹⁶ Note that I have not mentioned a specific theology in response to Communist and socialist ideologies, and this is of set purpose. I do not believe that the most effective counterresponse to these ideologies is a theoretical discussion of the metaphysical “proofs” of God’s existence. Rather the Church’s convincing “argument” for the belief in God is a relentless struggle for equality and justice, especially in favour of the poor and the oppressed.

marriage, the Vatican's financial scandals, the impact of globalization, climate change, and ecological destruction.

As it turned out, to the surprise of both conservatives and liberals, Bergoglio, who took il Poverello of Assisi not only as his name but also as his role model, began his pontificate by unostentatiously dropping the papal princely lifestyle, instituted sweeping changes in the Roman Curia, made many apostolic visits to far-flung places, participated collegially in several synods of bishops, and issued a series of ground-breaking documents, on the mission of Church (*The Joy of the Gospel*), ecology (*Laudato Si'* and *Querida Amazonia*), love in the family (*Amoris Laetitia*), and social friendship (*Fratelli Tutti*). Here I will not consider all the issues mentioned above but only one part of Francis's agenda that is very important to him but on which he has not devoted a full-fledged and comprehensive document. I refer to interreligious dialogue, or to use Francis' preferred expression, interreligious *encounter*.

As is well known, with *Nostra Aetate*, the Catholic Church made a volte-face in its assessment of other religions. Though the shortest of all the 16 conciliar documents, with only 1,141 words in 41 sentences and 5 paragraphs in the original Latin, the declaration improbably became the magna carta of the Church's relations with non-Christian religions. Of course, there lacked no vigorous opposition to the various postconciliar initiatives and theologies of interreligious dialogue, as the condemnation of several theological writings on religious pluralism and the declaration *Dominus Iesus* of the Congregation for the Doctrine of the Faith (2000) under Ratzinger/Benedict XVI readily show. Francis inherited a contentious and ambiguous legacy on interreligious dialogue but has consistently and firmly pledged to promote mutual understanding between the Catholic Church and other religions.

So far, there is still a dearth of scholarly investigations of Pope Francis's activities and thought on interreligious dialogue.¹⁷ In general, Francis

¹⁷ A significant study of Pope Francis's understanding of interreligious dialogue in English is Harold Kasimow, Alan Race, and Rabbi Abraham Skorka, eds., *Pope Francis and Interreligious Dialogue: Religious Thinkers Engage with Recent Papal Initiatives* (New York: Palgrave Macmillan,

approaches interreligious dialogue primarily as a pastor and a practical theologian and not as a systematic theologian, like Benedict XVI, concerned with expounding on the theological issues implicated in the dialogue between Christianity and non-Christian religions. Here I will not chronicle Francis's activities in favour of interreligious dialogue, especially his many meetings with the leaders of other religions, in particular the Grand Imam Ahmed Al-Tayyeb of Egypt, with whom he signed the historic "Document on Human Fraternity for World Peace and Living Together." Rather I will reflect on the pronouncements Francis made on interreligious encounter on disparate occasions to see if they open the door for re-thinking Catholic traditional teachings on the major issues involving interreligious dialogue.

One of Pope Francis's key refrains is that interreligious dialogue is an indispensable and effective way to resolve all kinds of conflicts (not just religious), restore peace and harmony, build up social justice, and preserve ecological integrity. Already in his very first writing, *Evangelii Gaudium* (EG, nos. 238-258), Francis speaks of dialogue in three areas to promote full human development and the common good: dialogue with states, dialogue with society, including cultures and the sciences, and dialogue with non-Catholic Christians (ecumenical dialogue) and non-Christian believers (interreligious dialogue). In his latest encyclical *Fratelli Tutti* Francis comes closest to formulating his theology of interreligious dialogue (FT, nos. 271-285.) It is most noteworthy that in both documents Francis places interreligious dialogue in the context of *social* dialogue, the goal of which is "to establish friendship, peace and harmony, and to share spiritual and moral values and experiences in a spirit of truth and love" (FT, no. 271).

This approach is Francis's both strengths and weaknesses. On the one hand, it harnesses the energies of all religions to achieve concrete and tangible goals, not least the elimination of religious violence. On the other hand, it moves away from doctrinal dialogue and leaves unexamined and

2018). Leo Lefebure's final assessment (303-328) is particularly insightful.

unchanged the *theological* claims that have fuelled suspicion, hatred, and violence in the first place. Among these claims are, for instance,

- The uniqueness and universality of Jesus as saviour;
- The truth and superiority of Christianity over all other religions; the divine origin of Christian revelation, sacred books, and rituals in contrast to the purely human character of those of other religions;
- The missionary obligation to “proclaim” the Gospel to all;
- The necessity of converting other believers and unbelievers to Christianity, and more specifically, to the Catholic Church, which alone and exclusively has all the means of salvation.

Admittedly, these theological claims, central in traditional Catholic theology of religion, *by themselves* do not lead to violence but when backed up by Christians’ superior economic, political, military, and colonial powers, which were not rare, together they made a combustible mix to ignite oppression and war against other believers and unbelievers. Left untouched, they threaten to derail the very objectives Francis sets for interreligious encounters.

To date, Francis has not dealt explicitly with any of these Christian claims. He has simply repeated Vatican II’s teaching on the possibility of salvation for all, including non-Christian and unbelievers, as contained especially in *Lumen Gentium*, no. 16, *Ad Gentes*, no. 9, and *Nostra Aetate*. He insists that “evangelization and interreligious dialogue, far from being opposed, mutually support and nourish each other” and that a “facile syncretism” must be avoided in interreligious dialogue (*EG*, no. 251). He maintains that in interreligious dialogue Christians must hold on to their “Christian identity” (*FT*, no. 277). His continued use of traditional expressions to designate Christian mission such as “proclamation” implies that the Church has the whole truth to teach non-Christians

with authority (“proclaim”) and has little if anything to learn from them.

On the other hand, some of Francis’ statements seem to open the door, however slightly, for revising and modifying the current teachings of the Catholic Church on the issues listed above. He acknowledges that God’s work in non-Christians “tends to produce signs and rites, sacred expressions which in turn brings others to a communitarian experience of journeying towards God” (*EG*, no. 254). In other words, it is God who establishes what we call non-Christian “religions” and therefore non-Christian religions lie within the divine economy of salvation. Francis even calls them “channels which the Holy Spirit raises up to liberate non-Christians from atheistic immanentism or from purely individual religious experiences,” even though they “lack the meaning and efficacy of the sacraments instituted by Christ” (*EG*, no. 254). “Channels” used by the Holy Spirit may be regarded as the equivalents of Christian “sacraments.”

Furthermore, Francis explicitly acknowledges that interreligious dialogue can be “a process in which, by mutual listening, both parts [Christian and non-Christian] can be purified and enriched” (*EG*, no. 250). The pope pointedly notes that Christians can benefit from the teachings and practices of other religions to be better Christians (*EG*, no. 254). In this way, Christian mission is not to be understood as a one-directional activity of Christians to non-Christians (*missio ad gentes*) but a reciprocal “evangelization” among other believers (*missio inter gentes*) and with them (*missio cum gentibus*). As for conversion, Pope Francis says that in fraternal/sisterly dialogue “with my identity and my empathy, my openness, I walk with the other. I don’t try to make him come over me. I don’t proselytize.” He acknowledges that God will move hearts and someone will ask for baptism, sometimes not. But always let us walk together. This is the heart of dialogue” (On the 6th Asian Youth Day Meeting with the Bishops of Asia, 17 August 2014).

One of Francis' favorite images for interreligious dialogue and the "culture of encounter" is the polyhedron "whose different sides for a variegated unity in which the whole is greater than the part" and the sum of its parts (*FT*, no. 215). He strongly urges that we create "a social covenant": "Such a covenant also demands the realization that some things may have to be renounced for the common good. No one can possess the whole truth or satisfy his or her every desire since that pretension would lead to nullifying others by denying their rights" (*FT*, 111). Should not this statement be applied to the Church as a whole as well, and if so, which of its traditional teachings on other religions will have to be "renounced" or at least modified "for the common good"?

It is not the task of the pope to make dogmatic pronouncements on these still-unresolved issues, but at least his statements leave the door open and encourage theologians to explore them in the context of religious pluralism, especially in Asia. In this endeavour they are guided by Pope Francis's four principles: first, time is greater than space; second, unity prevails over conflict; third, realities are more important than ideas; and fourth, the whole is greater than the sum of its parts (*EG*, nos. 222-237). Accordingly, all the truths must be contextualized in their history and development; doctrinal differences must not lead to division and conflict; ideas can never exhaustively capture reality and must be revised constantly to fully reflect reality; and, individual truths must be seen as part of a whole that is greater than each of them and gives validity to them. Meanwhile, as theological explorations are being carried out, the Church must exercise its evangelizing mission in the only way possible, namely, sincere and humble dialogue and fraternal encounter, to build up justice and peace, as Pope Francis and the Federation of Asian Bishops' Conferences never tire to insist. In this way, Asian Catholicism and Asian theologians can make a significant contribution to a new understanding of the nature of the Church, its mission, and its relations to other religions.

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Living on the Edge of Hackable Life: Commoditization of Human Privacy

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Abstract: Coronavirus has hacked our bodily life and we are all running for safety. It is possible to not just possible to hack our bodies but also our mind and free will. New development in AI and the growing surveillance capitalism has made it possible to hack into our minds and will. New technologies like blockchain can save our mind and freedom of will. But there is a cost that we have to pay to save it. It is a loss of privacy. The loss of privacy then is not seen as a loss as it becomes raw material that can be sold as passive work. Blockchain backed economy is set to transform the way we trust but it will commoditize our privacy and over its benefits to us. As things our today, our privacy already stands commoditized but its economic benefits are monopolized by Big data analytics. An example of this is the recent pegaus controversy.

Keywords: Coronavirus, Hackable Life, Blockchain, Human Vulnerability, Cybertopia, Surveillance Capitalism

Cronavirus has hacked our bodily life and we are all running for safety. It has set an algorithm into our bodies to reproduce itself.

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So far, we find that it has been medically impossible to reverse it. We are fast realising that algorithms define our lives both biologically as well as socio-politically (Harari, 2019). All life on earth is running in the power of algorithms that nature and the divine have inscribed into it. A view that sees evolution of life as an unfolding of algorithms seems to be a way forward for science. This means humans too are driven through these algorithms. This is why we are hackable. Coronavirus has hacked us biologically. But the impacts of this event will leave a lasting imprint on the canvas of our life. Besides, hacking our biology, the novel virus has hacked our economy, our government, our medical establishment, and our leadership whether religious or political. We are indeed living into a new brave world of the algorithms that know us better than we know ourselves. We have to quickly understand this new world around us and find our ways to address it. The evangelists of the Big data world are pushing ahead a future that is already present (Ohlhorst, 2013). They are in a significant way hacking into our decision making ability. What would the world look like where algorithms designed to hack our personal lives reign? Our digital future is already present. It is said that algorithms are already taking several decisions in our lives. We are guided by computer codes or algorithms to find places, hotels, coffee houses, malls, theatres (Fratasi and Della Rosa, 2017: 20-23), etc. These codes enable us to make choices while we shop online. Our heart beats, sugar levels, blood pressure surges and several other intimate things are monitored by algorithms (Bohr and Memarzadeh, 2020: 20-24). We enjoy surrendering decision making to these smart codes. The question is, are algorithms able to make objective decisions? Algorithms work on the data. Data reflect human bias. We do not have adequate data. There is always missing data. That is why there is a margin of error. But we trust them because they seem to be doing a pretty good job. The algorithmic model of human life is fast becoming normal. It is going to influence our policing, justice administration, and health care. We are getting used to a hackable life.

Both biotech and InfoTech revolution are increasing our ability to hack our life. Yuval Noah Harari has exposed the consequences of these revolutions from the long term basis in his book, *Homo Deus: a Brief History of Tomorrow* (Harari, 2016), and has dwelt on the immediate consequences of this technology in his book, *21 Lessons for the 21st Century* (Harari, 2019). Following the trail of his work, in this study we attempt to study the impacts of InfoTech on us, particularly the impacts of Big Data analytics. Harari deals with this issue in depth in the third chapter of his book *21 Lessons for the 21st Century*. (Harari, 2019: 50-74). We begin our study by drawing our attention to human vulnerabilities as we surge through the digital world. Next, we focus on the lure of the cybertopia (Ebo, 1998: 2-5) and the fangs of surveillance capitalism (Zuboff, 2019). All is not dark about the InfoTech revolution that is unfolding around us. We have technological solutions like the block chain to increase our cyber security (Swan, 2015). We try to understand these possibilities in the two sections that follow our analysis of surveillance capitalism. The first section deals with the promises of block chain technologies while the next section studies game theory to explore the possibilities of tracing safeguards to face the growing network of surveillance capitalism. Our study comes to a conclusion that is a bit disheartening. It indicates that even if we find science that will not fail humanity, human dishonesty may find ways of failing science and technology.

The Digital World and Human Vulnerabilities

We are producing data all the time. Using social media platforms like Facebook, we are already leaving our data footprints as well as become accessible to engineered and customised algorithms that has the power to make choices for us. The primary goal of these algorithms like those used by Facebook or Goggle is to make us stay engaged on-line (Brockmann, 2013: 51). This increases our chances of receiving customised commercial or political messaging that can do the trick. We then click on the product / object of desire.

No prizes for guessing who stands to benefit in this process. But there are also good outcomes like the Arab spring. It is greeted as the Facebook revolution. These movements produce engagements and Big data companies prey on these engagements and milk them for profits. Negativity/ violence/ fear maximises engagement and increases the decimals of their success. The key to their success is simply getting us stay engaged to so-called their services that are free of cost. But there is no free coffee.

By engaging on their platforms, we leave data footprints that enable them to prey on our personal behavioural patterns that manifest our preferences and vulnerabilities by customising their messaging to suit the interest of the highest bidder (Singh, 2017: 286). The business model of these companies is fascist in character. They keep us engaged in our enjoyment of narcissism while they do the decision making for us. Negative sentiments like fear, resentment, hate, and hostility produce intensive engagement (Shen, 2019: 233). This is why we can trace how the increased quotient of fear and hate in our society leads to increased engagement into our echo-chambers in our social network platforms where we continue to hear our own voice or feed on our narcissism as we produce data that become the raw material for data mining companies to socially engineer our life. This is why we have to understand the business model of these platforms. This is urgent because when we hand over our decision making to an algorithm, we are actually handing over our decision making to a company that stays hidden while we feed on our narcissistic enjoyments.

Cambridge Analytica has already exhibited the dark sides of this fascist business model (Kaiser, 2019). These companies will not change their business model. It is we who have to become mindful of how their messaging is affecting our life. Coronavirus has hacked our life and we are rattled. But before that we have already mindlessly allowed our will power to be hacked in the social media platforms. We are already living on the edge of a hackable life. We

already have AI- Psychologists so to say who using psychodemographics and the predictive power of AI/ algorithms trap us into a life that is designed for us (Ravi et al, 2010: 183). Maybe the corona moment of humanity is a call to understand and address the strengths and vulnerabilities of living on the edge of hackable life. We cannot run away from the digital environment. We will produce data footprints of our intimate life. We cannot mindlessly live in the digital-hive. We will have to be mindful and critically choose our responses. We need to develop inbuilt resistances within us so that we are not lured and duped into doing things mindlessly. Being off-line is a luxury that we cannot afford. That is why we need to be good at being online and not just get lost in the narcissisms of our echo-chambers. We have to use computers but we cannot hand ourselves to computers and the algorithms. Algorithms with their predictive power are taking way options from the plate of our life. Technology actually should have given us options but algorithms take away options as we believe that they know what is best for us (Christian and Griffiths, 2016) This is why algorithms are fascists in character and they have to be kept within their limits. We cannot allow algorithms to hack our will power while we live on the edge of a hackable life.

Cybertopia and Surveillance Capitalism

We cannot unplug our digital life. It is the elite who can afford to disconnect. Some hotels offer digital detoxification for those who wish to live outside connectivity for some time (Syversten, 2020: 105). Steve Jobs did not want his children to have an iPad or iPhone (Keslowitz, 2020: 14). Most hi-tech people want to keep their children low-tech. The globe is covered by the digital web and we have no space to escape the digital life of our society. We have stepped into surveillance capitalism. A fascinating cybertopia is leading us and we are leaving data trails that are taking away our privacy and intimacy. We are becoming more and more data visible and it is difficult to cover ourselves and become invisible to the

probing of digital technologies. Maybe like the medical caregivers use a complete cover while treating patients of covid-19, we will need a kind of Faraday cage that will insulate and render us invisible to the probing of the digital spying technologies. But with the growth in AI and face recognition algorithms, this has become increasingly difficult. We are indeed living on the edge of hackability.

We cannot lock the virus with lockdowns likewise; we cannot lock away our hackability. Our connectivity to the web is everyday affair. The cyber optimists see the digital-hive as all milk and honey for us. The internet is positioned as the biggest free market. We are moving into virtual cities and virtual countries. The digital revolution is as dangerous as it is fantastic. E-stonia is greeted a start-up nation (Jennings, 2019: 116). It has about 1.5 million virtual citizens who have an e-residency (Estonia, 2015). It is open to all citizens of the world. Citizens enjoy digital identity and e-governance by taking digital residency. One can send and receive encrypted documents. One can sign directly and do business online without any hassles of regulations of local governments. The digital identity cannot be used by anyone except the person who is having it. No one can fake identity. This means cybersecurity becomes almost given. We are fast moving towards competing virtual identities. The identities that are given by Facebook and other social media platforms are hackable and so those who give us more secure identities will emerge victors. E-countries like E-stonia will offer services online where citizens become clients who pay for the services received. These developments may disrupt national boundaries and local governments will have to compete with these e-nations. Lines dividing states and countries will be bridged with digital passports (Khate, 2008: 207).

We are fast moving towards a cashless economy. Several e-wallets are in the market competing to get us to use them. But this is a step closer to a fascist's economy/ surveillance capitalism. It means

every single transaction that we do will be monitored and recorded by some bank somewhere. The cash economy offers us space to spend money without anyone knowing where one is spending it. Governments have plugged this freedom with some upper limit to cash spending. In this context, Bitcoin which is an electronic equivalent to cash becomes interesting because it is cryptocurrency. We are already hit by the bitcoin gospel (Campbell-Verduyn, 2018). It is preaching that we can be our own bank and is positioned as a financial miracle. It has no transaction fees and is lightning quick. It eliminates the central bank. One can mine the bitcoins by solving complex mathematical problems online (Armstrong, 2017: 16). All the bitcoin miners are linked to what is called the blockchain where they have an individual account or wallet (Jain, 2020: 69). Bitcoin is viewed as an ultimate remedy against invasive state interventions (Werback, 2019: 158). Some think that bitcoin is like the French revolution that separated Church from State. Bitcoin is separating money from the banks and the State (Dodd, 2017: 197). It is not democratising the economy but elitizing it. This is because a bitcoin owned by anyone cannot be invested by someone else like the way banks do with our savings. But it does serve as a counter-power and form of protest to the existing banking system. So far bitcoin code is not hacked. There is a steady growth of bitcoin as a medium of exchange. Just like the value of gold is largely constructed by humans association with it. Bitcoins are also growing in value in a similar fashion. Average persons today cannot become bitcoin miners but the bitcoin community is growing. The community grows because people buy bitcoins.

The blockchain on which bitcoin works is a global open ledger (Brito & Castillo, 2013: 4). It can be used for several other things besides money and is seen as a great invention. But this is where we are fast getting trapped into a fascist economy that is pushing uniformity hard on to the global community. Although all the members of the blockchain are treated as equal and enjoy a form of

digital democracy, the fact that they have to work in the same model and are watched by every other member on the public ledger draws it into the fascist mode of operation. But blockchain brings total transparency and yet keep individual privacy safe. This means it can be used by criminals and maybe also used to fund terror. Block chain technology is fascinating and cannot be ignored. May be it promotes distributed consensus. The only problem with it is that it is taking away heterogeneity and leads us to embrace sameness. It can make the world flat for all. But it will do away with the diversity of the world. It has the power to change the world the way we experience it.

The question still remains. Why are we so fascinated by e-life? Although there are several issues with it yet lured by its promises. The question boils down why we are enjoying living on the edge of hackable life. My hunch is that it is because it offers us space to indulge in the enjoyment of narcissisms. May be there are other reasons too. At a time, when our bodily life is hacked by the novel virus, we have to understand our hackability and find adequate responses so that we can stay safe as we live on the edge of hackable life. A new technology called blockchain has a promise of increasing trust among people. It is an algorithm behind Bitcoin. It brings transparency to us. Some Governments are trying to build a block chained based Governance. It is a data-based technology and because of its architecture it is said that it enables everyone to trust the system. It is a tool of decentralisation and direct participation. It is attractive because it disrupts gatekeepers of different levels who mediate our interactions and renders them unnecessary.

Facing the Future that Is Already Present

Blockchain increases Collaboration. They say that it records everything and helps fixing responsibility and accountability. It gives us the visibility of all transactions becomes new trust architecture (Werback, 2018). It is a revolutionary technology and is largely secure because its algorithms are difficult to hack.

Blockchain can give us some control over our digital traces. Blockchain can assist us to expand our democracy, built smart cities, and put e-administration to work efficiently (Allen, 2019: vii-viii). In simple terms blockchain can operate as a trusted third party. The blockchain does open new opportunities to humanity. Blockchain is an algorithm that has asymmetric cryptography and distributed systems. It is a network system that is decentralised. Alibaba, Uber, Facebook and the like are centralised networks. It is not a rider to the driver but a rider to Uber to the driver system. Blockchain eliminates the middle man (Alli, et al, 2020: 86). We need the middle man/ institution to facilitate trust. Blockchain will change the way we trust. It does not need any central authority. It produces a ledger that is indelible and not tamperable (Subramanian, 2020: 13). It will do away with the intermediaries like banks and other registries, that stand between us.

We trust the intermediary more than the party with which we are transacting. But with the blockchain ledgers are created in real-time and these ledgers are indelible, immutable, and distributed. Thus, the information can be trusted and accessed in real-time. Blockchain has the power to fill the gap of trust in our transactions by writing one single universal ledger. Though there is only one ledger. It is a distributed ledger giving simultaneous access to all members in the chain. There is something totally different happening in the blockchain. We are moving away from a centralised trust backed by the mediating institutions to distributed trust. It is this distributed trust that is at the heart and soul of a blockchain. This is why it appears that mediating services, especially online are on the way out. It sets us to create trust companies that will replace every other company in the world. Blockchain technology has multiple applications. It is set to create a transparent economy. Besides finances, blockchain can manage our healthcare, our education system, land title registries, and trace product journeys / supply chains, political elections, and the like. It is said that it can be applied to our work.

Work may be seen as active and passive. Some corporates may be willing to pay for the passive work that we do without being conscious because it brings value to them. For now, our engagements on Facebook bring value to it and it uses it in the form of messaging to benefit the commercial or political interest. But we are paid nothing. This can change with a blockchain. We can be on Facebook like peer to peer interaction platforms where our data footprints as well as what they do with the data footprint are visible on the universal ledger. But will they do it? It will puncture their messaging adverts as they require us to be in darkness. It does not suit their business model. The face of Facebook is hidden from us. We cannot see what they do with our data traces and how much they earn on the raw material that is provided by us. This is because Facebook is a centralized network. Blockchain is a decentralised network/chain that is transparent and greatly intemparable. The fact that we can see how our passive work is creating value is important to be able to get paid for our passive work. If Facebook is re-invented using the blockchain they will have to compensate us for that value our passive work is creating for them.

We are emitting data everywhere. This data becomes the raw material for commercial as well as political interests. But no one is paid for it. There may be possibilities of earning if this data mining technologies take us on the blockchain. With the growth of the internet of things, we may be able to share surplus electric power or even storage/ processing capacity of our laptops/ computers that we are not using and get paid through a blockchain (Mougayar, 2016: 114). Corporates like Facebook may generate crypto-currencies like the bitcoin (internet of money). Our engagement time and content on Facebook may become like mining a bitcoin. This means we may get paid with crypto-currencies that we can spend or exchange in our market. We are fast moving into a blockchain economy that will care for everyone who is on the chain.

While thinking about our vulnerabilities and our hackable condition, we are facing a future that can be borderless and transparent. Becoming more transparent, we can build an informed and just society. It is a great tool against corruption and is designed to build equity. The new blockchain technology will not just change how we transfer value, but could dramatically change of systems of identity and Governance. It is a new type of shared database which has a single point of reference to truth. Living in a post-truth world, blockchain technology becomes vital. Given its security strengths and intemperabilty, it is our best chance as we are already on the edge of hackability. Privacy still is a risk as all people on the chain have access to the universal ledger. But abuse of it is difficult on a blockchain. Blockchain, for now, is difficult to hack but what will happen in the future only time will tell us. But for now, living on the edge of hackability, our best bet is blockchain technology and we cannot ignore it. It is resourceful because it is public and permanent. But we will not be completely out of a fascist economy since we will not have privacy on the blockchain technology.

Striving for a Liveable Present

There is a link to Game theory with blockchain (Alzahrani, et al, 465-470). Game theory is viewed as a science of decision making. It is the mathematics behind the decisions we make. Some say the game of poker influenced game theory. It is a way of analysing strategic situation (Webster, 2014: XII). Strategic situations are instances where the outcome of our action is not just depending on our own actions but on the actions of someone else. coronavirus pandemic situation is one instance of a strategic situation where the likelihood of us catching the infection does not just depend on our action but the actions of the human vectors of the virus. We can see our condition as competition against the virus or as cooperation with each other to save our bodily life from being hacked by the virus. Game theory helps us to understand both competitions as well as cooperation. It is also about decision taken in self-interest.

There are times when the decisions taken in self-interest are competitive and there are decisions taken in self interest also cooperative.

The blockchain deals with decisions taken in self-interest that become cooperative. This reminds us of the invisible hand of the market of Adam Smith. It teaches us that in a free market, each of the players has to simply pursue their self-interest. As a result of this pursuit of self interest, there will be a balancing invisible hand of the market that will give each player what he / she deserves. Although this system appears just, it is heavily loaded on the side of the powerful players. Game theory actually improves the invisible hand of the market proposed by Smith. It teaches that the invisible hand works only in special instances and not all the time. Blockchain along with game theory can democratically actualize this instance. There are two kinds of games. They are finite games and infinite games (Carse, 1986). Most games are finite. Finite games are based on known players, fixed rules, and known objectives. The objective is to win the game. Football, cricket, baseball, etc., are finite games. An infinite game is defined by known and unknown players, where the rules are changeable and the objective is to perpetuate the game or stay in the game as long as possible (Thomas, n.d.). In an infinite game, there are no losers and winners. We cannot lose the game. This is why the players keep playing the game. The only way an infinite game comes to a halt when players run out of resources or will to play. Business, life, simple conversation, cold wars and jobs, are instances of infinite games.

Infinite games are basically based on our values while finite games are based on our interest. In an infinite game, one is either ahead or behind. But it is easy to slide down and treat the infinite game as a finite game and look to win when there is no room for winning (Mundo, 2020). The reality of an infinite game is that one is only competing against oneself. Every time one reaches a horizon, one

can see new possibilities to move on with the game. The infinite game does not consume us but generate us. The finite game can be played into an infinite game but we cannot play the infinite game in a finite game. Game theory has Nash equilibrium, a point where each player stands to benefit while pursuing his own self-interest (*Prisoner's Dilemma*, 2020). It is the point when the players know the strategy of the other player but he/ she has no incentive to change his/ her strategy. Nash equilibrium was beautifully presented by the movie, a beautiful mind (Witmer, 2014: 117). Nash equilibria can be traced in infinite games too. Nash equilibrium is a point of cooperation. It is the best response that the players can give in a game. This may be a point at which blockchain and game theory meets. Most games have at least one Nash equilibria but it is not easy to trace it. Nash equilibrium is not the dominant strategy of the players. It is a non-dominant strategy but it produces a win-win situation for all.

With all its strengths about its security blockchain is still attackable by human dishonesty. One way to further improve its security and efficiency is said to be provided by game theory. Blockchain does not consider the human factor. Humans on the chain may be dishonest and deviate from the protocols of validation that they have to observe and thus undermining the consensus process. Game theory assists blockchain to bring honesty among the human players. It is done by introducing game theoretical models into the consensus protocol to reward the honest and to punish the dishonest validators that do not adhere to the protocols (Bikramaditya et al, 2018). There are several efforts to combine game theory to improve the participation of humans to build distributed consensus. Blockchain provides the architecture for a distributed consensus building. It is humans who have to work on this architecture and build consensus. This is why the human factor is very central to the quality of consensus-building that is produced on the blockchain. The issue becomes important because humans may randomly join or are placed at certain nodes of the blockchain by authorities.

The human factor can attack the consensus-building protocols in several ways. Human judgement can err. Bias or greed can influence us. Hence, models of game theory are used to incentivize humans to follow the protocols of the blockchain honestly. Bitcoin, for instance, motivates the miners to use their computing power to secure the network by rewarding them with bitcoins (economic incentive). The consensus among the nodes is reached by proof-of-work (PoW) which reflects the real, quantifiable resources it took to get there. Blockchain and game theory when combined show that we can collectively grow when each of us is honestly promoting his/her interest. While we are reflecting on how we are pushed today to live on the edge of a hackable life, maybe game theory can illumine our present condition. We are playing an infinite game and we have to continue to stay in the game and stay safe. Coronavirus is playing an infinite game with us. But in this infinite game, we can play a finite game and defeat it. Life is indeed an infinite game. Let the game go on.

Conclusion

It is possible to not just possible to hack our bodies but also our mind and free will. New development in AI and the growing surveillance capitalism has made it possible to hack into our minds and will. New technologies like blockchain can save our mind and freedom of will. But there is a cost that we have to pay to save it. It is a loss of privacy. The loss of privacy then is not seen as a loss as it becomes raw material that can be sold as passive work. Blockchain backed economy is set to transform the way we trust but it will commoditize our privacy and over its benefits to us. As things our today, our privacy already stands commoditized but its economic benefits are monopolized by Big data analytics. The blockchain technology also with game theory can assist us to reap the benefits of our visibility and connectivity online. It can also check human tendency to win by inflicting losses on others. It can transform self-interest from being competitive to cooperative. We may cooperate with the service providers who use our private data and receive payment for

sharing it with them. But this means we get co-opted into the surveillance capitalism. Some may say that this is a lesser evil as we get compensated for our digital visibility. But the truth will remain that we would sink deeper into the clutches of the fascist economy. The recent Pegasus controversy is one example of such self-interest spying over the rivals (Duggal, 2021).

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John Henry Newman and His Untiring Quest for the Truth: The Magisterium and Personal Conscience

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Abstract: Conscience is the living sanctuary in Person. Precisely because we have a moral conscience-, we ought to seek the truth and so shape our choices and our lives accordance with the Truth. John Henry Newman did not write a theological treatise on conscience, but it played a significant role in his life (Autobiographical essay “Apologia Pro vita Sua”). His prayer life, intellect and his conscience led him from the Anglican Church to the Catholic Church. Conscience was for him the guiding light in his life. The uniqueness of his notion of conscience lies in his emphasis on conscience in relation to freedom, responsibility and belief in God. This recast helped to protect the dignity of conscience also in view of the papal dogma on the infallibility of the pope: “Certainly, if I am obliged to bring religion into after-dinner toasts ... I shall drink – to the Pope, if you please – still, to Conscience first, and to the Pope afterwards.”

Keywords: John Henry Newman, Conscience, Dignity of human person, Truth, Existence of God, One Church, papal infallibility.

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Amidst many voices and noises around us, the mild echo of the conscience is often unheeded. The sacred conscience in each person is an unyielding authority and has Devine purpose. Obeying it means conforming to the will of God and experiencing the freedom.

The Magisterium versus Personal Conscience

The Catholic Church in ninetieth and twentieth Century was struggling, with not only political developments in Europe (aftermath of French Revolution, collapse of Papal States) weakening of ecclesiastical influence, but also to grasp the relation between individual conscience of the faithful and the fidelity to the teaching of the Church (Magisterium). One of the leading historian and ecclesiastical figure embroiled in the conflict between the papal Authority and the personal conscience was the German Priest and Professor Ignaz von Doellinger (1799-1890). He was one of the most learned and influential Scholars of his time and became later a staunch opponent of temporal power of the Pope (Howard, 2017: 1-15). John Henry Newman (1801-1890) and the British Prime Minister William E. Gladstone (1809-1898) were among many his friends. Doellinger found himself caught up in a fierce conflict between his personal conscience and papal authority, between his conviction and Church doctrine. He refused to accept the doctrine of papal infallibility promulgated at the First Vatican Council (Doellinger, 1862), and because of his non-acceptance of the conciliar Doctrine, he was ex-communicated. John Henry Newman remarks over Doellinger: “As to Doellinger ... the case is quite tragic.” Newman showed his solidarity for Doellinger (Ward, 1912: 438-9).

Johann Joseph Ignanz von Doellinger was not just a simple Catholic priest, but a most authoritative and well-versed church historian. His well-articulated opposition to the teaching of papal infallibility bears witness to it (Doellinger, under pseudonym- Janus, 1869). Here he criticizes the notion of papal infallibility and found its promulgation inopportune. It throws light on the integrity of his

personality itself as a man of intellectual integrity and of deep convictions. His commitment to the truth and conscience demanded an enormous price. Doellinger himself gave justification of his position. “Because...if I did so in a question which is for the historical eye perfectly clear and unambiguous, there would then be no longer for me any such thing as historical truth and certainty; I should then have to suppose that my whole life long I had been in a world of dizzy illusion, and that in historical matters I am altogether incapable of distinguishing truth from fable and falsehood (Cited in Sparrow-Simpson, 1909: 324).

The apprehensions regarding the consequences from the new doctrine of the infallibility of the Pope raised doubts and demanded elucidation. The papacy was under sustained attack and many Theologians tried their best to defend the claims of the Church. Unlike Doellinger, John Henry Newman saw the need to explain the relationship between conscience and obedience towards Church authority in a manner, which avoided confrontation and solicited dialogue. He himself was wrestling with the consequences of an exaggerated understanding of papal authority. Deeply stirred over the decision of the Council to define the dogma of the infallibility of the Pope and fearing possible reactions from Catholics and non-Catholics, Newman wrote to his Ordinary of Birmingham, Bishop William B. Ullathorne, expressing his disapproval against defining papal infallibility: “If it is God’s Will that Pope’s Infallibility should be defined, then it is His Blessed Will to throw back the times and the moments of that triumph He has destined for His Kingdom; and I shall feel I have to bow my head to His adorable inscrutable Providence. You have not touched on the subject yourself, but I think you will allow me to express to you my feelings which for the most part I keep to myself” (Letter to the Bishop 28.01.1870, Ward, 1913: 288-289).

For Newman, his interest was not primarily to vindicate the papacy or papal teaching, but much deeper, to explore the Truth from

different angles and understand it in its context. He was not a man of extremes but the apostle of *via media*. Avery Dulles gives a clear assessment and judgment regarding the position of John Henry Newman towards the papal infallibility. “He writes as if caught between two mindsets, unable to choose between them. He is torn by two sets of fears. When he looks at the ultramontane curialists, he speaks almost as a liberal, defending the rights of private judgment and conscience against the harsh impositions of authority. But when he contemplates the rapid spread of infidelity, he rushes to the defense of centralized authority. Thus he is at one moment the ally of Döllinger and the Gallicans and at the next moment the admirer of Cardinal Dechamps and the papalists. He wavers and sometimes contradicts his own previous statements” (Dulles, 1990: 449). Unfortunately, the theology of Newman has been often misinterpreted und distorted. In order avoid false interpretation of his teaching; we must get to his own original words and his authentic teaching. The role of conscience in the moral and spiritual life of Christian is one of the central themes of Newman’s theological research. Then, the person is for him defined by his conscience. No temporal advantages and gains can override the principles of conscience without causing lasting harm to the person.

Vatican I and the Papal Primacy

The First Vatican Council in his dogmatic Constitution on the Church of Christ “*Pastor Aeternus*” defined on 18th July 1870 that: “... we teach and define that is a dogma Divinely revealed that the Roman pontiff when he speaks *ex cathedra*, that is when in discharge of the office of pastor and doctor of all Christians, by virtue of his supreme Apostolic authority, he defines a doctrine regarding faith or morals to be held by the universal Church, by the Divine assistance promised to him in Blessed Peter, is possessed of the infallibility with which the Divine Redeemer willed that his Church should be endowed in defining doctrine regarding faith or morals, and that therefore such definitions of the Roman pontiff are

of themselves, and not from the consent of the church, irreformable” (Ch. 4). Newman lived in a time of great religious and political turmoil. He knew all about political under-currents and felt the brunt of non-Catholic misunderstanding and some Catholic rejection. Amidst all controversies and confrontations, he was guided and led by his unflinching conscience as a natural mode to hear God’s Voice. This same concept of conscience he brought into relation with ecclesiastical authority, which he accepted as divinely ordained to root out errors and face challenges, which were confronted by the Church.

Although the fears and uncertainties regarding the doctrine of infallibility were genuine but not shattering, Doellinger remains unreconciled and is a victim of misunderstanding papal authority and the conscience. Thomas Howard in his Book “The Pope and the Professor” juxtaposes Doellinger with Pope Pius IX. Doellinger considered papalism and in particular the doctrine of papal infallibility counter to the modern, enlightened Christianity, which he represented. In this matter of controversy, a question can be raised: Were the Roman Pontiffs generally against the freedom of conscience? Pope Pius IX spoke in his Encyclical “Quanta cura” 1864 against “liberty of conscience and refers to his predecessor, Pope Gregory XVI., who called it in his encyclical “Mirari vos” 1832 a “deliramentum” (insanity). Pope Gregory XVI condemned the extreme liberalism, which permitted all kinds of groundless, libelous and subversive public opinions, without any legal restrictions. He termed such conception of freedom of conscience as “deliramentum” according to which “freedom of conscience must be asserted und vindicated for everyone whatsoever.” Newman sought to explain the true nature of conscience. The “liberty of conscience” as condemned by “Quanta cura” has not to do with true nature of freedom of conscience, but with the “liberty of self-will”. The Church does not support such an understanding or opinions of the liberty of conscience. Conscience is bound to uphold the truth in the same way the papacy is bound to uphold the truth. Despite the

hopes and fears of the moment, the papal infallibility been specifically invoked only on certain solemn occasions like in 1854 defining the dogma of Mary's Immaculate Conception or in 1950 to define the dogma of her bodily assumption into Heaven. The dogmatic constitution *Lumen gentium* of the Second Vatican Council explicitly reaffirmed the teaching of the First Vatican Council on papal Infallibility (*Lumen gentium*, LG, Art. 25).

The personality of John Henry Newman is an exemplar, shining sign for modern man. He transmitted through his remarkable writings and teachings a perfect example of authenticity, courage and perseverance. He was unmoved through the false charges against him, defended his convictions out of faith and conscience. An interesting aspect of his personal integrity is the connection between conscience and truth. It is a connection, which enables one to detect his personal life of faith and his theological quest. Newman's personal journey to catholic faith is an impressive endorsement of the fundamental conviction of conscience. He sought Truth in religion at all cost and adapted the traditional notion of conscience by emphasizing more the connection of conscience to human freedom, responsibility and relationship to God. To understand Newman's theological understanding of the conscience, we must know his three conversions, which are steps along the spiritual path. The first conversion he had as a young boy and it is a conversion to true faith in the living God. Newman had spiritual experience of God as the living reality. More than natural things Newman recognized that God and the Soul, man's spiritual identity, constitute what is genuinely real.

John Henry Newman: Rome and Not Canterbury the True Church

Arguably, the most renowned convert of the 19th century to Catholic Church is John Henry Newman. At the age of 44, John Henry became a Roman Catholic and was ordained a Roman Catholic priest. Before he graduated from Trinity College, Oxford

and he was an Anglican vicar of St. Mary's University Church. In 1833 John along with few others, initiated a spiritual and doctrinal renewal of Anglican Church, which was known as the "Oxford movement." The Oxford movement was the name given to the endeavours and plans of a group of Anglican Clergymen at Oxford University in 1830s. This Movement sought to restore Catholic faith and practice within the Anglican Church. Its founding members were John Keble (1792-1866) Professor of poetry, Edward Bouverie Pusey (1800-1892) Professor of Hebrew and John Henry Newman, vicar of St. Mary's and fellow of Oriel. To promote their ideas for the renewal of the Anglican Church they preferred a series of publications called "tracts" -hence they were later known as tracterians. They wrote tracts that called the British Protestants back to the historical roots of their faith and urging a more serious attitude toward doctrine and church discipline.

This Anglo-Catholic movement was to move the Church of England away from Protestantism towards a middle way "via media" between Anglicanism and Roman Catholicism. The main conviction shared by the movement was that England had lost the Faith of the Ancient Church Fathers and that it needed a (second Reformation) a comeback to the original Church. While still in Oxford, Newman questioned his own spiritual path within the Anglican Church. He prayed for light and guidance and followed a strict religious life. In his eagerness to find the true Nature of the one Church, Newman started to study the development of Christian doctrine. He started with the Church fathers and came to quick conclusion: "To be deep in history is to cease to be Protestant." In his book "An Essay on the Development of Christian Doctrine", he found the living connection between the apostolic faith and the Catholic Church. The Catholic Church is the continuation of the community founded by Jesus. Newman begins there explaining how true development in doctrine occur. He presents the unfolding of the teaching from the apostolic to the present time. Church has tried to safeguard the true teaching of Christ. The Catholic doctrine is the

evolving of the same faith, which was in seminal form and has now blossomed into doctrine and dogmas. There is no corruption or innovation in the teaching of the Church. The path to such a profound understanding was triggered by his conscience, which pondered seriously on the nature of the Church. In order to understand his decision to leave the Anglican Church, we must know the nature of conscience according to Newman.

Conscience the Path to Truth

Newman chose the inscription on his grave, “*Ex umbris et imaginibus in veritatem*” – “Out of shadows and images into truth.” That was truly his life’s maxim. He dedicated his life in searching and following the Truth and was fully committed to it, no matter what price he had to pay. His decision to join the Catholic Church costed him not only his position at Oxford University, but also damaged his friendships and reputation (Schockenhoff, 2003: 122-143). Some Catholics and many Anglicans became distrustful of him. However, his passion for Truth gained him new friends and companions, but above all, he valued to be at home in the true Church of Christ. Admittedly, “what is truth?” (Jn 18,38) This question posed to Jesus by Pilate continues to echo until today. Newman was restless and he sought to answer, what is truth. In his famous Novel titled *Callista: A Tale of the Third Century*, speaks out one of the Characters: “The Truth! ... What is truth?” (Newman, 1901: 249). Truth is an indispensable guide to men; it acts like a compass in his moral and faith life.

Newman saw a deeper connection between Conscience and Truth. His numerous statements about conscience are most striking and relevant texts, which he left for us. Not by chance, he is called *Doctor conscientiae* or teacher of conscience. The most conclusive certainty for the existence of God for Newman was in the testimony of conscience and not through the argument of logic (Boekraad-Tristram, 1961). Newman laid emphasis on the certainty of his own existence in feeling, experiencing and sensing. He found and

experienced God in the voice of his own conscience, a supreme Governor and Judge, which confirmed the existence of God. From this basic connection between Conscience and Truth, we can see the consequence in his personal life of faith and in his theological understanding. No other influence can be traced in his vivid search for truth and his fundamental conviction, “conscience as the advocate of truth in the innermost part of the human person” (Geissler, 2012: 1). If the human conscience is of paramount importance then it cannot be self-sufficient and arbitrary, hence, it calls for lifelong obedience to objective truth.

In his serious analysis of the phenomenon of conscience, Newman differentiates two functions or dimensions of the same conscience: namely, moral sense and sense of duty. He describes the sublime-character of conscience in a magnificent way: “The rule and measure of duty is not utility, nor expedience, nor the happiness of the greatest number, nor State convenience, nor fitness, order, and the pulchrum. Conscience is not a long-sighted selfishness, nor a desire to be consistent with oneself, but it is a messenger from Him, who, both in nature and in grace, speaks to us behind a veil, and teaches and rules us by His representatives. Conscience is the aboriginal Vicar of Christ, a prophet in its informations, a monarch in its peremptoriness, a priest in its blessings and anathemas, and, even though the eternal priesthood throughout the Church could cease to be, in it the sacerdotal principle would remain and would have a sway” (Newman, 1896: 248f.) The understanding and role of conscience goes beyond knowledge to action. It is an authority, which inspires to act.

In his spiritual autobiographical book *Apologia Pro vita Sua (A defence of one’s own life)*, Newman tells that his search brought him the right home for his faith. In Chapter 10 of his book *Grammar of Assent*, Newman sums up the importance of having an active conscience: “Conscience is nearer to me than any other means of knowledge. And as it is given to me, so also is it given to others;

and being carried about by every individual in his own breast, and requiring nothing besides itself, it is thus adapted for the communication to each separately of that knowledge which is most momentous to him individually,— adapted for the use of all classes and conditions of men, for high and low, young and old, men and women independently of books, of educated reasoning, of physical knowledge, or of philosophy. Conscience, too, teaches us, not only that God is, but He is; it provides for the mind a real image of Him, as a medium of worship; it gives us a rule of right and wrong, as being His rule, and a code of moral duties” (Newman, 1958: 390). Like Newman, everyone has to form his conscience, examine it and obey it under all circumstances.

Conscience: A Path to True Faith

Another decisive step in the life of Newman, which is a consequence of his understanding of conscience, is obviously the obedience to God as the Redeemer and the quest for the fullness of truth in the one Church of Christ. The question of the one Church of Christ is ultimately connected to the question of Salvation. According to Newman, the obedience to conscience form an “*organum investigandi* given us for gaining religious truth, and which would lead the mind by an infallible succession from the rejection of atheism to theism, and from theism to Christianity, and from Christianity to Evangelical Religion, and from these to Catholicity” (Newman, 1874: 499). It is interesting because Newman before his conversion to Catholic Church bore an anti-Roman sentiment, which was common in the Anglican Church. He had warned his faithful about the danger of Rome like that of a plague. No doubt, Newman lived in a time of mutual suspicion and antagonism between the two Churches.

The right belief in God enlightened by the obedience to conscience brought him to realisation of the true Church, to a spiritual home. The conscience is for him the connecting principle between Creator and his Creature. In his *Apologia pro vita sua*, Newman says

candidly: “I am a Catholic by virtue of my believing in a God; and if I am asked why I believe in a God, I answer that it is because I believe in myself, for I feel it impossible to believe in my own existence (and of that fact I am quite sure) without believing also in the existence of Him, who lives as a Personal, All-seeing, All-judging Being in my conscience” (Newman, 1865: 198). The conscience of the person becomes the highest moral law and Newman had again discreetly solved the problem between conscience and obedience to the Church’s Magisterium during the time of papal infallibility doctrine. The theme of conscience lies at the heart of “The Letter to the Duke of Norfolk.” Newman wrote this letter in the wake of the First Vatican Council as a response to the charge of the then British Prime Minister William Gladstone, in light of the First Vatican Council’s adoption of the new dogma, Catholics would have no mental freedom, being captives and slaves of the Pope. Newman explained to the Duke of Norfolk that Catholics in England would continue to be faithful subjects of the Crown after the doctrine of papal infallibility (Doctrine of infallibility, First Vatican Council 1869-70). Catholics remain masters of their conscience and not the Pope. The oft-quoted saying of Newman, “if I am obliged to bring religion into after-dinner toasts, (which indeed does not seem quite the thing) I shall drink—to the Pope, if you please—still, to Conscience first, and to the Pope afterwards.” It is a clear testimony, which states that our Catholic understanding of conscience is in no way a blind obedience to the Magisterium but one based on a respect to personal conscience guided by faith (Zimmermann, 2005: 289-317).

Newman became a great inspiration for the “White Rose Resistance” against Hitler in Germany. Many Newman’s ideas of conscience translated in German language helped Hans and Sophie Scholl to fight against the Nazi-regime. Hans and Sophie Scholl were brother and sister. As Students, they were arrested and executed after being found guilty of distributing anti-war, anti-Hitler leaflets at the University of Munich. They were both active

within the White Rose non-violent resistance group. Theodor Haeckel, philosopher and culture historian, who guided the “White Rose”, became Catholic after translating Newman’s book *Grammar of Assent*. The Second Vatican Council has assimilated many elements of Newman’s understanding of conscience. “*Gaudium et spes*”, Article 16 states: “In the depths of his conscience, man detects a law which he does not impose upon himself, but which holds him to obedience” (also John Paul II. 1993: 54-56). Similarly, we read in the Declaration “*Dignitatis Humanae* Art. 3: “that the highest norm of human life is God’s divine law – eternal, objective, and universal.” In addition, “Wherefore every man has the duty, and therefore the right, to seek the truth ... in order that he may with prudence form for himself right and true judgments of conscience.”

One True Church

Conscience as creative Principle of the Religion expresses itself through the sense of duty. For Newman conscience is the echo of God’s voice and not the voice of God. The experience of God in conscience calls for a response. We can notice the compatibility of his convictions with his proceedings. The moment he realises, that the Catholic Church is the bearer of the truth, he leaves his old Church in which he grew and lived. The greatness of the person lies in his openness to the truth, which God communicates to him (Allsopp, 1992: 192-208). He sought truth in religion and that at all cost. He saw the important source of doctrinal and spiritual unity provided by the bishop of Rome, which was lacking in Anglican Church. The Witness of the Church Fathers, whom he had extensively studied, urged him to join the Church of Rome, which had the fullness of Antiquity, Apostolic Succession, Universality and Holiness. In his most influential Work “*An Essay on the Development of Christian Doctrine*, painstakingly details the manner in which Christian Doctrine has developed over time. Digging deep into the history of the early Church Newman is overwhelmed with the certainty and without doubt, that the

Protestant position lacks a solid basis, and that the Catholic Church is the true Church founded by Christ. Having studied the Fathers of the Church, he felt the depth of faith and there was no other better preference than to crossover to Catholic Church. Indeed, this book is more on the defence of the Roman Catholic Church and her claim to be one true Church. It is one of the most famous presentation in defence of the Church by the most noted converts. He notes "... the doctrines of which the present Catholic religion consist are prima facie the correct, true, faithful, legitimate development of the doctrines which preceded them, and not their corruption" (Newman, 1845: 202). Truth was his passion. The same Truth Newman found in becoming Catholic, he defended against the relativism of the 19th century.

The more we occupy ourselves with the writings of Newman, the more we see the depth of his theological reflections and convictions. Great parallels can be drawn in the lives of the two great Saints of English Reformation, John Fisher (1469-1535), Thomas More (1478-1535) and John Henry Newman. John Fisher and Thomas More (A play from Robert Bolt titled "A Man for All Seasons", 1960 and the motion film with the same title 1966- depicting the life of Sir Thomas More) were Martyrs of conscience. Both had to die because they refused to accept King Henry VIII as supreme Head of the Church of England and for upholding the Catholic Church's doctrine of papal primacy (Mann, 2017). Thomas More, the Lord Chancellor and was executed by Henry VIII for his refusal to sign the first succession act. His famous words: "The king's good servant, but God's first." John Cardinal Fisher was the Bishop from Rochester, he was decapitated while he refused to accept the second marriage of Henry VIII. John Fisher and Thomas More willingly accepted the execution than to betray their conscience and the Catholic Faith. The integrity of their conscience remained intact throughout their lives, trials and condemnation. Peter Berglar titled his book over Thomas More; "A Lonely Voice Against the Power of the State," gives reason why he deliberately chose this subtitle.

He writes, “Thomas More stood alone, first, because conscience is something altogether personal, but above all because those who follow their conscience often are few. Where circumstances require it, obedience to conscience also implies the capacity for steadfastness in the face of an overwhelming majority that thinks or decides otherwise” (Berglar, 2009: vii). The consequence of following the conscience led John Fisher and Thomas More to Martyrdom, they died defending the inalienable dignity of human conscience and John Henry led the conscience to Catholic Faith. He is not a Martyr, but had to suffer injustice and false accusations. They were persons of moral integrity, witnesses of the primacy of truth and defenders of human conscience. They loved the Catholic teaching. According to great Irish author James Joyce, whom Newman was the greatest literary writer, said of Newman, “nobody has ever written English prose that can be compared with that of a tiresome footling little Anglican parson who afterwards became a prince of the only true Church”.

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From Peter to Mary: Rethinking the Theological Virtues of Faith, Hope and, Love

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Abstract: The theological virtues namely, faith, hope, and love (cf. 1 Cor. 13:13) are implicit in the affirmation of *Mysterium Fidei*. Christian understanding of faith is therefore the unity of knowing, hoping, and loving and are reciprocally related aspects of an existential genuine Christian way of Being. Christian faith not only includes the knowledge of certain content but also the response which justifies the decisions to believe. In the New Testament, the character of Mary is apt example of how the unity of faith, hope and love are manifested in their true meaning. However, comparing the character of Mary with the character of Peter in the Gospel of Mark, one can see the challenge of Christian discipleship poses for Christian way of living.

Keywords: Faith, Hope, Love, Mary, Peter, Ecclesiogenesis, *Mysterium Fidei*

Introduction

The New Testament accounts of Mary as a Biblical figure are very rare. However, these accounts powerfully present the true and

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enduring meaning of the Christian understanding of faith. So, it is no wonder then that, the New Testament accounts of Mary has produced four Marian dogmas, several doctrines, literature, and more devotional practices. So, this small study on Mary from the New Testament perspective is an attempt to illustrate that she is the embodiment of theological virtues, namely faith, hope, and love.

The heart of Christian Mystery is to confess that the incarnate and the crucified Son of God is risen from the dead to give us the Holy Spirit. Every faithful is regularly called to affirm this Mystery of faith, very particularly at the Eucharist, after the Institution Narrative, i.e., *Mysterium Fidei*: “Your death we proclaim, O Lord, and your resurrection we confess until you come” (cf. 1 Cor. 15:14ff).¹ The theological virtues namely, faith, hope, and love (cf. 1 Cor. 13:13) are implicit in this affirmation of *Mysterium Fidei*. Our *faith* in Jesus is that he is the Lord (cf. Rom. 10:11; Phil. 2:10); however, his lordship is proclaimed on the Cross (cf. 1 Cor. 1:23) which is the true and ultimate act of God’s *Love* (cf. Jn. 15:3). While crucifixion is an act of humans to thwart God’s plan of salvation,² God, in raising Jesus from death - we have been given hope a trustworthy hope (cf. Rom. 8:24, Heb. 10:22; Benedict XVI, *Spe salvi* 1), that God will not fail who puts trust in him.

¹ And this is the heart of the Gospel according to St. Paul. “...that Christ died for our sins, in accordance with the scriptures, and that he was buried; and that on the third day, he was raised to life, in accordance with the scriptures (1 Cor. 15: 1-4).

² Pope Francis has aptly articulated; “Jesus suffered betrayal by the disciple who sold him and by the disciple who denied him. He was betrayed by the people who sang hosanna to him and then shouted: ‘Crucify him!’ (Mt 27:22). He was betrayed by the religious institution that unjustly condemned him and by the political institution that washed its hands of him” (Pope Francis, “Homily. Palm Sunday 5 April 2020”)

Presupposition

T. Aquinas's famous definition of faith states that "believing is an act of the intellect assenting to the divine truth by command of the will moved by God through grace" (STh II-II, 2, 9). A holistic approach to faith includes an *assent* (to the content of Christian revelation), that is formed by the decision to *hope* (the eschatological dimension of faith) and completed by the practice of *love*. Faith, hope, and love are reciprocally related aspects of an existential genuine Christian attitude. A genuine principle of love includes faith because faith and love condition and demand each other reciprocally. Similarly, in the principle of love there is also present the principle of hope, which looks beyond the present that seeks the whole.³ Therefore, Christian understanding of faith is the unity of *knowing, hoping, and loving*, (Alfaro, 1982: 341) and cannot be separated. What we are trying to achieve here is to demonstrate that these three virtues can be found in Mary as portrayed by the Evangelist Luke in his gospel. And Mary as a model of faith become clear, when we compare her with the character of Peter in the Gospel of Mark.⁴

³ "Of course, the principle of love, if it is to be genuine, includes faith. Only thus does it remain what it is. For without Faith, which we have come to understand as a term expressing man's ultimate need to receive and the inadequacy of all personal achievement, Love becomes an arbitrary deed. It cancels itself out and becomes self-righteousness: Faith and Love condition and demand each other reciprocally. Similarly, in the principle of Love there is also present the principle of hope, which looks beyond the moment and its isolation and seeks the whole. Thus, our reflections finally lead of their own accord to the words in which Paul named the main supporting pillars of Christianity: 'So Faith, Hope, Love abide, these three; but the greatest of these is Love' (1 Cor 13:13)" (Ratzinger, 2004: 270).

⁴ Peter is presented as a spokesperson for Jesus's disciples. Therefore, Peter's reaction simply reflects the thought of the Twelve and is, therefore, not considered a character or individual distinct from the Twelve. As a

We need to keep in mind that Biblical Narrative Criticism, which also studies the way figures and persons are presented in the Gospel, lets us know that the figures reveal the Evangelist's theological outlook and the purpose of writing the gospel. Gospels do not give us descriptive accounts of the "what really happened"; characters act and speak and it is through their acting and speaking that they are revealed. So, Mary and Peter are not only, in the first place, historical persons but rather characters in the gospel *narratives* with a particular purpose (Lonsdale, 1984: 133-145; Vorster, 1987: 58). They are constructs that reflect an author's attempt to relate the *story of Jesus* for a specific theological purpose and persuade his reader, particularly those who most probably heard the narrative but did not see it individually. However, there can be difference of opinions (Vorster, 59, 73). Their ultimate aim is to tell the truth about Jesus Christ as the revelation of God and how this revelation affected the saints of early Christianity and, thereby, invites a faith response from present readers.⁵

So, 1) we are going to evaluate the character of Peter in the Gospel of Mark and how the characterization of Mary in the Gospel of Luke stands out better and complements it;

2) what the faithful can derive from these characters in understanding the theological virtues of faith, hope, and love. And, finally, what prompts such theological reflection is the understanding that the whole Bible needs to be taken as one book. Vatican II teaches that:

spokesperson Peter is viewed as a "type" rather than an individual. He represents the disciples and their failure (Whitaker, 2013: 667ff.).

⁵ R. Brown, for example, argues that Luke's main concern in the Infancy Narrative is not to get into the mind of the historical Mary at the scene of the Annunciation, but "to tell the reader how the child was conceived and hence to explain his identity" (Brown, 1993: 307).

Since Holy Scripture must be read and interpreted in the sacred spirit in which it was written, no less serious attention must be given to the content and unity of the whole of Scripture, if the meaning of the sacred texts is to be correctly worked out. The living tradition of the whole Church must be taken into account along with the harmony which exists between elements of the faith (*Dei Verbum* 12).

And Ratzinger also notes that:

The basic and primary presupposition of theological exegesis is, therefore, the conviction that Scripture – the multiplicity of its authors and its long historical genesis notwithstanding- is *one* book having a real intrinsic unity in the midst of its various tensions. This presupposition rests in turn upon the firm belief that Scripture is ultimately the work of a single author, who has both a human and a divine aspect (Ratzinger, 2005: 39)

Faith: Mary Is Blessed Because She Has believed

Fundamental to Christian faith proclaiming Jesus is the Lord-*Kyrios*, that is, the New Testament Faith, which Paul formulated in his confession of faith. “I live in faith in Jesus Christ “Son of God, who Loved me and gave himself for me” (Gal. 2:20). (Fries, 1996: 77). Paul’s confession affirms that the Christian faith is a personal ‘faith in Jesus Christ’ as well as an affirmational/propositional faith, i.e., faith in the Son of God “who loves me and gives himself for me”. Theologically speaking, an experience of the person of Jesus gradually evolves into a confession or a declaration that Jesus is the Christ, the *Messiah*. The confession of Paul brings to light the importance and the difficulty of Christian faith, namely, that Christian confession in Jesus Christ is not only to inform but also to move, to effect, to make an impact. (Fries, 1996: 77) This is the difficulty that we can encounter in Peter’s confession (cf. Mk. 8:27-30).

a. Impulsive Peter

Jesus' messianic claims at the scene at Caesarea Philippi is an important gospel passage about the discussion on Jesus' identity (also Mk 9.27-33). Peter's confession about Jesus, "you are the Christ" (Mk. 8:29) is a summarized declaration of Jesus's identity. However, Peter is portrayed here as an impulsive who reacted to Jesus' query on the spur of the moment (Mk 8:32, also 14:28)⁶ At first glance Peter's confession that Jesus is the Messiah is a very "positive" declaration. But the impression is very strongly corrected, as Peter's immediate reaction to the passion prediction is a refusal to accept the suffering of the Son of man. Peter misconceives Jesus' mission and his identity. Therefore, he opposes Jesus instead of helping him (Vorster, 1987: 71-73; Whitaker, 2013: 667). Peter's misconception arises from the fact that the identity of Jesus as revealed does not fit Peter's expectation. The revelation of Jesus as suffering Messiah does not move Peter because of his hardness of heart;⁷ rather he wishes to move his master according to his desire. Peter is rebuked promptly because he hesitatingly wished to fulfill the task of a follower in terms of 8:34-9:1; and we see in the latter part of the Gospel that Peter, as an unobtrusive follower, becomes aware of his lack of insight.

b. Pondering Mary

Luke's Gospel introduces Mary in 1:26-27, in a few brief points. She lived in a very insignificant place, in the town of Galilea named Nazareth (1:26). Well known are the sarcastic comments of

⁶ Peter is a person who at first sight is willing to obey. He promises to follow Jesus even if everybody else falls away and insists that he will not deny Jesus (Mk. 14:28ff) but in the end he fails ... when he realizes it, he bursts into tears (cf. Mk. 14:72) (cf. Vorster, 1987: 65).

⁷ Nevertheless, it is argued that Peter's and the disciples' incomprehension is due to their hardness of heart, and it serves the Christological function of heightening the Mystery of Jesus' identity. Because Jesus' identity is a Mystery, the disciples cannot grasp it without the help of divine assistance (Matera, 1989: 153-172).

Nathaniel, “can anything good come out of Nazareth” (Jn. 1:46). God chose a young girl from this lowly place to become the mother of the Messiah (Sri, 2012: 2). Mary is a *virgin* who is *betrothed*. In first century, Judaism, betrothal represented the first stage of a two-step marriage process different from engagement” in modern society. At a betrothal in Mary’s day, the bride and groom formally exchanged consent in the presence of witnesses (cf. Mal 2:14). This forged a legal bond between the two who would then be considered married. The woman would be called the groom’s “wife” (see Matt. 1:20, 24) and this union could only be broken by divorce. Any violation of the man’s marital rights would be considered adultery. After the betrothal, the wife usually remained living at her family home for up to a year. Then occurred the second step of the marriage process, ‘taking’ the wife to the man’s home. It was then that the man’s support for his wife and marital sexual relations formally began. So, Mary is legally married to Joseph, but she is not yet to the second stage of the marriage (Sri, 2012: 3-5). Mary is “troubled” by the greetings of the angel Gabriel (Lk. 1:26-29), and she is said to be afraid, which is why the angel Gabriel told her “do not be afraid...” (Lk. 1:30) and she *asks a question* because: 1) of the human impossibility involved in conceiving a child; 2) cultural shock because she is not yet living with her husband. The announcement to Mary is completely unheard of and has no biblical prototype for her to consider.⁸ Thus Mary’s query is about the process, not proof for this birth. (Sri, 2012, 12). However against the human impossibility, she is told that “with God, nothing will be impossible”, and she is given a similar sign - her elderly kinswoman Elizabeth is pregnant (Lk. 1:36-37). Mary becomes obedient to this

⁸ For instance, the ancient roots of God’s covenant people first sprouted with God’s gift of a son (Isaac) to a nonagenarian barren woman (Sarah) and her century-old husband (Abraham) (Gen. 17:15-22; 21:1-7) and that, at another critical junction in Israel’s history, God listened to the prayers of a desperate childless woman (Hannah) in the sanctuary and granted her a son as well (Samuel) (1 Sam. 1:1-20; cf. Jdgs. 13:2-25) (Sri, 2012: 12).

revelation and even enthusiastic in her response that she is the handmaid of the Lord, “let it be to me according to your *Word*”. By showing Mary’s readiness to obey the word of God (*rema*), Luke is here already presenting Mary as one of “those who hear the word of God (*logos*) and do it or keep it” (Lk. 8:21; 11:28).⁹ Thus, along with her unique mission of being Jesus’ physical mother, she is identified with archetypal faith for “everyone who like her is a handmaiden or servant of God can be a mother of Jesus who lets the divine word become flesh in his or her own body” (Balthasar, 2005: 139). Against this background we can recognize in Mary as a model of faith; namely, 1) in her obedience to the word of God, 2) in her capacity to dialogue with God, 3) and in her discernment of the process of participation in God’s salvific plan.¹⁰

The depth of her faith is well illustrated in her *Magnificat*. It embodies the joy of Mary who knows that Yahweh is faithful in his promises to her forefathers. She becomes the spokesperson of those Poor Ones whom God had helped by his might, whether they were women yearning for children or Israel reduced by oppression to the status of a “handmaid” (1 Mac. 2:11) of “low estate” (1 Sam. 9: 16). She is confident that Yahweh is going to bring blessings to those who fear him, and she could attest to it in a personal way because she had been assured by the angel, “for God nothing will be impossible” (Lk.1:37) (Brown, 2005: 361-362). She is hopeful that Yahweh will not fail her in her mission of being Jesus’ physical mother.

⁹ Luke is here already presenting Mary as one of “those who hear the word [*logos*] of God and do it” by placing on Mary’s lips at the end of the Annunciation scene: “Behold the handmaid of the Lord. Let it happen to me according to your word [*rema*]” (l: 38) (Brown, 1993: 318).

¹⁰ God who appreciates human freedom, “himself wanted in sovereign freedom to become man in her, the lowly handmaiden” (Balthasar, 2005: 139).

Love as Kenosis

Mary remains with her Son at the Cross when the other disciples run away (Jn 19: 25). Nothing could separate her from the love of God [revealed] in Christ Jesus (cf. 8: 31-9) (O'Collins, 2011: 143).

a. The Reluctant Peter

Peter's confession of Jesus as the Messiah is not without a foundation. It is argued that even during the lifetime of Jesus, i.e., before Easter, there existed among the disciples the understanding that Jesus is the Christ, that is the Messiah. Some of the disciples who were close to the movements of Zealots thought of political messiahship.¹¹ But Jesus had already rejected such an interpretation of his activity. However, Peter's confession is related to the prophetic tradition of the anointed, i.e., Jesus as the messenger and embodiment of God's final word who demands absolute obedience. According to this tradition, the Messiah is the prophet of the last times anointed with the Holy Spirit (Kasper, 2011: 94). However, Jesus rebukes Peter, because Jesus transcends this idea¹² or develops it "in his saying about the divinely ordained necessity for suffering" (Kasper, 2011: 94).¹³ According to G. O. Collins, the key to understand Jesus as suffering Messiah is in his preaching of the

¹¹ This means there existed a conflicting understanding about the concept of Messiahship (Whitaker, 2013: 670).

¹² G. O'Collins argues that "It would seem almost unaccountably odd if Jesus had never reflected on and applied to himself the Jewish conviction that the righteous suffer but God will vindicate them (Pss. 27, 37,38, 41, 55,69, 109) In Psalm 22 (and the other psalms) the righteous person does not die, but after severe sufferings is delivered and vindicated by God in the course of this life" (Id., 1995: 70-71).

¹³ While there may be traces of such ideas in the Jewish tradition, they are foreign to Peter not only here in Caesarea Philippi but also on Good Friday... because such ... messianic expectations could give rise to political misinterpretations of the messianic movement this might set off among the people could lead to accusation and condemnation] (Kasper, 2011: 94). This is one of the reasons the crowd, who sang Hosanna on his Triumphant entry into Jerusalem, rejected him before Pilate.

Kingdom of God. “Jesus saw suffering and persecution as characterizing the coming of that kingdom which he insistently preached. The message of the Kingdom led more or less directly to the Mystery of the passion” (O’Collins, 2011: 72). During his trial, Jesus never denies that he is the Messiah, otherwise he would call into question his mission and preaching of the Kingdom of God; because in his life Jesus had claimed that the Kingdom of God has *already* come (cf. Matt. 11:4; Lk. 7:22).

[Therefore Jesus’...] mission culminated in the suffering ordeal to come: a time of crisis and distress which was to move towards the day of the Son of Man (Mk. 13 parr.), the restoration of Israel (Matt. 19:28 par.), the banquet of the saved, and the salvation of the nations (Matt. 8: 11 par.). Thus, his arrest, trial, and crucifixion dramatized the very thing which totally engaged Jesus, that rule of God which was to come through a time of ordeal (O’Collins, 2011: 72).

Therefore, Jesus accepts that he is the Suffering Messiah, the Messiah of the Cross, and invites and prepares disciples to accept this truth (cf. Mk. 14:25). “[The] essential connection between the message of Jesus and his person meant that the vindication of his person in and through death entailed the vindication of God’s kingdom, and vice versa” (O’Collins, 2011: 73), which Jesus envisages is a cosmic and eschatological triumph (Mk. 8:38) whereas Peter hoped for triumph at an historical level (Mk. 8.33) and, therefore, he rebuked Jesus words about his suffering (Whitaker, 2013 : 670).¹⁴

¹⁴ “If dominion is a mark of the Messiah, Jesus’ dominion takes the form of service. If the Messiah’s path to dominion leads through struggle and victory, Jesus’ path points towards suffering and defeat. . . In the dominion of service which includes suffering which comes from thinking God’s thoughts, . . . we begin to see the new understanding of Messiahship which prevented Jesus from letting himself be called

Peter's failure is in the rebuke; for the word often used in the Gospel of Mark to admonish and to rebuke one's Master is not expected from a disciple.¹⁵ Jesus' "rebuke" response also befits the manner of one who wants to correct the disciple's idea of his status. Thus Jesus' "get behind me" and "If any man would come after me, let him deny himself and take up his Cross and follow me" (Mk 34).

What Peter is currently doing standing in front of Jesus is rebuking him as if he, Peter, is the teacher. Consequently, Jesus' words are simultaneously a rebuke and a recall to adopt the correct posture of a true disciple - one who follows and who thinks according to the divine way and not the human way (8:33) (Whitaker, 2013: 673).

Jesus certainly saw that his proclamation of the Kingdom of God and his impending suffering could not be separated because his redemptive service, his option for the poor and the marginalized, won him, from the very beginning, the hostility of his opponents (cf. Mk. 2:1-12). Following Jesus means following him in this service of Love: 'If anyone would be first, he must be last of all and servant of all' (Mk. 9:35). A life like this involves being prepared for anything, leaving everything (cf. Mk. 10:28), even risking your life (cf. Mk. 8.34-35). Jesus saw his own fate prefigured in that of the prophets who were persecuted and rejected in Jerusalem (cf. Mk. 12:1-12). Jesus wanted to alert his disciples that opting for him does not mean peace, but a break with the *status quo* and they will meet the same fate as he will (cf. Mk. 8.34) (Kasper, 2011: 104-108). "His

Messiah, since that title would only have encouraged misunderstanding of his mission" (Kasper, 2011: 94-95).

¹⁵ On the lips of Jesus, rebuke is a powerful action word. It is used against chaotic nature and to demons who knew Jesus' true identity (Mk. 1:25; 3:12; 4:39; 8:30,33; 9:25); as a command to be silent or to keep his identity hidden (Mk. 1:25; 3:12; 4:39; 8:30); in the stilling of the stormy wind (Mk. 4:39); and in Jesus's command to unclean spirit to exit a person (Mk. 1:25; 9:25) (Whitaker, 2013: 671).

death on the Cross is the culmination of that turning of God against himself in which he gives himself in order to raise man up and save him. This is Love in its most radical form” (Benedict XVI, *Deus Caritas est*, 12). In the aftermath of Easter, Peter will be reinstated and can become pastor to Christ’s flock only after he has three times testified to his love (Jn. 21: 15–19) (O’Collins, 2011: 143).

b. The Cruciformity of Mary’s Faith

Faith responses and commitments need to be actualized by the decision the faithful make. The Cruciformity of faith means that one demonstrates faith conviction by one’s obedient, self-emptying act which Christ exhibited on the Cross. In other words, the self-emptying act of Christ shapes Christian commitments and attitudes in all circumstances.

Luke presents Mary as the faithful remnant in whom all the important aspects of the promises of the Old Testament to the daughter of Zion are fulfilled.¹⁶ The Cruciformity of faith is evident in Mary’s pilgrimage of faith (Ratzinger, 2005: 50). First, Mary’s faith was tested when “the bombshell virgin birth” announcement was dropped by Gabriel. In her socio-religious background, according to the law of Moses (cf. Dt. 22:22; Lev. 20:10), to be found with a child before coming to live with her betrothed was a

¹⁶ That is why the angel addressed her as “Hail Mary; E. Sri argues that “Hail” (Lk. 1:28) is reminiscent of the Daughter Zion oracles and this interpretation fits with the many royal messianic themes in the Annunciation scene. “Hail,” in Greek *Chaire*, is literally a command to “rejoice.” And this brings to mind the mysterious Daughter Zion figure of the Old Testament and signals that prophecy is coming to fulfillment and God is coming to Israel as King. In the Old Testament, particularly in the Prophets, “Daughter Zion” is a symbolic figure representing the Faithful remnant of God’s people, i.e., the Faithful people of Israel who were awaiting the messianic age (Zep. 3:14-15; Zec 9:9. “Sons of Zion” in Joel 2:23) is a similar image. The prophets foretold that they would rejoice because the Lord the King would liberate them from their enemies (cf. Sri, 2018: 14ff).

disgraceful situation. Thus, Luke highlights the realism of Mary's challenge while presenting her as the faithful remnant. Secondly, although what is being revealed to her remains a Mystery (cf. Lk. 2:48 and John Paul II, *Redemptoris Mater*, 17), her response to God, "let it be with me according to your word" (Lk. 1:38), is with strong conviction. Mary continues to repeat her faithful response at every new circumstance during her faith journey, namely, Mary's encounter with the aged Simeon and Hanna, and in her losing and finding Jesus in the Temple. Knowing that she is dealing with mystery, she prefers to keep it in her heart (Lk. 2:19; 2:51; cf. 1:29; 2:33). She does not become a hindrance to her son's mission; she rather affirms her faith in walking with her son towards Calvary. Against this background, John Paul II teaches that:

On that wood of the Cross her Son hangs in agony as one condemned. "He was despised and rejected by men; a man of sorrows...he was despised, and we esteemed him not": as one destroyed (cf. Is. 53:3- 5). How great, how heroic then is the obedience of faith shown by Mary in the face of God's "unsearchable judgments"! How completely she "abandons herself to God" without reserve... Through this faith, Mary is perfectly united with Christ in his self- emptying. This is perhaps the deepest "kenosis" of Faith in human history (*Redemptoris Mater* 18).

Through her pilgrimage of faith, she participates in and makes present the Mystery of Christ to the world. "The *Pietà* completes the picture of the Cross because Mary accepts the Cross, the Cross communicating itself in Love, the Cross that now allows us to experience in her compassion the compassion of God" (Ratzinger, 2005: 78-79). In her *Magnificat* she highlights the *depth* of her faith conviction that God will not abandon his faithful. The *Pietà*, i.e., at the Cross she achieves the *integrity* of her faith pilgrimage. Therefore, in her faithful response (Lk. 1:26-38), Luke portrays Mary as the epitome of the metaphor of the Daughter of Zion, in

other words, all that God wishes to realize for his people by his salvific action (Potterie, 1992: 3).¹⁷

Hope - God Will Not Fail Us

The resurrection of Jesus which makes the Gospel the good news because it contains fidelity of God, who is infinitely greater and more powerful than human persons and who can counsel and help when human beings find themselves at the end of their own wisdom and strength.

a. Peter and the Hopeless Situation

A person who yields to the temptation to evade the Cross is not a person of hope, because he cannot see beyond the Cross. Even in the passion prediction, Jesus says that after three days he will rise again (Mk. 8:31). The impulsive Peter immediately rebuked Jesus in the prediction of his Passion. However, Jesus rebukes Peter and addresses him as Satan, an unambiguously negative term. One possibility put forward is that, like the demonic forces, Peter perceives who Jesus really is and is thus described as behaving like the Satan: 1) Jesus was tempted by Satan in the wilderness to find

¹⁷ According to de la Potterie, God is a loving father. Although God showed how he felt toward the rebellious Israelites, he also had an eye for the future when the relationship would be restored and he could once again return to them and welcome them into his arms (cf. Zech. 2:10; 9:9). In the Old Testament, Zion is imaged as Spouse and Daughter. “Here the Old Testament texts of the ‘Daughter of Zion’ are applied to a definite woman. ... This is precisely the reason why, in the Fourth Gospel, both at Cana and at the Cross, Jesus addresses Mary calling her ‘Woman’”... The particular woman Mary, the Mother of Jesus, is in a certain way the historical realization of this symbolic figure who is called in by the prophets, depending on the context, the ‘Daughter of Zion, the Mother-Zion, or the Virgin Israel. All of Israel’s expectation of salvation was projected upon this symbolic figure of the ‘Messianic Daughter of Zion’; this symbolic figure, described by the prophets, is concretized at once in a daughter of Israel, Mary, who thus becomes the personification of the messianic people in eschatological times” (Potterie, 1992: 17-18).

shortcuts to still his hunger and to find glory. Peter's language is similar to the language of Satan, while Peter accepts that Jesus is Messiah, he never wanted the divinely willed plan of messiahship. 2) In other parts of the New Testament Satan is portrayed as a 'blinder' associated with darkness and incomprehension rather than light (cf. 2 Cor 4:4; Acts 18; Whitaker, 2013: 673) So, Peter as a spokesperson for the disciples, is behaving in a way that blinds others from seeing the path of true discipleship. Peter thought that if Jesus were to die at the hand of the Jews, then the Jesus' movement would be over.

b. Mary at Pentecost. Symbol of Hope – Matured in Faith

Mary's journey with her son does not end at Calvary, her faith looks beyond the Cross. She lives with the community of disciples in prayer in the days leading up to the descent of the Holy Spirit. Mary's presence at Pentecost is quite significant because Pentecost echoes the event of the Annunciation at Nazareth. Jesus Christ had at that time been conceived of the Holy Spirit and now, at Pentecost, the Holy Spirit brings forth a new community, the Church. and Mary unite these two great moments in the history of salvation (John Paul II, *Redemptoris Mater*, 24; Ratzinger, 2005: 57).

The angel Gabriel, as the messenger of God, strengthens Mary at the Annunciation by the promise that by the power of the Most High the Holy Spirit will overshadow her. At Pentecost the disciples are strengthened by the post Resurrection appearance of Jesus Christ. By his command they were not to depart from Jerusalem until clothed with the power from on high (cf. Lk. 24. 49; Acts. 1: 3-5). The disciples gather with Mary at the Upper Room (cf. Acts. 1:14) and received the Baptism of the Holy Spirit (cf. Acts 2:1-4) to become a new self-generating community. The faith of Mary as the prototypical hearer of the Word makes possible the bodily conception of Jesus. She bears the Word and keeps it. Mary's faith reaches its maturity at Pentecost, by accompanying the disciples in that event. The Church participates in the archetypal faith of Mary

when the Church spiritually brings forth individuals through the sacrament of Baptism; a new generation of People believing, hoping, and loving again.

Concluding Reflections

Biblical faith expresses the conviction that God's plan of salvation reveals itself in human history for humanity's sake (cf. Dt. 26:5-11). Biblical figures tell us not only how God acted in their history but also that it has a message for us today. Our discussion on the theological virtues of faith, hope, and love is an attempt to understand *how* these virtues play out in the New Testament figures of Mary and Peter within the Mystery of Christ. Based on our studies we can conclude our findings under three headings, namely, Christological (*Faith*), Eschatological (*Hope*), and Ecclesial (*Love*).

Christological (Faith)

Because within the Mystery of Christ the role of Mary and Peter in the New Testament evolves and develops, we can say that our study on the theological virtues is also Christological. We began this study with the question Jesus himself put to his disciples, "Who do you say that I am?" (Mk. 8:29) - a Christological question around which fundamental Christian faith stands.

Both Mary and Peter have their faith tested concerning the question of the Messiah. Mary was asked if she could be the mother of the Messiah-King, i.e., the Incarnation, Peter was asked if he could follow the suffering Messiah, i.e., the King of the Cross. However, the difference is found in their response, but a similarity can be discerned in the God providence. In the last analysis what we see is that the will of God will succeed. God saves both the good and the bad.

a. Mary as the Handmaid in the Mystery of Christ

From the Annunciation to Pentecost Mary stands in the New Testament as a model for all Christians in her faith and discipleship. Mary's life is uniquely related to the decisive moment (*Kairos*= Gal. 4:4-7) in the history of salvation, because she opened the door of the world for the definitive coming of the redeeming God into the flesh of our humanity (Rahner, TI- I 1961: 201-14; 202-3). Her singular position in God's saving plan very much dependent on the Mystery of Christ which lies at the very heart of the dogma of the Immaculate Conception. "...that the Blessed Virgin Mary, at the first instant of her conception, by a singular privilege and grace of the Omnipotent God, in virtue of the merits of Jesus Christ, the Savior of mankind, was preserved immaculate from all stain of original sin..." (Pius IX, *Ineffabilis Deus*). The dogma links "Mary to the merits of Christ that would have been applied to her by anticipation or retroactively. The Son's merits flowed back upon the mother, not in the irreversible temporality of history but in the sovereign mind of God the Creator who makes all creatures what they are" (Tavard, 1996: 195). It is the God and not the sinful conduct of the ancestors, that gives being to the creature.

Along with her unique role, the dogma teaches she was chosen by the Triune God to be the *Theotokos*, to be a "worthy" God-bearer (Jelly, 1992: 276). Dogma demonstrates the abiding being of God who desires to be with humankind in this world. Therefore, the Church teaches that "only in the Mystery of Christ is her Mystery made clear" (John Paul II. *Redemptoris missio* 4; cf. 19).¹⁸ If Scripture is the account of God's action in human history, the Church dogmas teach the eternal truth that is hidden in God's

¹⁸According to Vatican II: 'Devoutly meditating on her and contemplating her in the light of the Word made man, the Church reverently penetrates more deeply into the great Mystery of the Incarnation and becomes more and more like her spouse,' *Lumen Gentium*, no. 65.

revelation. The Marian Dogmas teach about the Mystery of Christ and this has been well elucidated in the words of Balthasar:

The statement that Mary is *theotokos*, the one who gives birth to God, is in the first place a statement which has its rightful setting in Christology. The statement that her conception was immaculate is in the first place a statement whose setting is the doctrine of grace and redemption. The statement that she is a virgin, in order that she may become the Mother of Christ – In itself a simple repetition of the witness of Scripture – is in the reflection of the Church a statement taken from the theology of the Covenant and consequently from the doctrine of the people of the Church. And the dogma of the Assumption of her body into heaven is, properly understood, a part of the universal Christian doctrine of the Last Things (Balthasar, 1975: 65).

In the conclusion to his brief survey of post-conciliar Mariology, A. Dulles concisely states:

There can be no cleavage between the Mary of history and the Mary of dogma. By a neglect of history, one can open the path to a divinized Mary in whom mythical projection overcomes theology. By a neglect of dogma one can deprive Mary of her distinctive role in salvation history and reduce her to the common level of humanity (Dulles, 2002: 219).

Within the “hierarchy of truths,”¹⁹ as taught by Vatican II, the primary or central truths are the Trinity, Incarnation, and Redemption. The function of Marian dogmas or revealed truths is to shed light upon the central mysteries of our Christian faith and

¹⁹ “When comparing doctrines with one another, they should remember that in Catholic doctrine there exists a “hierarchy” of truths, since they vary in their relation to the fundamental Christian faith (*Unitatis redintegratio*, 11).

also to inspire us to live more fully in fidelity to them. They have as well soteriological and ecclesiological aspects which help enlighten us about the central Mystery of our redemption by Christ alone and inspire us to more devoted discipleship (Jelly, 1992: 276). Mary's uniqueness is to be found in her distinctive role which she faithfully accomplished. We can situate Mary's distinctive role within God's plan of salvation who desires that all to be saved (1 Tim. 2:4) and everyone who is called by God according to his purpose has a unique role to fulfill in his/her life (cf. Eph. 1:3; 2:10). For which, as Vatican II taught that she is the "type and excellent exemplar in faith and charity."

While type and exemplar, Mary is also member of the Church. This limits her exemplarity in a sense; she should not, for example, be made out to possess all the different graces and charisms given to the members of the Church, as certain authors did in the past in an effort to explain how she is "full of grace." Rather, the Council considers her in the history of salvation and concludes that in her personal role and virtues she is type of the Church and exemplar for everyone in the Church. In yet a more positive direction, because she is member, Mary as type enters into the reality of the Church. She is type and exemplar from within the Church, sharing the Church's life (Neumann, 1986: 122).

The Catechism of the Catholic Church's teaching on "Mary - Mother of Christ, Mother of the Church", states that "Mary's function as mother of men in no way obscures or diminishes this unique mediation of Christ, but rather shows its power" (CCC 916, cf. LG 60). In Christ everyone is called and is destined in love to be God's sons and daughters (cf. Eph. 1:3; Rom. 8:28). The Holy Spirit who overshadows Mary at the Incarnation of Jesus is the same Spirit who makes us a new creation by forgiving our sin and giving us

faith, hope, and love.²⁰ Considering the nature of Mary's Faith as it is manifested from the Annunciation onwards, namely, her self-entrustment to God's faithful Love and her promise to be the Mother of the Savior, will help the faithful to understand that *believing* in God involves offering oneself unconditionally (*loving*) to God's plan.

Peter and the Cost of Discipleship

Peter as a biblical figure demonstrates the difficulty in following Christ where one encounters the cost of discipleship. Although Jesus rebukes Peter, he is allowed to accompany Jesus on special occasions (cf. Mk. 5:37f.; 8:27ff.; 13:3ff.), particularly at the Transfiguration (Mk. 9:2ff) (Vorster, 1987: 73). And Peter goes along with Jesus to Jerusalem. Peter, who so emphatically claimed to die with Jesus, makes as far as the courtyard (14:66), and was, literally, the last man standing. All the other male disciples had fled (14:50-51). He is not a non-follower of Jesus in Mark's Gospel. He is present during Jesus' trial although at a distance which is the mark of fallibility (Vorster, 1987: 70). And his fallibility of faith in Jesus reaches its zenith at a most critical situation: Peter denies his discipleship of Jesus three times and the scene ends poignantly. Peter, hearing the cock crow and *recalling what Jesus said* (14:30), *weeps* (14:72). *He disowned his master because he lost his hope in a powerless messiah thereby, he failed in loving Jesus, his master*

²⁰ St. Augustine, on the *Predestination of the Saints*, argues that all is God's gift, including the act of faith. Since God's grace and power to save are at the very heart of the gospel, it would be quite difficult to refute the biblical arguments that Augustine presents. We receive a share in "every spiritual blessing in the heavenly places" (Eph. 1:3) because God, from eternity and solely because of his own goodness and Love, willed that it be so. The Holy Spirit who overshadows Mary at the Incarnation of Jesus is the same Spirit who makes us a new creation by forgiving our sins and giving us faith, hope, and love. From eternity, God has predestined the Head and the members in the Head (cf. Eph. 1:3-6) (cf. Levering, 2013:122).

in his way to messiahship. When one's Faith in a person is no more a force to look forward, then the Love for that person gradually fades away. However, by presenting the poignant Peter who remembers what Jesus said and consequently weeping for his failure, Mark is communicating to the reader that Peter is preparing for his recall as Jesus' true disciple (Whitaker, 2013: 677). Here we see the transformation an impulsive to a pondering Peter.

Thus, at the end of the Gospel we see that the relationship of Peter (Mk. 16:7) with Jesus' followers is re-established (Vorster, 1987: 70). Peter is the only disciple mentioned by name at this point in the Gospel. While the character of Peter offers the meaning of cost of discipleship in following the suffering messiah, more confidently, Peter's character offers an example of one who failed Jesus twice but was forgiven and called to follow him again after failure (Whitaker, 2013: 681-682). He goes on to become an important figure in the Jerusalem community and to embrace martyrdom and to confess his ultimate love for his Master. (Whitaker, 2013: 678-679). Thus, he demonstrates the very meaning of the Mystery of Christ, namely, that God's Love wins over both the good and the bad.

b. Eschatological Dimension

“Who do you say that I am?” is an existential question to which in every generation the faithful must respond in their particular time and place. Therefore, reflection on Faith as a theological virtue does not become abstract but is rather an analysis of the act of Faith from the personal context in which it takes place.

In our exploration of the figure of Mary we have found that she is a person imbued with the virtue of hope. In the depth of her faith, she could praise God. She remembered the promise made to Abraham and his descendants (cf. Lk 1:55). She remained hopeful that the same God would guide her. Therefore, she could move on with her Son to the moment of Calvary (cf. Benedict XVI, *Spe Salvi*, 50). At

the Annunciation she was told that her Son would be called great and that he would sit on the throne of David his Father. Now he was dying in disgrace and her *Pietà* is nothing but a quiet still meditation on the Mystery of the Cross where she saw beyond “the power of God, and the wisdom of God” (1 Cor. 1:24). At the foot of the Cross thus we see the maturity of her Faith.

We have also seen that, although, Jesus had rebuked Peter for his reluctance to accept the suffering Messiah, Peter was not a non-follower. The joy of the resurrection touched him as well. Peter became a martyr for Christ because he understood that faith in Jesus needs to be demonstrated by following him in its existential context. A theology of hope is nothing but faith’s capacity to see beyond the present crisis and to live out to the belief that the providence of God will not abandon us (cf. Heb.11: 1)

c. Ecclesial Dimension

Two unique moments in the redemptive economy of grace are the incarnation of the Word and the birth of the Church. These two historic events are brought about through the action of the Holy Spirit. Mary links these two events through her pilgrimage she makes from Nazareth to the Upper Room in Jerusalem; a journey that expresses her fiat which is preserved in hope and anchored in her love of God.

We have stated that the Church participates in the archetypal faith of Mary when the Church lives out the theological virtues, namely, faith, hope, and love. This calls to mind the famous concept in the theology of the Church: *Ecclesiogenesis*, i.e., a dynamic vision of the Church’s self-realizing herself in the history. Against this background a much-quoted metaphorical saying of Venerable Bede is *Nam et Ecclesia quotidie gignit Ecclesiam*, – “Every day the Church gives birth to the Church” (Bede, II: XII) gains its significance. J. Komonchak, who has often quoted this statement interpreted it as follows. There are two inseparable moments in this

daily genesis of the Church, an objective moment, and a subjective reception. The objective moment refers to the constitutive meaning that centers around the life, teachings, death, and resurrection of Jesus Christ, which are represented in the Scriptures, in the tradition, in dogmas, in the liturgy etc. They are the objective principle of the unity of the Church across generations. When these objective principles are received and appropriated by each successive generation of Christians it becomes a subjective moment. But the objective meanings that make the Church a distinctive community do not affect the Church except in so far as they are received and appropriated by each successive generation of Christians in the Church's daily genesis (Komonchak, 1995: 89). Faith comes from hearing, St. Paul said, but he also said that no one can say Jesus is Lord except in the Holy Spirit. And it is the act of personal and communal appropriation of the Gospel that is the second, subjective moment in the Church's daily genesis.

Mary's Faith is archetypal because she shows us that God wants humankind to be fruitful. Mary actively demonstrates how to hear the message of salvation, and thus move from hearing to faith, from faith to hope and from hope to love. Thus, the journey she makes from the Annunciation to the Pentecost reveal her personal moments wherein she endured the faith trails, while anchoring securely in God's promises, and her love for her Son was never a hindrance in his mission. Mary brought forth Jesus by the power of the Spirit. So too, a faithful community brings forth Jesus in and through the Spirit which they have received in the sacraments.

The Pentecost event shows that God desires that the Church, as a faithful community, reproduce itself by reproducing its constitutive acts of Christian meaning and value. The common meaning of Christ event constitutes the Church but her self-realizing herself in the history is the result of dialectic interaction between God's communication and human response.

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Jesus and Ambedkar: The Relevance of the Emancipatory Correlation between Jesus and Dr. Ambedkar to the Contemporary Indian Catholic Church

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Abstract: Being built on the values like, justice, equality, liberty and fraternity, the preamble of Indian Constitution, the existing caste-based divisive situation in India, is worrisome. Obviously, constant effort has been taken to undo the caste discriminative factors at various times, by different individuals. Among those individuals, Dr. Bhimrao Ramji Ambedkar stands unique. Being born in the same oppressive situation, he deeply analyzed the caste system, vigorously fought this systemic evil, organized people, initiated its systematic eradication and tirelessly worked for justice and equity. His sacrifice is not exclusively for Dalits, but to all who are oppressed, neglected, discriminated, and exploited. Thereby Dr. Ambedkar becomes a universal icon to

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fight injustice and inequality. Deeply impressed by this great human being, I find those values of Dr. Ambedkar are nothing but the Kingdom values, preached and lived by Jesus. In Christian sense, I would say that God instrumented Dr. Ambedkar to realize His Kingdom values in our times. Truly, this accommodative understanding would help us to get inspired by the prophetic role of Dr. Ambedkar and work for the emancipation of the oppressed in our localities.

Keywords: Jesus, Dr. Ambedkar, Dalits, India, Caste, Oppression, Liberation

Introduction

India is well known for her rich heritage, variety of cultures, religious traditions, languages, and ethnicities. Though she contains such diversities within herself, proudly she stands unique for her nature ‘unity in diversity’. The projection of her shores displays a glorious side of Indianness. But when we walk through the streets of India, her divisive and discriminative face which is so cruel and inhuman to the core glares at us. The prime factor for it is the caste system founded on graded inequality. It is an inbuilt ideology that exists in every Indian’s mind and heart. It is predestined for an Indian to be born in a particular caste. Naturally the people at the lowest layer of the system (depressed class or Dalits) are the victims of this unjust structure. It is in this oppressive scenario, Christianity landed in Indian soil. The Dalits who were longing for equality, liberty and fraternity embraced Christianity with the hope of attaining those values. Unfortunately, Christianity in India also adopted the caste practices. In the salvation history, God has picked up prophets like Moses, Isaiah, Jeramiah, and others in order to set free His people from the legal, social, or political restraints or bondages. Finally, He sent His Son Jesus, the Prophet of the prophets, to set His people free. Today, God raises human beings ‘to act in the manner of prophets’ and to emancipate His people in their own respective continents and nations. Likewise, God raised Dr. Ambedkar in India to act as a prophet in order to set free His

oppressed people from the socio-political-economic slavery of India. Building an emancipatory correlation between Jesus and Dr. Ambedkar is an invitation extended to the Indian Catholic Church to emancipate the Dalits in India.

Social Hierarchy Based On Caste: An Oppressive Structure of Indian Society

India's caste system is possibly the world's longest surviving social hierarchy. It encompasses a complex order of social groups on the basis of ritual purity. In Indian context, the Hindu *Varna* system divides whole society and places *Brahmins* at the top, followed by *Kshatriyas* or warriors, *Vaishyas* or traders, and *Sudras* or servants. The Dalits are considered unworthy to be in the hierarchical status of the caste system. As the caste system is religiously underpinned, it is fiercely advocated as one of the religious practices (Srinivas, 1969: 265). Not only Hindus but also other religious communities practice caste though they may theoretically reject it (Thapar, 2004: 67). The repercussions of inhuman caste practices are oppression, economic exploitation, and social exclusion. The Caste system, by its nature, poses a threat to equality, human dignity, human rights and social justice which jointly form a human community of peace and harmony. Anything that corrodes equality, dignity, rights and justice, is undoubtedly evil.

Jesus' Encounter with His Oppressive Society

The oppressive picture of India resembles the oppressive nature of the Jewish community at the time of Jesus. Being incarnated in time and space, Jesus encountered all societal oppressive realities and challenged any structure that promoted inequality, discrimination, oppression, and repression. Thus Jesus becomes a forerunner in liberating the oppressed people of any structure.

Similarities between Jewish Society and Indian Society

Though Indian caste discrimination and Jewish racial discrimination have their origin of discrimination and inequality in purity-pollution ideology, both differ essentially. Jewish racial discrimination labels someone as untouchable by way of his/her act or physical stature that comes from biological inter-mingling of two races. On the contrary, Indian caste discrimination labels someone as untouchable by birth. Even if two individuals appear to be similar in their physical and intellectual qualities, since one is born in a particular caste, s/he is considered to be impure and untouchable. In both the cases, religion perpetuates discrimination and sustains oppression. Basically both the systems value inequality, injustice, discrimination, and oppression and distort human dignity. The victims cry in hopelessness, lifelessness, and desperation. It is they who long for liberation.

Social Stance of Jesus

Jesus' social stance gives a radical message to his community by emphasizing on regaining justice prophetically. In his first appearance in his hometown synagogue, he reads the prophet Isaiah's revolutionary call for justice and liberation for the poor (Lk 4:16-21). A carpenter's son reclaims the dream of justice. This dream contains liberty to captives, recovery of sight to the blind and freedom to the oppressed. Jesus establishes God's reign of justice here and now. He sides with the weak and confronts the powerful. His mission is defined by justice and irrupts into human history with all its structures.

Jesus' Liberative Vision and Mission

Abba Experience

Anyone who works for the liberation of the oppressed and marginalized experiences *Abba*. The traditional understanding of *Abba* experience has direct reference to the intimacy of Jesus with

the Father. But here we underscore the suffering of Jesus on account of the abandonment of the Father on the cross where he cried “My God, my God, why have you forsaken me?” (Mk 15:34) and “It is finished” (Jn 19:30). It is the *Abba* experience of the detachment from the Father. Soares-Prabhu argues that ‘*Abba*’ is a heart that goes out to the poor and oppressed (Soares-Prabhu, 2003: 4). The vision of the kingdom of God originates from the *Abba* experience that assures freedom, fellowship and justice (Soares-Prabhu, 2003: 51). Jesus’ life is an experience that expressed itself in an almost exclusive commitment to the liberation of those who suffered discrimination in any way. Thus a commitment to work for the liberation of discriminated people is an outcome of *Abba* experience and it is a free gift of God that anybody can receive irrespective of any barrier.

Human Response

Abba experience necessarily pushes anyone to respond instantly. It is a response against the forces opposed to God’s reign of justice, equality, peace and harmony. Kappen says that the reign of God is embodied in things, events, persons and experiences that lie at the root of humans’ response (Kappen, 1977: 62). The purpose of God in human history has to be realized through human effort for the liberation of all. Thus *Abba* experience is manifested in Jesus’ liberative endeavors in which everyone is invited to participate.

Preferential Option for the Marginalized

Liberative endeavours are rooted on the preferential option for the marginalized or priorities one sets in favour of the victims. This option expresses itself in concrete actions. Jesus took an irreversible stand for the marginalized that no pressure of the public opinion could ever discourage him (Jn 8:1-10), nor the violence of the established authority could frighten him (Lk 13:31-33). And he passionately executed his option by breaking the Sabbath (Mk 2:23-3:6), ignoring the rules of the ritual cleanliness (Mk 7:1-15),

touching the lepers (Mk 1:41), and dining with the socially outcasts, tax collectors and sinners (Mk 2:15-17; Lk 15:1-2) Therefore, the preferential option for the marginalized is a firm stand that challenges any oppressive and unjust structure or institution. Anyone who truly follows Jesus, chooses this option uncompromisingly.

Realization of the Kingdom of God

In fact, the preferential option for the marginalized is the beginning of the realization of the kingdom of God. For Jesus, the kingdom of God entails the overcoming of misery and the transformation of society for the sake of the poor. Realizing the kingdom of God is working for the liberation of the poor from unjust structures. Leonardo Boff says that the kingdom of God is a complete, global and structural transfiguration and the revolution of the reality of human beings (Boff, 1978: 53). Hence, anyone who works for the liberation of the poor, the marginalized and the oppressed, ultimately works for the realization of the kingdom of God.

Hope for an Ultimate Liberation

The realization of the kingdom includes both the present and the future. It is an on-going process that continues today, tomorrow and forever in various forms by different persons. Kappan says that one can understand the kingdom which has an already and not yet character. Understanding this eschatological nature of the kingdom, Jesus focuses on the future of human community, an absolute future, free from every possibility of alienation. Gutierrez argues that the prophets had on the one hand their orientation towards future and on the other, their concern with the present. Fighting in the present for a better present and future is a prophetic call.

Mahatma Dr. Bhimrao Ramji Ambedkar: The Indian Prophet of the Oppressed

God, the liberator, raised Mahatma Dr. Ambedkar in India ‘to act as a prophet’ in order to set free His oppressed people from the socio-political-economic-spiritual slavery of India (I find it more fitting to attribute the title ‘Mahatma’ to Dr. Ambedkar who extraordinarily worked for the emancipation of Dalits). In the context of Religious Pluralistic India, my attempt is not Christianizing Dr. Ambedkar, rather finding the liberative kingdom elements in him in order to arrive at pathways for the Indian Catholic Church to fight against Indian social evils.

Untouchable Experience: The Abba Experience of Dr. Ambedkar for a Prophetic Realization

Every experience of Dr. Ambedkar was an *Abba* experience (the suffering of a complete detachment like that of a Calvary experience) that convinced him to form himself as a liberator of the Dalits and such experiences were heart-breaking, inhuman and cruel. Beginning from his early age till his death, even after his death, he has been experiencing the untouchability. The chain of *Abba* experiences of Dr. Ambedkar amidst his people and in his life made him to realize the need for a liberative and prophetic mission for his people. It was a self-realization of a prophet.

Dr. Ambedkar’s Response to Abba Experience

As a response to his *Abba* experience of inhuman treatment of untouchability, Dr. Ambedkar internally felt the need of an intellectual weapon to encounter the institutionalized discriminatory structure. Thereby he grabbed all the opportunities to equip himself with the sole aim of fighting against caste discrimination and untouchability. One can intuitively understand how God works through different individuals to shape His chosen ones for a great mission.

Preferential Option for the Oppressed

The *Abba* experience of a person results in taking a stand for the poor, oppressed and the marginalized. It is undoubtedly true with Dr. Ambedkar also. Once he said, “Whenever there has been a conflict between my personal interests and the interests of the country as a whole, I have always placed the claim of the country above my personal claims... Whenever there is conflict of interest between the country and Untouchables so far as I am concerned Untouchables’ interests will take precedence over the interests of the country.” Through this he strongly advocated that India must assure equal status to all classes in religious, social, economic and political matters.

Realization of the Kingdom of God

Dr. Ambedkar placing himself at the forefront marched forward to work for the emancipation of the Dalits in India by way of the realization of Justice, Equality, Liberty and Fraternity. He walked like Moses in leading the people from slavery. He became the spokesperson of the oppressed people like any other prophets in the salvation history. Ultimately we can find him as a Kingdom Realizer. Dr. Ambedkar used the *Constitution of India* as a powerful weapon to demolish the caste-based oppressive structures and to realize the kingdom values in India.

Prophetic Hope for the Future

Dr. Ambedkar functioned as a Prophet having a great hope for the liberative future of Dalits. He awakened hope for an ultimate liberation in the hearts of the Dalits and in all those who worked for the emancipation of Dalits. His humility and unexpected entry into the Constituent Assembly definitely portrays God’s hand in his election which he had never thought of. His desire to safeguard the interests of the Scheduled Castes exhibits God’s plan for the liberation and emancipation of the oppressed people. Cumulatively they speak of God’s plan to instil a hope and liberation in the hearts

and minds of the discriminated, through Dr. Ambedkar, His chosen prophet.

Dr. Ambedkar's Just Society: The Kingdom of God

In Hindu social order, there is no room for individual justice. Dr. Ambedkar says that in his just society, caste has no place. For him justice is simply another name for liberty, equality and fraternity. This leads one to reject completely the old life before entering into new life. However, this transformation does not take place in a day or two. It is a process or a journey towards its completion. Obviously this journey gives everyone a hope for an ultimate liberation – complete liberation. It is with this hope Dr. Ambedkar laboured throughout his life for the emancipation of the Dalits. He also has set a platform for anyone who works for the same cause.

Relevance of Dr. Bhimrao Ramji Ambedkar to the Indian Catholic Church

Dr. Ambedkar, having been experienced Christianity in foreign countries, sharply critiqued the unsocial attitude of the Christian missionaries; the Indian Christian community as a disjointed community; high class nature; and the treatment of caste Christians over the Dalit Christians. It is true even with today's Christianity.

The social teachings of the Church insist on equality, liberty and fraternity through *Humanae Vitae*, *Gaudium et Spes*, *Populorum Progressio*, *Dignitatis Humanae*, *Evangelium Vitae*, *Querida Amazonia*.

Critical Evaluation of the Indian Catholic Church

Dr. Ambedkar was able to feel the pain of the Dalits because he was one of the victims of the inhuman and discriminatory caste practices. To have *Abba* experience, one needs to incarnate oneself and become an insider, perhaps only then it becomes an *Abba* experience for the particular individual. But the Indian Catholic

Church has not yet incarnated into the Dalitness. She looks at the Dalit issues as an outsider. As an outsider she would not be able to understand the suffering of discrimination. Undoubtedly, she keeps herself away deliberately.

Once Dr. Ambedkar had the *Abba* experience amidst caste discriminative practices and customs, he responded convincingly by way of working for a casteless society in order to protect his fellow human beings from untouchability, discrimination and oppression. Since the Indian Catholic Church does not have a radical incarnation and *Abba* experience, she is incapable of going against the well-established oppressive structures of the caste system. Very sadly she has incorporated the system within herself. Pathetically, she had never taken wholeheartedly any lawful measure on the field to eradicate caste system within her boundaries in order to promote equality.

Dr. Ambedkar chose always the right path which keeps the depressed class in the forefront. He never compromised his values with anything or anybody. He fought against even Gandhi the most respected figure of his time and placed the depressed class ahead of national interest. He raised his voice against all the unjust structures. But the Indian Catholic Church keeps silence whenever it is possible and especially when justice is denied at the cost of the poor Dalits.

Dr. Ambedkar certainly awakened hope for ultimate liberation of the oppressed of this country. He never wanted the depressed people to live at the mercy of the oppressors, rather he encouraged them to fight and claim their rights. Truly speaking, does the Indian Catholic Church give hope? If she gives hope, to whom does she give?

Need of Dr. Ambedkars in the Church

The Catholic Church lives today in the same situation in which Dr. Ambedkar lived prophetically. He has taken a lead in the liberating prophetic mission for Dalits in his time. The condition of the Dalits

implicitly remains same even today. Though there are number of individuals who work for the liberation of the Dalits within the Church, their effects are never brought into limelight. The Church in India needs Dr. Ambedkars to take up the same prophetic mission in our time to abolish discriminative caste practices. The mission could be successful only when the interest of the Dalits is placed above our personal interests. This is the realization of the kingdom of God in India.

Conclusion

Jesus and Dr. Ambedkar cannot be certainly weighed on the same balance. But both Jesus and Dr. Ambedkar, within their respective historical context, have done the primary and preliminary ground work for a constant fight in order to have liberation which gives the foretaste of the ultimate liberation. This constant fight against oppression has got diluted in today's Indian Catholic Church or perhaps she has even well accommodated the oppressive elements at various convenient levels. We realize that the Catholic Church, which is situated in the same social scenario, distances herself from embracing Jesus' model of radical commitment to address the issues related to oppression. Or oftentimes she washes her hand with charity works which in no way seem to emancipate the Dalits. The Indian Catholic Church must understand 'what the Dalits need is not charity but justice'.

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Dialogue among Religions: For Harmonious and Meaningful Future

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Abstract: This article takes up some scattered thoughts on interreligious dialogue. At the outset the article rushes through various stand-positions of the Catholic Church with regard to other religions pointing to the paradigm shift taken place with Vatican II. The different basic dispositions in the pluri-religious context such as exclusivism, inclusivism, pluralism and ‘*perichoresis*’ are critically evaluated. It reminds all that dialogue is a method of apostolate and emphasizes the importance of dialogue, especially in the Indian situation. It is pointed out that the dialogues among the religions are possible at different levels such as at ‘official dais’, at ‘everyday life’, at ‘prayer services’ and at ‘cooperation for justice and peace’ and the criteria cannot be the same at all levels. The article is wound up with certain concluding remarks, above all underscoring the apophatic dimension of the divine which leads all to humility and openness.

Keywords: Inter-religious Dialogue, Pluri-religious Context Models and Levels of Inter-religious Dialogue Dialogue-a Method of Apostolate –Inter-religious Dialogue.

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Overture

Till the discovery of “the new world” happened through the adventurous voyage of Portuguese navigators in the beginning of the 15th century, most of the Christians thought, the world was Christian with an exception of “the vicious Muslims.” During this period of time there was no serious and formal efforts for an encounter between Christianity and other religions. Vatican II was the first council in the ecclesial history that took expressively a standpoint with regard to other religions. Originally, even at that time there was no intention to express such statements. A declaration with regard to the relationship with Judaism, that too only with regard to the standpoint of the Church, was in the plan. Yet the discussions and deliberations occurred in the council and requests from circles outside the council led to the elaboration of the topic, which emerged as *Nostra Aetate*, the document on the relationship of the Church to non-Christian religions.¹

Besides this declaration on non-Christian religions, the Decree on the Church’s Missionary Activity-*Ad Gentes* - makes deliberations in this direction. The Pastoral Constitution on the Church in the Modern World-*Gaudium et Spes*, the Declaration on Religious Liberty-*Dignitatis Humanae* and Dogmatic Constitution of the Church-*Lumen Gentium* handle the above mentioned theme in one way or other at least indirectly. In this sense the Council is not only aware of the existence of non-Christian religions, but also has made several attempts to look at this reality from different perspectives. This is very clear if we compare some teachings of the Church in Vatican I or those just before Vatican II with the documents of Vatican II. In 1854, in his sermon *Singulari quadam* Pius IX stated:

It must, of course, be held as of faith that no one can be saved outside the apostolic Roman Church, that the

¹ Cf. Introduction to *Nostra Aetate*.

Church is the only ark of salvation, and that whoever does not enter it will perish in the flood. Yet, on the other hand, it must likewise be held as certain that those who are in ignorance of the true religion, if this ignorance is invincible, are not subject to any guilt in this matter before the eyes of the Lord (ND 1010).

In Vatican II, however, we notice a different basic disposition. *Lumen Gentium* states:

Those who, through no fault of their own, do not know the Gospel of Christ or his Church, but who nevertheless seek God with a sincere heart, and moved by grace, try in their action to do his will as they know it through the dictates of their conscience – those too may achieve eternal salvation (LG 16).

The declaration on Non-Christian Religions, *Nostra Aetate*, not only acknowledges the importance of the dialogue among world religions but also speak of the other faiths in positive terms:

The Catholic Church rejects nothing that is true and holy in these religions. She looks with sincere respect upon those ways of conduct and of life, those rules and teaching which, though differing in many particulars from what she holds and sets forth, nevertheless reflect a ray of that truth which enlightens all men (NA 2).

The standpoint revealed in these statements surely indicates a paradigm shift in the history of the Church.

A Glance to the History

Karl Marx wrote in ‘The Communist Manifesto,’ “The history of all hitherto existing society is the history of class struggles.” Even those who do not subscribe to the Marxian understanding of history and society find an element of truth in the above sweeping statement. In this line, from a particular perspective one can say that the history of humankind has been in a way to a great extent the struggle of

some to dominate over others. I think, this averment is true to a great measure when we look into the history of religions and societies.

Christianity was persecuted in its early centuries. However, once it was accepted as the official religion of the Roman empire, the situation changed in manifold perspectives. The struggle for domination by the religion or the secular world over the other is seen almost in all parts of the world in different phases of history. Religion and secularism often moved ahead in hostility, though certain temporal peace treaties and attempts for reconciliation can be pointed out here and there. I look at the present crisis and conflicts that exist between the religion and the secular outlook, both in India and elsewhere, as the continuation of the age-old struggle and the fights for domination. Wherever there is domination, though apparent peaceful atmosphere may artificially be created for some time, it can never provide sustainable peace and harmony. Mutual respect rooted in one's own conviction which is not unawareness of the experiential and linguistic limitations, especially in dealing with the ultimate questions, can truly contribute to an atmosphere of genuine dialogue, peace and harmony.

Decades back there was difference in the understanding about secularism in the western world and in India. In the western world the expression secularism means an inherent hostility to religion. In India secularism was not understood in terms of hostility against the religion at least during the formulation of Indian constitution, but as an openness to all religions without favouring any religion in particular. I think in the recent past as the broad understanding about Hinduism is being manipulated and narrowed as *Hindutva*, the common Indian understanding gets blended with the western understanding to a great extent, though there are still some who cherish the former insight and stand and speak for the same.

It is only knowing and understanding that can lead to lasting and sustainable harmony and peace, not any refined strategies for the old game. In the game for dominance, in fact there is no lasting winner

and loser, but only sporadic intervals of violence. Such intervals need not be misunderstood as peace and harmony.

Dialogue as a Method of Apostolate

The capability for reciprocal communication even of complex ideas differentiate human beings from other animals. Dialogue is surely a means for knowing and understanding and so it is a way to true peace and harmony. Dialogue could be understood in manifold ways: At purely human level it is reciprocal communication which can lead to common goal or to interpersonal communion; in the context of religious plurality it can mean - all positive and constructive interreligious relations with individuals and communities of other faiths which are directed at mutual understanding and enrichment in obedience to truth and respect for freedom. Witnessing one's own faith and exploring the religious convictions of the dialogue-partner in whole sincerity, not as a strategy, are parts of it. The encyclical letter "*Ecclesiam Suam*" sees dialogue as a recognized method of apostolate and as a way of making spiritual contact.²

Thus, in the spirit of Vatican II, dialogue promotes better understanding and collaboration between Christians and the followers of different religious traditions. It paves the way for special attention to disciplinary formation in religious studies and encourages the emergence of persons committed to it. The mission as a participation in the mission of the triune God can only proceed nowadays in dialogue and can only be conducted in humility, where human intellectual independence and autonomy are achieved and appreciated to a great extent.

Indian Situation

In Indian context the encounter with religions is not something, which takes place on the formal dais alone, but it belongs still to the day-to-day life of a common man. When Christianity speaks of its

² Cf. Paul VI, Encyclical Letter – *Ecclesiam Suam*, August 6, 1964, n. 81.

uniqueness and singular revelation took place in Jesus Christ and endorses the entry into the Church instituted by him, the traditional Hinduism leaves all religions to be what they are, namely the different ways, to arrive at the absolute mystery. Christianity is not a bare religion of philosophical certainties, on the contrary an engagement for the person of Jesus Christ, whom Christians proclaim as the Lord and master of this world. So dialogue is a matter of Christian interest. In this context one needs to approach the dialogue partner in genuine respect and modesty, not in an air of “big-brother” mentality.

The Basic Disposition Required

In the pluri-religious context one’s basic disposition with regard to other religions can be generally categorized as exclusivism, inclusivism and pluralism. Let me explain very briefly of these three possibilities.

Exclusivism

Those who have the disposition of exclusivism operate on the conviction that they have the monopoly of truth. When a tradition claims to have all the truth for all time, anything which goes against this “truth” should be false. Prior to Vatican II the Church fostered this disposition.

This disposition has both advantages and disadvantages or positive and negative sides. The positive side of it is that it gives new energy, enthusiasm and a “security feeling” in all what one does and speaks. The danger of it is the intolerance, pride, closeness and contempt for those of other faiths. One tries to bring others of different convictions to his or her conviction even using violence. The history provides us with enumerable examples for the same.

Inclusivism

Inclusivism is an attempt to solve the problems which emerge from the disposition of exclusivism. Each one can follow his or her own way. No one needs to condemn other ways and possibilities. One

can even foster relation with those who have different convictions, provided that he experiences all what is to be known or to be understood or to be loved or to be lived is already present in his or her tradition. One can be at peace with oneself and others. This is an intelligent disposition. Because it provides the space for one to be faithful to one's own tradition and at the same time to be open and universal. Basically this is the official position of the Church since Vatican II.

But this position is not totally free of problems. A neutral observer sees elements of arrogance and megalomania in this position. The thoughts behind such a disposition are the following, "Only I have the privilege of a comprehensive understanding and the ability for tolerance; only I can assign the proper positions for others, for 'my tradition' or 'my truth' is better and higher than all others. Though this disposition, on the one hand reconciles with the fact of pluralistic understandings and expressions of 'religious truths' and provides the space of relationship with them, on the other hand fails to recognize the independent intellectual content of the truth, for truth is one for the theists, another for atheists, or for Islam or for Buddhism. Since there are many opposing teachings depending upon the basic outlook of each religion, which has a horizon of its own *mythos*, erudition in one's outlook cannot be criterion of truth for all.

Pluralism

Anyone who takes the experiential reality as it is without any manipulation and cherishes the intellectual honesty, cannot but see the gap between the ideal proclaimed and the reality lived. This gap is true with regard to all religions for they are lived and proclaimed by imperfect human beings. Where there is awareness that my religion as it is lived is not totally identical with the ideals preached, but still remains the symbol of the right paths and those with other faiths also can have the similar convictions, though there are shortcomings at the existential level like mine, one may neither

simply reject the religious claims of others nor see all what is good in other traditions as already present in my own tradition. In such a situation the one option remains, is, is the third category of disposition, namely pluralism, which sees that different religions, in spite of all the shortcomings at the existential level, as parallel possibilities, which lead to the ultimate goal of human beings.

One's duty and responsibility that emerge from such a disposition is not to disturb others and never try to convert others to my convictions and my ways. On the contrary each one should deepen oneself in his or her own tradition so that an encounter takes place at the end at the deepest level where there is the least dichotomy between what is preached and what is lived. In other words, be a better Christian, a better Marxist, a better Hindu and in that process you would surely experience some common paths where others of different faiths also travel.

This disposition has many advantages at the practical level, but also difficulties. It provides space for tolerance and respect for others who profess different faiths. It avoids syncretism and eclecticism. The problem with this disposition is that it makes the haste conclusion that all traditions carry the inner strength for growth and maturity. It does not see the advantages of mutual learning and thus closes the possibility for newness and widening of one's own horizon.

Perichoresis

In the present situation where we see through the merits and limitations of these different standpoints, we should go for a fourth basic disposition, which would resemble *perichoresis* or *circumincession*.³ Meeting with different world-religions is indeed

³ Perichoresis is derived from the Greek *peri* "around" and *chorea*, which refers to "a dance, especially the round dance with its music". *Perichoresis* is a term referring to the relationship of the three persons of the triune God (Father, Son and Holy Spirit) to one another. The Latin expression *circumincession* is derived from the Latin *circum*, "around" and *incedere*

a great enrichment and in the process we may realize that the faith and practice of our neighbours different from ours not only places our faith and practices in question but also can be an opportunity for deepening of our understanding about our own faith and practices. It can make us opener to see other religions in their complimentary and enriching aspects and perhaps even enable us to seek answers to certain particular open-questions of our faith in the religion of our neighbours provided we hold the religiosity of our own faith intact. This happens in the concrete encounter in life.

A total exchange takes place in *communio*, not in argumentative and verbal communication. Religions exist not in total isolation in the vacuum, but in the mutual “*Ich-Du*” relationship⁴ like day and night.

meaning “to go, to step, to march along” and used for the same concept. Modern authors extend the original usage as an analogy to cover other interpersonal relationships. The term “co-inherence” is sometimes used as a synonym. Since humans are made in the image of God, a Christian understanding of an adequate anthropology of humans’ social relations is informed by the divine attributes, what can be known of God’s activity and God’s presence in human affairs. Theologians such as Hans Urs von Balthasar, Henri de Lubac, and Joseph Ratzinger locate the reciprocal dynamism between God and God’s creatures in the liturgical action of sacrament, celebrating the sacred mysteries in Eucharistic communion, in a hermeneutic of continuity and apostolic unity.

⁴ *Ich-Du* (“I-Thou” or “I-You”) is a relationship that stresses the mutual, holistic existence of two beings. It is a concrete encounter, because these beings meet one another in their authentic existence, without any qualification or objectification of one another. Even imagination and ideas do not play a role in this relation. In an ‘I-Thou’ encounter, infinity and universality are made actual (rather than being merely concepts). Martin Buber stressed that an *Ich-Du* relationship lacks any composition (e. g., structure) and communicates no content (e. g., information). Despite the fact that *Ich-Du* cannot be proven to happen as an event (e. g., it cannot be measured), Buber stressed that it is real and perceivable. A variety of examples are used to illustrate *Ich-Du* relationships in daily life—two lovers, an observer and a cat, the author and a tree, and two strangers on a train. Common English words used to describe the *Ich-Du* relationship include encounter, meeting, dialogue, mutuality, and exchange.

My own religiosity reveals its full meaning only in relation to the religiosity of the other. Therefore, the relationship of the religions to each other is to be seen neither as exclusivism (my standpoint alone is true) nor as inclusivism (all other standpoints through mine) nor as pluralism (all strive independent from each other for the same goal), on the contrary as *perichoresis* or *cicumincessio sui generis*, that is, the mutual penetration taking place without distorting or destroying the other and without getting distorted or destroyed by the other.⁵

The positive sides of this basic disposition are tolerance, openness, big-heartedness and mutual trust. Since there is mutual encouragement and demand, no religion is totally alien to the other. We all need each other. This total encounter can complement each other and set certain aspects in the right order. The biggest challenge here is to answer two basic questions: Who does guarantee the mutual penetration in the right sense? What is the basis of such a disposition? Searching into the creative role of hermeneutics and establishing the same might lead to the right answers to these questions, opines Raymon Panikkar.⁶ He proposes *diatopical hermeneutics* for intercultural communication.⁷

⁵ Cf. R. Panikkar, *Der neue religioese Weg*, 27.

⁶ Cf. *Ibid.*

⁷ *Diatopical* hermeneutics stands for the thematic consideration of understanding the other *without assuming that the other has the same basic self-understanding*. The ultimate human horizon, and not only differing contexts, is at stake here.

Diatopical hermeneutics is a hermeneutic that goes beyond traditional *morphological* hermeneutics and *diachronical* hermeneutics, inasmuch as it “takes as its point of departure the awareness that the “topoi,” locations within distinct cultures, cannot be understood with the tools of understanding from only one tradition or culture.” *Morphological* hermeneutics deciphers the treasures (*morphe*, forms, values) of a particular culture, a single tradition. *Diachronical* hermeneutics represents mediation between temporally distant eras in the cultural history of humanity, but still, normally, with reference to a single tradition.

Religious identity is not a party membership, that is, not a part of the whole, but fidelity to the wholeness of one's being, which at the same time related to the whole. Each religion resembles a language. Just as there are non-translational expressions in a language there are elements in religions, which cannot be translated without losing the nuances of what is stated. So there is a need to understand a religion from within. The issues, which require clarification for understanding, are not only of a purely intellectual character. They are also of a political nature and depend upon economic factors and psychological reactions. The history with its aftereffects of colonialism, exploitation, mistrust, deceit and fights from all sides cannot be abolished overnight. Religions are more than intellectual constructs. These points are to be taken into consideration so that the interreligious dialogue becomes a genuine dialogue without being reduced to a refined strategy.

In *Redemptoris missio* John Paul II reminds all that interreligious dialogue is part of the Church's evangelizing mission. By dialogue what is meant here is a process of mutual instruction and enlightenment. True interfaith-dialogue is the result of deep respect for all that the Spirit has wrought in the various religions. Through dialogue the Church seeks to uncover and cultivate the "seeds of the word" and the rays of truth that are to be found among all peoples and in all religious traditions. Doctrinal compromises are surely to be avoided. Because without being rooted in one's own religious traditions and convictions true inter-religious dialogue will not be

Seeking, among other things, to break out of the *hermeneutic circle* created by the limits of a single culture, *diatopical hermeneutics* attempts "to bring into contact radically different human horizons," traditions, or cultural locations (*topoi*) in order to achieve a true *dialogical dialogue* that bears in mind cultural differences. It is the art of arriving at understanding "by going through these different locations" (*dia-topos*). To achieve this, there must be a renewed encounter between *mythos* and *logos*, between subjectivity and objectivity, the heart and the mind, rational thought and the spirit that flies free breaking all rigid mental schemes.

possible.⁸ Only a religious person will be able to understand the nuances of what is said by another person of different faith, just as it is said only a *jnani* can recognize another *jnani*. One has definitely to strip off the “big-brother mentality” to have a proper encounter.

The Various Levels of Inter-Religious Dialogue

The inter-religious dialogue can take place at least at four levels: a) at the level of official dais b) at the level of day today life c) at the level of prayer d) at the level of cooperation for peace and justice. This distinction indicates that there are differences in the process and procedure involved at each level. One need not be well-versed at all levels, but one needs to be aware of such varied possibilities to be open to the prompting of the Holy Spirit.

At the Level of Official Dais

Considering the Indian context and the history of Indian theology, I think, the inter-religious dialogue at the official level can take place in three ways. These three ways correspond three directions or contexts one observes in Indian theology. In other words, the various theological endeavours in India could be classified into three categories, namely a) Religious-cultural context b) Spiritual-contemplative context and c) Socio-political context. Let me comment on these three contexts very briefly for clarity sake.

Theology in Religious-Cultural Context

The separation between religion and culture is extremely difficult in Indian context, since they have grown and developed intertwined for thousands of years. The expressions like *Ashram*, *Guru*, *Sannyasi* etc. are familiar to every Indian like the lines on the palm, though these expressions emerged in Hindu-religious milieu.⁹ They remind us of search of the Indian spirit for millions of years for the absolute and mark the important aspects of Indian religious and intellectual legacy. We can say that the Indian culture has greatly

⁸ Cf. RM 56.

⁹ Cf. C. Valluvassery, *Christus im Kontext und Kontext in Christus*, 95.

been influenced by the *Sannyasis*, who in their passion for the absolute and the eternal left everything and the seers (*rishis*) and the saints, and displays the same in very subtle ways and otherwise.¹⁰ This spirit is still actual today in the Indian life. S. Radhakrishnan, a renowned Indian philosopher, writes of it so pointed:

From the beginning of her history India has adored and idealized, not soldiers and statesmen, not men of science or leaders of industry, not even poets and philosophers, who influence the world by their deeds or by their words, but those rarer and more chastened spirits, whose greatness lies in what they are and not in what they do; men who have stamped infinity on the thought and life of the country, men who have added to the invisible forces of goodness in the world. To a world given over to the pursuit of power and pleasure, wealth and glory, they declare the reality of the unseen world and the call of the spiritual life. Their self-possession and self-command, their strange deep wisdom, their exquisite courtesy, their humility and greatness of soul, their abounding humanity, proclaim that the destiny of man is to know himself and thereby further the universal life of which he is an integral element. This ideal has dominated the Indian religious landscape for over forty centuries.¹¹

The fact that emperors and kings and other leaders with bare foot and great respect have called on *Sannyasis* and *Rishis* in their *Ashrams* to receive blessing and pieces of advice, is not something of the remote past in India. The same is continued still by the politicians and others who adorn responsible and leading positions in society in India. I do not want to idealize this situation. There are, of course, pseudo-*Sannyasis* and corrupt politicians and religious

¹⁰ Cf. F. Wilfred & M. M. Thomas, *Theologiegeschichte der Dritten Welt. Indien*, 182.

¹¹ S. Radhakrishnan, *Eastern Religions and Western Thought*, 35.

leaders who commercialize religion and “god”. But it is an undeniable fact that the lifestyle of *Sannyasis* and the context and culture of *Ashram* are still alive and influential in Indian societies today. Therefore, the theology in India cannot but remain untouched by these sources of Indian life and thinking pattern. This is applicable for inter-religious dialogues too.

The theology in the religious-cultural or *ashramic* context is above all stamped by *advaitic* (non-dualistic) outlook. Inter-religious dialogue in the religio-context cannot overlook the *advaitic* tradition which reached philosophical peak through the interpretations of Sankara.¹²

Theology in Spiritual-Contemplative Context

Theology in spiritual-contemplative context is not totally apart from the theology in religio-cultural context. The difference is mainly on the emphasis. Whereas the theology in religio-cultural context makes use of the philosophical legacy spread over the Upanishads and Advaitic Tradition, the theology in spiritual-context places the focus on the intuitive and mystical aspects of the religious experiences. Jules Monchanin (Param-Arubi-Anandam 1895-1957), Henri Le Saux (Swami Abhishiktananda, 1910-1973), Bede Griffiths (Swami Dayananda, 1906-1993) etc. have been the pioneers in this direction. The gist of theological thinking here is the following: The real point of meeting of religions (meeting between Christianity and Hinduism, in Indian context) must be in the mystical experience. Hinduism seeks to know God to experience the reality of God in the depths of the soul. It is at this level that Hindus

¹² Sankara was an Indian philosopher and theologian, lived in 8th century, who consolidated the doctrine of Advaita Vedanta unifying and establishing the main currents of thought in Hinduism. His works in Sanskrit discuss the unity of the *Atman* and *Nirguna Brahman*, “*brahman* without attributes”. He wrote copious commentaries on the Vedic canon (*Brahma Sutras*, Principal *Upanishads* and *Bhagavad Gita*) in support of his thesis. His works elaborate on ideas found in the *Upanishads*.

and Christians have to meet so that they can find out what they have in common and where the real difference lies. It is in this union with God – behind images and concepts – in the ground of the soul that true meeting must take place. The Christian monk assumes all the classical spiritual paths of India, namely *niskamakarma*, *bhakti* and *jnana* and consequently works out a spiritual theological synthesis of them all. Thus a way for the true dialogue with Hinduism is paved.¹³

Dialogue is readiness to listen to the other as other. It is more than just stopping the talking; it demands inner silence that enables one to understand the other as he or she understands himself or herself; it is a “putting into brackets” one’s own conviction. In the real dialogue the moment will occur when the listener speaks, not the prefabricated answer, but the word to the partner who has been understood. This is a different dimension of dialogue.

Theology in the Socio-Political Context

Theology in the socio-political context is a later development. The growing awareness about the injustice prevailing in the society coupled with the realisation that the salvation provided by our Lord Jesus Christ is not totally otherworldly, but is to be realised here and now paved the way for the theology in the socio-political context. The insight that there are not only unjust incidents and actions, but also unjust structures which beget and multiply unjust realities functioned as the catalyst for the development of theology in socio-political context.

In 1947 India became independent. The concentration in the years followed it was on the strengthening of the unity of the nation and the democratic social life and the improvement of economic realities. The Christian response during this time was intensifying of the social help and development projects. The time immediately

¹³ Cf. J. G. Weber, ed., *In Quest of the Absolute*, Kalamazoo: Cistercian Publications and London: Mowbrays, 1976; Abhishiktananda, *Hindu-Christian Meeting Point within the Cave of the Heart*, Delhi, 1976.

after the independence was predominantly a time of euphoria. Meanwhile many got rid of the dreamlike optimism about the immediate post-independence era. A small elite group from the homeland, that was brought up, educated and trained during the colonial period according to the vision and mentality for the colonial power, could easily assume the power in the society and the oppression and the injustice remained in everyday life without any change. What practically changed was only the colour of the oppressor: the gap between ‘the have’ and ‘the have not’ was further widened and the percentage of those who had to live in the existence-minimum, in hunger and poverty, became higher. The situation slowly gave birth to various liberation movements with varied characters. *Dalits*-movement, the mobilisation of outcastes etc. are just to name a few. In Kerala, the leadership of Sri Narayana Guru played a vital role in the socio-religious uplift of the Ezhava community, that was discriminated in many ways. In Kerala context, the social analysis of Marxism was also of great support in exposing the unjust social structure and it inspired many to dream of a just and equal society.

In short, we can say that at the beginning almost all liberation-movements for social and economic uplift of the downtrodden emerged independent of any ecclesial encouragement and but it paved the way for retrospection on the role and responsibility of the Church. Gradually emerged also ecclesial movements, which stood for social justice and equality. The initiative for the same came up from a small group of Christians who joined hand with those who belonged to other religions and ideologies for social transformation. Thus began liberation movements which stood for the uplift of *Adivasis* in North India and the fisher-folk in Kerala, where the involvement of priests and the religious were conspicuous and vital. In this context emerged a row of theologians who inspired on the one hand the activists to intensify their fight for social justice and on the other hand who began to theologially articulate the happenings at the basis level. To this group belong theologians like

Samuel Rayan (1920-2019), Sebastian Kappen (1924-1993), Soares Prabhu (1929-1995) etc. Interreligious dialogue in this context will have surely different tone and colour from what was said above about the other two contexts.

At the Level of Everyday Life

In Indian context the inter-religious dialogue takes place undoubtedly at the level of day-to-day life. This is because Christianity is a minority in India and the Christians are mingling with persons of other beliefs at various levels of societal life. It could be at the workplace, it could be at the social engagement, it could be during a travel, it could be at the bus stop, railway station or at the airport. The list can be enlarged easily, for the pluri-religious context is part of Indian life. Knowingly or unknowingly an Indian Christian enters into an intra-religious dialogue as he mingles with persons of other beliefs in his day-to-day life. Because the lives of certain persons of different faith with whom he regularly or rarely interacts edify him at times in a more comprehensive manner than the so called “saints” within his own religion. One of the reasons could be, as the old saying goes, the fact that familiarity breeds contempt.

Surely there are saintly persons who profess a different faith than Christianity, live a life more “Christian” than many of the ‘Sunday Christians.’¹⁴ Mahatma Gandhi is a classic example for such occurrence. He once happened to have said, “I believe in Christ, but not in Christians.” What made him say so was undoubtedly the gap between what is proclaimed and what is lived. Pope Paul VI formulated it pointedly as he said, “Modern man listens more willingly to witnesses than to teachers, if he does listen to teachers,

¹⁴ What I mean here is the fact that there are many Christians on the paper - in the sense that they are once baptized and there is record of the same in their respective parishes - they visit the Church once in a while or participate in the Sunday Mass, but whose lives are totally alien from the Christian values and message of love, hope and faith.

it is because they are witnesses.”¹⁵ It is a matter of fact we come across in our life persons who do not profess Christian faith, but live much more as “Christian” than the so called Christians, on whose head once the baptismal water was poured and whose names are in baptism register book. It may lead one to the realisation that the so called Christian virtues are not the monopoly of the Christians.¹⁶ When I pen these lines, pictures of many non-Christians who edified me in my short-span of life, with their words and deeds concretely occur to my mind. Such an experience provides one a completely different disposition and platform in the inter-religious dialogue.

At the Level of Prayer

The conversation between Jesus and the Samaritan woman narrated in the Gospel of John (4:1-26) sheds light on certain insights on prayer. Jesus tells the Samaritan woman, “Yet a time is coming and has now come when true worshipers will worship the Father in spirit and truth, for they are the kind of worshippers the Father seeks.”

¹⁵ *Evangelii nuntiandi*, 41.

¹⁶ To make an interreligious dialogue a real dialogue where genuine ‘give and take’ takes place, a Christian should accept the reality in all modesty: a) A Christian does not have the monopoly of the ethical quality, neither at the natural nor at the supernatural levels. Even that which are at time called as specific Christian moral teachings such as all-embracing love and love of enemies, returning blessing against a curse and acknowledging the human dignity of all everywhere etc. can be seen in other religions too, almost in the same wording, perhaps five hundred years before Christ. b) The fact of God choosing a particular people for a particular purpose does not indicate the rejection of others. c) A Christian cannot have also a monopoly of salvation. If we take seriously the voice of our conscience, the light of our reason and the Christian teaching about God’s will of universal salvation, then we cannot doubt that the salvation is offered to everyone in the world. We can’t actually speak of ‘ordinary’ or ‘extraordinary’ paths of salvation since criteria for such a discussion lack. Neither the number nor the quality nor any other possibility with regard to the personal salvation or redemption is revealed to us. Christ himself has turned back such a question brimming with ungrounded confidence and claim.

The exegetes aver that what Jesus refers here are not something abstract, but the truth he reveals and the Holy Spirit he gives. Holy Spirit, as the breath of divine life, makes itself felt in prayer. Pope John Paul II states, “Wherever people are praying in the world, there the Holy Spirit is, the living breath of prayers.”¹⁷ It is this realisation that prompted Pope John Paul II to organize two important summits of prayer for members of all religions at Assisi. For some ardent Christians this gesture of Pope John Paul II was not fully digested. As Pope John Paul II addressed the Roman curia on October 22, 1987, he not only reflected on the Assisi day of prayer for peace which took place on October 27, 1986, but also referring to the letter to the Romans Chapter 8, verses 26 and 27 he stated, “We can indeed maintain that every authentic prayer is called forth by the Holy Spirit, who is mysteriously present in the heart of every person.” In praying one submits totally to God and recognizes one’s own poverty in relation to him. Prayer is therefore an important means of realizing God’s plan for humanity.¹⁸

At the Level of Cooperation for Justice and Peace

The combined endeavours for justice and peace undoubtedly provide a platform for the meeting of different religions. Various religions can surely play a preeminent role in preserving peace and in building a space and place worthy of human being. Religions, worthy of the name, inherently contain an openness and submission to the transcendental will of the absolute. The spiritual vision they foster of human being make them capable of respecting fundamental human rights. Thus a religious and ethical vision can overcome the instincts of aggression and xenophobia and avert the tendency to violence and terrorism. Surely one has to distinguish between the perennial values a religion upholds and the external observances and practices, which are supposed to be guided by those values.

¹⁷ *Dominum et vivificantem*, 65.

¹⁸ John Paul II, Address to the Roman Curia; *Origins* 16 (Jan 15, 1987): 561-563, at 563.

Whenever those practices and observances deviate from the values owing to the human limitedness, they are to be continuously corrected, refined, updated and maintained. The power for the same is inherent in all authentic religions and such a realisation opens us the possibility for cooperation with other faiths for justice and peace.

Some Concluding Remarks

The different levels and contexts of interreligious-dialogue - actual, required and possible, elaborated above - reveal that we cannot have fixed, ready-made and perennial pattern for interreligious dialogue. We have to be open to the prompting of the Holy Spirit in each concrete context.

The existence of various religions and their insights and focuses cannot be outside the plan of God. The declaration of Vatican II on the Relation of the Church to the Non-Christian Religions states:

The Church, therefore, urges her sons to enter with prudence and charity into discussion and collaboration with members of other religions. Let Christians, while witnessing to their own faith and way of life acknowledge, preserve and encourage the spiritual and moral truths found among non-Christians, also their social life and culture (NA 2).

The different levels and contexts possible for inter-religious dialogue, indicate the fact all cannot be experts at all levels and contexts. Human beings are different not only in appearance, physical, intellectual and emotional capacities but also in pre-understanding, thinking-pattern, perception and in the *myths* and *logos* (Valluvassery, 2001: 129). they cherish. So the unity that we all aspire for need not be uniformity and monolithic. In this vast universe and in the long history of the Church we all have only a limited role to play, on account of limited span of life and our existential facts which are limited in time and space. So perennial formulae of interreligious dialogue for all time and all contexts

cannot be created based on any particular time and space. If we are convinced that our existence now on this earth is not outside the divine providence, we need not be too much worried of the future. We all are just instruments in the hands of God. As being endowed with intellect and will we are to apply our mind and cooperate with the prompting of the Holy Spirit.

In his speech delivered on December 11, 1962 opening Vatican II, Pope John XXIII said, “The substance of the ancient doctrine of the deposit of faith is one thing, and the way in which it is presented is another.” These words have meaning in the context of interreligious dialogue too. Considering the complex, manifold and pluri-religious situation of India Samuel Rayan proposed the order of an Indian Christology as follows:

a) to start with the indwelling Christ who is my rest, best and deepest self and b) to proceed to the Christ who is in all and is the Self of all, the Universal Self and the *Antaryamin*; and c) to go to the new community which experiences Christ as indwelling and loving, and shares in his personal experience; and d) finally to see that his experience was an experience of being wholly from God and for God, and of being born of God; of belonging to the world of sin and death and of God’s redemptive action which raises the dead and calls into existence that which is not. Here, in the historical Jesus, with his awareness of the indwelling Father as his best Self, the circuit is complete.¹⁹

In the interreligious dialogue, the starting point need not be always the same. The starting point can vary as per the context. We have a great paragon of it in the Areopagus sermon of St Paul recounted in Acts 17: 16-34: Paul had encountered conflicts as a result of his preaching in Thessalonica and Berea in northern Greece and had been carried to Athens as a place of safety. While he was waiting

¹⁹ S. Rayan, *An Indian Christology: A Discussion of Method*, in: *JD* 1 (1971), 213.

for his companions Silas and Timothy to arrive, Paul went to the synagogue and the Agora (marketplace) to preach about the Resurrection of Jesus. Some Greeks then took him to a meeting at the Areopagus, the high court in Athens, to explain himself. There Paul begins his address saying, “As I walked around and looked carefully at your objects of worship, I even found an altar with this inscription: TO AN UNKNOWN GOD. Now what you worship as something unknown I am going to proclaim to you.” St Paul begins where his listeners stand. He even quotes some of the poets over there that we are his offspring (Cf. Acts 17:28). This very words and deeds of St Paul makes clear that the starting point need not be always the same.

In the similar manner we should also be able to use our intellect and imagination to launch the dialogue with our neighbour of another faith. The starting point is to be passing to the context, not pre-fabricated notions and thinking pattern. Total openness is necessary for a real dialogue. The willingness to learn from each other is the first and foremost prerequisite for a true dialogue. It is always a hindrance when one or both partners claim to possess the absolute truth, because through such a claim the vacuum required to receive something new is stolen away and that which is already full, cannot receive anything more. In the context of interreligious dialogue with Hinduism or Buddhism or any religion belongs to the category of gnostic religions we cannot have the same trajectory as when we have dialogue with Judaism or Islam, which belong to the group of prophetic religions, for here a common theological language is still to be developed.

For a mind which is trained in the western thinking pattern, which operates on the principle of non-contradiction, the biggest problem is the question on the ‘uniqueness of Christ.’ How is this to be maintained, when we speak of a total or radical openness to be safeguarded to enable a truthful dialogue, which is never to be deteriorated as a diplomatic strategy hiding the sublime superiority complex?

According to R. Panikkar the question regarding ‘the safeguarding of the uniqueness of Christ’ is a pseudo-problem, which started since the loss of corporate identity (ecclesial in this case) and crystallised as a problem since modern science became the paradigm of intelligibility. It is love that entails the uniqueness of something or somebody. The scientific world is a loveless universe. Science approaches things in an impersonal and quantifiable manner. But we should not forget the fact that modern science is not the only paradigm of knowledge.

The question of the uniqueness of Christ appears as a problem once we approach Christ without love, i.e., “scientifically”. We try to find his identification and not to discover his identity when love is absent. Love is not an acknowledged epistemological tool and epistemology is basically served from ontology. That result the split between the intellect and the spirit, between intellectual life and spiritual life.

My statement that my mother is the most loving person in the world does not prevent or deny the space for my dialogue partner to state that his or her mother is the most loving person in the world. If this is true, then where is the problem?

Words and formulations are needed and important, but they cannot substitute life-witnessing or proclamation at the existential level. As Pope Francis states, Christianity should grow by attraction. It is not a product to be sold, but a way of life that embraces all without any prejudice or pre-calculation, for God has revealed himself as one who participates in the smiles and tears of human being in the word-incarnate, Jesus Christ. Herein lies the universality and uniqueness of Christian message.

Besides, the awareness on the apophatic dimension of the divine leads us to humility and openness.

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Solidarity and Fraternity of All Brothers and Sisters: A Creative Reading of *Fratelli tutti*

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Abstract: The Encyclical *Fratelli Tutti*, is an urgent appeal to all the citizens and faith-believers of the world to course-direct on a different path, for the survival of the world. The author makes a re-reading of the document, calling for social action through a creative social friendship and fraternity while underlining the key points in the document. This paper highlights on the theme of socio-political love. Positively, the author agrees that as a *Social Encyclical*, it would do well towards social friendship and support a culture of encounter. In this process, inter-faith dialogue, solidarity and forgiveness could contribute much towards an ecumenical and global renewal. With an inclusive approach to life and faith, the author affirms the inter-faith fraternity for the common good. In this context, the religious leaders will have to be authentic mediators in the name of human fraternity, by being at the service of all brothers and sisters.

Keywords: Fraternity, Solidarity, Social Friendship, , Fratelli tutti, Inter-Faith Dialogue

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Pope Francis has signed his “Social Encyclical” *Fratelli tutti* (FT 6; Francis, 2020)¹ on 3rd October, 2020 in Assisi, with an urgent call to all men and women on earth to follow the example of Jesus. By addressing persons by the loveable words ‘brothers’ and ‘sisters’, people of all caste, colour and creed, we wish to find a close bond with others beyond the blood relation. In daily social living, strangers and neighbours are made into ‘brothers’ and ‘sisters’. Christians too, win the hearts of people by addressing them with the same familiar words with love. They are expressions of family experience with close ties - words that all cultures and all times comprehend. They are evocative signs of solidarity which is inscribed at the heart of our common humanity. From the Biblical times and even earlier, history proved that to be close to others is to “experience the violence of Cain, the greed of Jacob, the jealousy of Joseph’s brothers” (Henning, 2020) and yet human beings continued to love the ‘other’ who is not one of its kin.

The encyclical FT is Francis’ vision for a post-pandemic world. It brings together themes that Pope Francis has underscored in various contexts over the past years of his pontificate. This first-of-a-kind document embraces ‘brotherhood’ among different religions, and calls for religious freedom, condemning religious persecution. The Covid-19 pandemic proves that “no one can face life in isolation”. Therefore, certain ideals with some tangible ways are laid out in FT for unitedly building a more just and fraternal world in daily relationships, in social life, politics and institutions, etc. The time has truly come to “dream, then, as a single human family” of “brothers and sisters all” (FT 7-8).

¹ Pope Francis’ 200-page third Encyclical Letter “Fratelli tutti” (henceforth FT) on *Fraternity and Social Friendship*, was published on 4th October 2020, on the occasion of the feast of Saint Francis of Assisi. This was inspired by St. Francis, like the Pontiff’s second Encyclical *Laudato Si*, on the Care of Our Common Home, marking the first Encyclical on ecology.

Keeping the purpose of Francis' writing of the Encyclical, i.e. solidarity, fraternity and social friendship among all brothers and sisters on earth, the author delves into a different reading of *Fratelli tutti*, while underlining the key points in the document, which is addressed to the entire Church, as well as to the whole world. With a particular key to understanding Pope Francis' appeal to the world, the author elaborates on the real family bond of fraternity and the local community. Taking the clue from Francis, this paper visions out an open heart, and how that has to be done in order to open itself to others in the world with love and concern, through social friendship, respecting the dignity of each person as brother and sister. This can enhance a universal fraternity, holding to human rights, and by fulfilling the societal responsibilities by all the stakeholders in the world. This needs to be done following the model of the Good Samaritan, through a better kind of politics that is at the service of the common good. In this context, the Church as a whole has to fulfill its socio-political task following the paths of renewed encounter and forgiveness, and not just remain naïve.

Following the courageous yet fragile, bold but non-violent universal leaders: Francis of Assisi, Martin Luther King, Desmond Tutu, Mahatma Gandhi, Blessed Charles de Foucauld and Pope Francis himself, the present author confirms that the present world religious leaders will have to be "authentic mediators" in the name of human fraternity, through dialogue, common cooperation, mutual knowledge and respect. The world religious leaders will have to be at the service of enhancing universal brotherhood and unity, beyond all caste, creed and affiliations, thus establishing peace and justice through genuine inter-faith fraternal dialogue. The author invites all to co-create together a world that is built on love, forgiveness, justice, equality, and together inspire change of policies, practices, and behaviour at all levels.

Keys to Understanding *Fratelli Tutti*: Fraternity and Social Friendship

The third encyclical of Pope Francis, after *Lumen fidei* (2013) and *Laudato Si'* (2015), *Fratelli tutti of fraternity and social friendship*, consists in treading on the dark clouds over a closed world, meeting the need of the strangers on the road - poor, migrants, neighbours in most need - envisaging and engendering an open world with a heart open to the whole creation by means of better kind of politics, dialogue and friendship in the society, through the willing and self-sacrificing paths of renewed encounter. A relatively long magisterial document, the encyclical FT that calls for fraternity and social friendship, is a summary of Pope Francis's thoughts garnered over the past years as people's priest and a pope of the periphery. According to Pope Francis, St. Francis of Assisi "did not wage a war of words aimed at imposing doctrines; he simply spread the love of God (...) and inspired the vision of a fraternal society" (FT 2-4). We have common membership in the human family, for we are the children of one Creator; and that in a globalized and interconnected post-pandemic world, only together can we be saved.

The Grand Imam of Al-Azhar says, "*Fratelli tutti*, is an extension of the Document on Human Fraternity, and reveals a global reality in which the vulnerable and marginalized pay the price for unstable positions and decisions (...) It is a message that is directed to people of good will, whose consciences are alive and restores to humanity consciousness."² In fact, FT is based on fraternity and social friendship that have concerned the Pope in recent years and on the

² Grand Imam Ahmad Al-Tayyeb, reacts in his Tweet, to the release of Pope Francis's Encyclical, *Fratelli tutti*, stating that Pope Francis "restores to humanity its consciousness." Al-Tayyeb co-signed the Document on *Human Fraternity for World Peace and Living Together* with Pope Francis in February 2019 in Abu Dhabi. FT contains several citations from the Document on Human Fraternity.

themes put forward in the *Document on Human Fraternity for World Peace and Living Together*, in February 2019.

The document opens with a rather “bleak assessment of the current state of the world”(Le Normand, 2020) stating that all brothers and sisters without borders are going through the “dark clouds over a closed world” (Ch. 1, FT 9-55) and “shattered dreams”, that seem to be the end of historical and human consciousness, lacking a proactive plan for everyone (FT15-28). Shadows over the closed world spread everywhere, “plunge humanity into confusion, loneliness, and desolation”. FT alarms against a “culture of walls”, of organized crime, fueled by fear (FT 27-28). With a “throwaway” culture in the world today, with insufficient universal human rights often being violated; within certain conflict and fear in the midst of globalization and progress, yet without a shared and decisive roadmap (FT 29-31). As the present pandemics and other calamities in history have proven, there has been an absence of human dignity on the peripheral borders (FT 37-41), with mixed feelings on the illusion of communication, shameless aggressions on various areas, and having information without wisdom (FT 42). The mass media has deteriorated ethics (FT 29), creating isolated virtual circles without freedom and constructive dialogue (FT 43-50).

Francis observes trends in our world that hinder the development of universal fraternity. According to him, “Globalized society makes us neighbours, but it does not make us brothers” (*intended sisters too!*, FT 12; Francis, 2014:1; *Caritas in Veritate*, CV19). The grey and dark clouds over a world that is so closed up on itself are observed in: the despair and discouragement that are widespread in society; the polarization that impedes dialogue and living together; the persons who are considered easily “sacrificed” and discarded; the inequality of rights and the new forms of slavery; and the moral deterioration and the weakening of spiritual values. Today one witnesses the manipulation and deformation of concepts such as, liberty, unity, democracy, freedom and justice; social community

and history; selfishness and indifference toward the common good; market logic based on profit and the culture of waste; unemployment, racism, poverty; disparity of rights; slavery, women and organ trafficking, subjugation of women, etc. (FT 10-24). In the face of these challenges, FT insists that “The road we must travel is that of closeness; it is the culture of encounter” with hope (FT 30); that God continues to sow abundant seeds of goodness, together with love, justice and solidarity, that has to be realized each day. It is with hope that we look beyond any personal convenience that limits our horizon, and it opens us up to grand ideals.

He warns that there are existing “signs of a certain regression” (FT 11). For him, words like democracy, freedom, justice or unity “have been bent and shaped to serve as tools for domination”, and “to justify any action” (FT 14) by the powerful. Therefore, the first victims of such self-centred agenda and xenophobia, are the voiceless poor. The document is a cry of alarm against demagogic populism. A false and “closed populist groups distort the word ‘people’” (FT 160), and this “unhealthy” and “irresponsible” populism by some political leaders who “seek popularity by appealing to the basest and most selfish inclinations of certain sectors of the population,” (FT 159) has to be denounced. Global problems call for global actions. The resurgence of nationalism, calls for a reformed, more ‘family-like’ United Nations. Pope Francis, a follower of “the theology of the people” says, “each of us is fully a person when we are part of a people” (FT 182). Therefore, he does not disqualify “people”.³ Living within multiple forms of subjection and of self-contempt (FT 51, 53), there is still a ray of hope always.

The document proposes that it is a social encyclical dedicated to putting forth a new vision of fraternity and social friendship, while treating the universal dimension of the doctrine of fraternal love.

³ The word ‘*people*’ appears 95 times in the new encyclical, FT.

The title *Fratelli tutti* being an expression of Saint Francis of Assisi (Admonitions, 6.1)⁴, is an evocative that encourages all to dream as a single human family and as fellow travellers sharing the same flesh. It is invitation to all men and women who will accept this reflection, and enter into a dialogue with love, that transcends the barriers of geography and distance. Pope Francis concludes the document with this prayerful wish: “Come, Holy Spirit, show us your beauty, reflected in all the peoples of the earth, so that we may discover anew that all are important and all are necessary, different faces of the one humanity that God so loves.”

Family Bond of Fraternity and Community

Family is part of one’s life and living. It cannot be chosen. One is born into it. A larger family called a community becomes a deliberately chosen social structure, which can be a source of rivalry, of jealousy. Then it becomes a problem to live in. Just as one shares the same space in the family, one learns to manage conflicts in family and community. Brothers and sisters of blood prefer to exist for what they are, having their identity, role and respect in their family. The first social nucleus is a gift from God that we receive, preserve and invest into. Yet, it has to be nourished by a certain form of friendship and closeness in order to commit to it as members. Often enough, the family or group of families can turn into a clan. We all are part of one community or the other, either chosen by will or born into. And here, we hear often the possessive pronouns - “my brother”, “my sister”. So often the priests address the congregation with these ‘dearness’; terms, expressing a common space, and a shared identity. This is true of the family, as well as of an “elective community, which creates a boundary, defines a belonging.”

⁴ Saint Francis of Assisi used the expression *Fratelli Tutti*, to propose a way of life marked by the flavour of the Gospel.

Jean-Jacques Goldman, a popular French singer wrote: “You are part of my community, the one I have chosen, the one I feel, much more than that of blood.” Here then, is an opening up to the other, with a belonging that brings like-minded beings together. We become part of a family, a history, a country. In the midst of diverse communities, there is still that belonging, that unity. Different or distant, the other is still the same as us. This ‘difference’ makes life what it is. We begin to know, accept, acknowledge and appreciate the difference through knowing each other.

France as a nation has its motto: *liberty, equality, fraternity*. But fraternity is different from the rest. Fraternity cannot be imposed by law. It is built by all of us. But, why fraternity? In this pandemic period, paradoxically, we need to build human fraternity as particular cultures are closing in. According to Véronique Albanel, a philosophy professor, fraternity is an intentional family build on solidarity, that is, “to live as a ‘family’ by welcoming others while respecting their person and their differences” (Henning, 2020). It is hospitality experienced on an equal footing. A community that engages in organizing and mobilizing as a family. Christian faith has to push us from Christian community to “community of the other”, holds Albanel. He says, a successful fraternity leads to others with solidarity, leaving extreme positions. It opens us to the larger unknown community, becoming truly the universal community (Catholic). This decisive and deliberately chosen enlarged community is at the heart of Christ intention – that all be one – not imaginary or ideal. It becomes a true and concrete human encounter. The encounter between Francis of Assisi and the Sultan at Damietta in 1219, or that between Pope Francis and the Grand Imam of Al-Azhar, Ahmed El-Tayebin, in February 2019 in Abu Dhabi, signing the document on “human fraternity”, are true examples. A movement towards a universal community. Similarly, the spirituality of Charles de Foucauld lived a life of fraternity with

the Muslim brethren, uniting all in one universal “everyone’s brother”, Jesus (Henning, 2020).⁵

“The word became brother” (flesh), (Henning, 2020)⁶ – Jesus, “the eldest of many brothers” (Rom 8: 29), whom all Christians are to follow, till the total fraternity is established, including all enemies within the family and outside. And the basis of such fraternal community is real contact. One cannot be a brother or sister unless another brother/sister relates that way. You need the other. Therefore, communal fraternity is an experience, lived with the neighbours, in daily life’s events. Quoting a Roman’s observation of the second century Christian community Tertullian, wrote, “Look, they say, how they love one another.” More than a community, it was “fraternity” (Greek word, *adelphotès*, fraternity being the proper name of the Church). In the words of Anne Lécu, a Dominican Sister, “To be brother and sister is to receive oneself from the same Father.” One cannot be brother or sister all by himself/herself. Fraternity engages in a relationship and recognizes the common humanity, - inclusive of all migrants, foreigners,

⁵ Paul VI speaks of Charles de Foucauld in his encyclical *Populorum Progressio* as - holding Jesus to be “everyone’s brother” ‘and not as the “universal brother” which is a bad translation. Cf. *Letter to Madame de Bondy* (7 January 1902). Saint Paul VI used these words in praising the saint’s commitment: Encyclical Letter *Populorum Progressio* (26 March 1967): AAS 59 (1967), 263, as referred in FT, *footnote* n.288. Charles de Foucauld, lived in Algeria, in the midst of the Tuareg Peoples, a nomadic Berber tribe. He went towards the different other, to the point of living “to work to establish the Fraternity on earth,” he declared in 1904, founding a “zaouïa”, an Islamic name for a sort of monastery or community of prayer and hospitality.

⁶ “The Word became Brother,” wrote Christian de Chergé, one of the seven Trappist monks of Tibhirine who were martyred in 1996, and beatified in 2018 among the eighteen Martyrs of Algeria. He said, “Brother of Abel and also of Cain, brother of Isaac and Ishmael at the same time, brother of Joseph and of the eleven others who sold him, brother of the plain and brother of the mountain, brother of Peter, of Judas and of both of them in me.”

neighbours and prisoners - of the same flesh. To sum it all, the only way to find the unseen God, is to recognize Him in all brothers and sisters.

“You are all brothers and sisters” (Mt 23.8). The call to universal fraternity requires openness to human beings who find their fulfilment in the sincere gift of self to others, with a love that calls for a greater ability to accept others and to reach out to the margins. A love capable of transcending borders for a greater good, is the basis of social friendship. This friendship for greater good, promotes values that advance integral human development. For, every person is valuable and “every human being has the right to live with dignity” (FT 107). This is achieved by: thinking and acting as a community; combatting the structural causes of poverty and inequality; the state being actively present and invest in assistance to the vulnerable; insuring that no one is excluded; establishing a lasting peace based on a global ethic of solidarity and service.

Vision of an Open Heart, Open to the World

Envisaging and engendering an open world (Ch. 3, FT 87-127), we are asked to move beyond ourselves engrained with the unique value of love - a love that is ever more open within open societies that integrate everyone (FT 88-98). We all suffer from the inadequate understandings of universal love (FT 99-100). Francis exhorts all to go “‘outside’ the self”, to find “a fuller existence in another” (FT 88), through the spiritual dynamism of charity leading toward “universal fulfilment” (FT 95), without selfishness (FT 92-93). It calls us to go beyond a world of “associates” with a universal love that promotes persons and lead towards liberty, equality and fraternity, while also promoting the moral good and the value of solidarity (FT 101-117). Re-envisaging the social role of property that ultimately belongs to the Creator-Giver and which needs to be shared, the rights of all peoples especially the poor and abandoned, and the rights without borders (FT 121-127) must be upheld.

A fraternal society with ethics and right to live with dignity, will promote dialogue and defeat the “virus” of “radical individualism” (FR 105). Every family needs to be protected with respect for its “primary and vital mission of education” (FT 114) with benevolence and solidarity (FT 112). All will have to fight against poverty and inequality (FT 115). Our God is universal love, and we are called to universal fraternity to share this love with an open heart, in an open world, without walls and divisions through social friendship, seeking what is morally good, and socially ethical. It is a call to solidarity, encounter and gratuitousness.

Only a *heart open to the whole world* (Ch. 4, FT 128-153)⁷, going beyond borders and their limits can bring healing in the world (FT 129-132). Through a fruitful exchange of reciprocal gifts of self and resources, a gratuitousness open to others, can there be solidarity and brotherhood (FT 137-141). This universal horizon of solidarity has to start with local region at the grass root level with a local flavour, thus connecting what is local with the universal (FT 142-153). Only a heart that opens to the whole world, works in favour of universal fraternity. It does so by: welcoming, protecting, promoting and integrating migrants, whose lives are “at stake” (FT 37), and the marginalized; becoming aware that either we *all* are saved or no one; executing a global juridical, political, and economic order that favours the development of all peoples in solidarity. To do so, *gratuitously*, we need to welcome strangers, without expecting tangible benefit; doing charity simply because they are good in themselves; serving without personal gain. For, “The true worth of the different countries of our world is measured by their ability to think as part of the larger human family. God always gives freely” (FT 139-141). All have rights to live with dignity in one’s own country. But those “fleeing grave humanitarian crises” must be given protection of citizens’ rights and assistance (FT 38-40) by

⁷ Part of the first chapter (FT 37-41) and the entire fourth chapter of FT (128-153) deal with the issues on migrants.

granting visas; opening humanitarian corridors; assuring lodging, security and essential services; offering opportunities for employment; helping in family reunification; protecting minors; guaranteeing religious freedom and promoting social inclusion by avoiding the use of the term “minorities” (FT 129-131). Any healthy culture of solidarity opens the minds and hearts to understand those who are different because differences represent an opportunity for growth (FT 133-135); in such universal fraternal communion, each human group discovers its own beauty; that this ‘limited human beings’ are limitless. As in a polyhedron – an image favorite to Francis – the whole is more than its parts, but each one of them is valued and respected (FT 145-146). It is possible to open to our neighbours within a family of nations. There is a need, therefore, for global governance, with long-term planning (FT 132) based on the principle of gratuitousness.

Social Friendship and Universal Fraternity with Dignity

The concept “social friendship” in the subtitle of FT along with fraternity, has been with Francis from 2000, then Cardinal Jorge Mario Bergoglio, Archbishop of Buenos Aires (Le Normand, 2020). He writes, “social friendship within a society makes true universal openness possible” and that a “love capable of transcending borders is the basis” (FT 99) of a genuine ‘social friendship’. This kind of friendship allowed the Good Samaritan of the parable (Lk 10: 25-37) “to interrupt his journey, change his plans, and unexpectedly come to the aid of an injured person who needed his help” (FT 101).

Social dialogue and friendship in society are paramount for a new culture, built together based on consensus and truth (FT 198-214]. Propagating a new culture of encounter, becomes a habitual joyous culture, a new-normal of acknowledging others by recovering act of kindness through concrete charity, understanding and acceptance of the other, because “no one is useless and no one is expendable” (FT 215). Dialogue and encounter allows one to respect the point of view of others. Relativism is not a solution, because without universal

principles and moral norms, laws become merely “arbitrary impositions” (FT 206; *Laudato Si*, 123). In this regard media has a special role: without exploiting human weaknesses it must be directed toward generous encounter with the least, promoting proximity and the sense of human family (FT 205). The miracle of “kindness”, has to be recovered because it is that which “frees us from the cruelty and creates a healthy coexistence and opens paths in places where exasperation burns bridges (FT 222-224).

In order to achieve “social friendship and universal fraternity”, it is necessary to “call for an acknowledgement of the worth of every human person” (FT 106). Unless this basic right to live with dignity is upheld, “there will be no future either for fraternity or for the survival of humanity” (FT 107). All those who consider the migrants and other disadvantaged people being “less human” are to be denounced. Francis writes: “This illusion, unmindful of the great fraternal values, leads to “a sort of cynicism. For that is the temptation we face if we go down the road of disenchantment and disappointment (...) Rather, it is closeness; it is the culture of encounter. Isolation, no; closeness, yes. Culture clash, no; culture of encounter, yes” (FT 30). The inalienable dignity of all people, that comes from God, is the source of fraternity; and therefore, the death penalty is “inadmissible” (FT 263) and a “just war” (Augustine, *Epistola* 229; FT, *footnote*, 242) ⁸ can never exist (FT 258).

In the Way of the Good Samaritan

Pope Francis holds that the global culture is sick with many social ills, which have been complicated by the Covid-19 pandemic. In order to overcome such ‘sickness’ we need today’s Good Samaritans, with a sense of solidarity, who gift their life, time,

⁸ Saint Augustine, who coined the phrase “just war” that no longer can be upheld, said that “it is a higher glory still to stay war itself with a word, than to slay men with the sword, and to procure or maintain peace by peace, not by war” (*Epistola* 229, 2: PL 33, 1020), as cited in FT, *footnote*, n.242.

money, energy, concerns and compassion to the neighbours on the peripheries, who are deprived and are different from us, by the very structures that the Global society has created. The poor and disabled are side-lined. We as brothers and sisters, need to share our goods with each other, because they belong to all. This has to be done with local flavour guided by universal worldview (think globally act locally!). All these are possible only through a culture of encounter that involves listening and reimagining the dividing structures. We cannot go back to the past ways of the world, instead, the ‘new normal’ is a chance to build a new society based on loving our neighbour with a vision laid down by Pope Francis in FT. The pandemics of inequality, xenophobia, individualism, ‘my-family-alone attitude’, self-seeking for comfortable living, hoarding of wealth for oneself, etc. exist today. These maladies inconvenience the poor and marginalised who are struggling through varied difficulties in life. It turns into bigger problems, expanding to a global scale, when the wealthy exploit the poor and economic inequality grows. While pockets of progress happen, the poor, the elderly and the disabled are left behind, and the gap is widened.

The solution to all these problems comes from the biblical parable of the Good Samaritan. The context of the parable is, *a stranger on the road* (Ch. 2, FT 56-86), abandoned on the wayside - a story constantly retold today of rape victims or victims of communal violence (FT 63-71). The various characters of the story (FT 72-76) are all part of each of us. Part of all the characters, namely, the assailants, the passers-by (Levite, Pharisee), the wounded and abandoned victim are in most of us. In the face of such reality, we question: who is my neighbour? Francis says, “Jesus asks us not to decide who is close enough to be our neighbour, but rather that we ourselves become neighbours to all” (FT 80). FT summons us to be actively involved in rehabilitating our wounded societies. The story of the Good Samaritan is being repeated today: determinism or fatalism are recourse to, in order to justify our own indifference. The elite ‘throwaway’ society tends to ignore others, especially the

weak. Often the governance and state authorities allow and encourage social exclusion. Today, we are witnessing ‘social distance’ and political apathy. True love in social friendship does not care if one in need comes from one place or another. For, love shatters the chains that keep us isolated and separate; it builds bridges. In the face of suffering, the only course is to imitate the Good Samaritan. What is learnt here is a decision to start anew as a Good Samaritan, meet the needs of the neighbours without borders (FT 77-83) and hear and respond positively to the pleas of the strangers (FT 84-86), who are different from us. Discovering a discarded and injured stranger, one can have two attitudes: ignore or help. An inclusive or exclusive attitude will define the person we are, and which political, social or religious group we belong to. In an unhealthy and “illiterate” society that cares less for the frail and vulnerable (FT 64-65), we need to become neighbours to others (FT 81), and be co-responsible in creating a society without prejudices, self-interests, and cultural barriers (FT 77). Love builds bridges and “we were made for love” (FT 88) according to “a universal dimension” (FT 83), recognizing Christ in the face of every excluded person (FT 85).

It is not just that the Samaritan was an outsider showing concern for a stranger, a neighbour different from him, or that the priest and the Levite, the religious leaders ignored him, following protocols. The Samaritan gives his time, prioritizing in helping the affected stranger. He enters into an encounter. The first step in building a healthier society starts with such encounter with our neighbours, people who are different and are struggling. This leads one to be aware of the larger social issues that cause others to suffer: the political and social structure that need to change and recognize the universal destination of goods, for as the early Church held, the earthly resources are not for us to hoard, but to be shared. It is a fact, while some nations hoard up tons and tons of food, others go through famines. The gap between the haves and have-nots widen.

When such big divide happens, the deprived ones naturally pursue better opportunities and migrate to other places. While doing so, the global society which one falls prey to, does harm to local cultures. The migrants lose their unique cultures. Therefore, care must be taken to provide good opportunities in the places that people are born. If that does not happen, migrants have to be welcomed with respect and friendships and not treating them as nuisance and act violently against them (FT 132-133). We need to act locally with a universal worldview. There has to be a movement towards peace and universal brotherhood. This is what Francis calls a culture based on encounter, involving listening, accepting, and ‘reimagining the structures’ that cause people to suffer. This means, giving strangers time like the Good Samaritan on an international level. It means listening to poor nations, involving them in decision-making, to find what is best for all people. As brothers and sisters we need to come out better by ridding ourselves of our individualistic attitudes and build a culture of collaboration, dialogue and encounter.

Jesus summarises the greatest commandment in the Bible: “You shall love the Lord, your God, with all your heart, with all your being, with all your strength, and with all your mind, and your neighbour as yourself “(Lk 10:40). All of religion and humanity is about having a loving heart for God and for creation, including men and women, filled with compassion and care. This is so, because Jesus is Christ, who is God-man, in whom divinity and humanity meet. Therefore, the love of God, with logical consistency and spiritual integrity, necessarily draws us to a love for all our brothers and sisters – the whole human race (Barron, 2020).

Better Kind of Politics at the Service of the Common Good

The world needs *a better kind of politics* (Ch. 5, FT 154-197) with positive and pro-active forms of populism and liberalism, thus distinguishing ‘popular’ from what is ‘populist’ (FT 155-162). To create an open world with an open heart, a better kind of politics for the common and universal good is essential, politics that is

“popular”, practising social charity out of “political love by integrating the economy with the social and cultural fabric into a consistent and life-giving human project” (Catholic Telegraph, 2020). Politics is meant to be at the service of the common good (FT 180) and makes it possible for people discuss and dialogue (FT 160) in a democratic way, and not fomenting selfishness in order to increase its own popularity (FT 159). It protects work, an “essential dimension of social life”, and enables everyone to develop their own abilities (FT 162), ultimately to have a dignified life.

Certainly, there are benefits and limits of modern days’ liberal approaches (FT 163-169). The international powers, including the UNO, must work through social and political charity (FT 170-185), and promote the force of law rather than the law of force, by favouring multilateral accords that better protect even the weakest states. The United Nations must give substance to the concept of a “family of nations” working for the common good and the protection of human rights (FT 173-175).

We need politics impregnated with political love (FT 177-182). It is a universally effective love with a local flavour (FT183-185). The exercise of political love has to be manifested through selfless sacrifices born of love, a love that integrates and unites (FT 186-192), with solidarity and subsidiarity (FT 187). According to Francis, politics has to guarantee fundamental human rights, and resolve social exclusion; sale of organs, weapons and drugs; sexual exploitation and human trafficking; slave labour; terrorism and organized crime which are to be eliminated. For him, hunger, is “criminal”, because food is “an inalienable right” (FT 188-189). We have to measure its success with fruitfulness over results (FT193-197). Dialogue built on social friendship, is the basis for a better politics that seeks the truth. Dialogue that leads to a culture of encounter with respect, in turn becomes a passionate way of life.

“Charity, according to the teaching of Jesus, is the synthesis of the entire Law” (cf. Mt 22:36-40). Manipulation of laws for political gain, destroys politics itself. We need a better kind of politics, one that: truly promotes the common good; does not seek electoral gains; serves as a channel for personal/fraternal growth; promotes an economy that favours productive diversity and business creativity; is far-sighted and capable of a new, integral and interdisciplinary dialogue. Therefore, FT calls for a social and political order whose soul is social charity: making it advance towards a civilization of love; recognizing *all* human beings as brothers and sisters. Charity through socio-political activities needs the light of truth, the light of reason and the light of faith. Social charity makes us love the common good; it makes us effectively seek the good of all people, in the social dimension that unites them. In socio-political activity, every person is sacred and deserves our affection and our respect, and if at least one person is helped to have a better life, that “already justifies the offering of my life” (FT 195).

Francis, therefore, writes a ‘political encyclical’⁹ based on theological and spiritual foundations, affirms his direct positions (FT 120)¹⁰ asserting what he says, and observes reactions for further dialogue and debate having political implications, just as the Gospel has. Though FT is not a dogmatic discourse, Francis shifts his points of view with risks, from secular to religious principles. For example, the concrete application on cancelling the debt of poor countries or no to *just war*¹¹, is not so simple, and can be debatable. But he expresses his point of view in fraternity. Similarly, his move

⁹ Encyclicals are quite regularly political, like the one written by Leo XIII (*Au milieu des sollicitudes*, on the Church and State in France in 1892), Pius XI on communism and Nazism, or John Paul II.

¹⁰ For example, Francis confuses and compromises when he assures that the natural right to private property will be secondary to the principal of the universal destination of created goods (FT 120).

¹¹ Francis’ intervention in Mali in 2013, for example, helped to protect the population.

towards decentralization in the Church and the culture of dialogue, can shake up the Church, yet he takes the risk of making people react (Noé, 2020).

Christian Socio-Political Task: Not to Be Naïve

Pope Francis has criticised “neo-liberal” system, “populism” and the claim for “individualistic-rights” (FT 111); he makes a harsh observation of excesses globalization, financial systems, and attitudes towards migrants whose fundamental rights are violated. But he does not provide any lines of action for putting an end to them. FT may seem to be too political for a spiritual leader, but it is his fight against the great evils that are plaguing today’s world. In a less diplomatic style, with a “left-wing” label attached to him, Francis tries to renew the language of the Church, following a radical Gospel path.

As head of state, as a great spiritual and political leader, he is charting a “common course” for humanity, on concrete situations drawn from the many national episcopal conferences that report on tragic events, violent conflicts and the civil wars in the world. He is, therefore, at the service of conflict resolution. With frankness, he diagnoses and confronts the political aberrations, going out of the confine of spiritual sphere. He prides where it hurts, by “attacking the various logics that exclude the poorest” (de Neuville, 2020)¹² and exposes the economic, societal and cultural systems that produce the “culture of waste”- a “throwaway culture” (FT 188).

Radical social Catholicism must take up the task at this perilous moment of politics of the powerful. Catholic world is underperforming in public life, though its social doctrine, poorly known and insufficiently appreciated by the faithful, is admired

¹² Marcel Rémon SJ, an expert on Catholic social teaching, a professor of geopolitics and director of the Center for Social Research and Action (CERAS), makes the statement.

outside. Persons inspired by Christian thinking kept a balance between personal responsibility and a concern for community, between individual rights and the common good. Today, we hear from Church leaders, the cry of cultural warfare, of gloom and danger, than the equilibrium of rights and duties, responsibility, hope and possibilities. The Church's socio-political teachings with radical moderation is missing today. In this context, FT offers a sharp critique of the *status quo* and at the same time sees human beings capable of transcendence in the face of growing inequality. As *Rerum novarum* insists on the dignity of work and the right of workers to organize collectively to maintain their family life and its values, FT empathizes with those outside the families with social friendship, to form a fraternity (FT 162; Francis, 2015, 2014).

It has to bring to the world “the joy of the Gospel,” with charity and justice by speaking fearlessly and consistently against the social and moral failures. Church's public witness is what Francis offers with decisive steps, towards democracy, religious freedom, and human rights. To be a “counter-cultural” force, one has to be critical of the *status quo*, with a monolithic political views based on the Gospel. But, Francis's most enthusiastic detractors speak about “intrinsic evils,” towards which he is leading the Church, because he speaks boldly, on migrants, racism, labour rights, climate change, social justice, war, economics and death penalty.

If we do not disassociate from right-wing politics, there will not be any progressive Catholicism (Dionne, 2020)¹³; the young will dismiss the institutions of faith and religious people; the more we are with secularism and the doctrine of moral relativism, the

¹³ The decline of progressive Catholicism reflects a reorientation of the hierarchy during the John Paul II and Benedict years, and a transformation of the Church's social base. A 2015 Pew Research report found that 13% of former Americans Catholics, now identify with other religious traditions. Only half of millennials (57%) raised Catholic have remained in the Church. Most of the Catholic are older and, more conservative.

traditional moral order will die in misery. We can never question the sincerity of another's faith, which is the mysterious gift of grace. Certainly, there are conflicting attitudes toward Francis's project. Creating a culture of life, rooted in solidarity, dialogue and conversion will go a long way to cease the vicious cycle the culture wars have let loose. Pope Francis says, "If the Church is alive, it must always surprise." (Francis, 2014; see also Wenders, 2018; FT *footnote*, 278)¹⁴

Paths of Renewed Encounter and Forgiveness

The *paths of renewed encounter* have to start anew from the truth, which is the art and architecture of peace, because without righteousness or justice there is no peace (FT 225-235). The process of encounter begins with the least in the society, through the value and meaning of forgiveness (FT 233-245). The renewed community will have to confront the inevitable conflict, the legitimate conflict through forgiveness that brings about reunion of brothers and sisters under one universal bond of brotherhood (FT 237-243). Francis stresses that fraternity and friendship in society are the means to build a better, fairer and more peaceful world. For this, one has to face and acknowledge the past mis-encounters, and work on re-encounter (FT Ch. 7; cf. Catholic Telegraph, 2020), in order to heal the past wounds through forgiveness. This is the best way to move on with memory, which is, forgiving but not forgetting (FT 244-254). One has to dare, confront the inevitable conflict, and acknowledge the historical truth in order to win justice which is

¹⁴ Francis told this in St Peter's Square on Pentecost Sunday 2014. "If the Church is alive, it must always surprise [...] A Church that doesn't have the capacity to surprise is a weak, sickened and dying Church." FT n. 281 quotes, "God does not see with his eyes, God sees with his heart. And God's love is the same for everyone, regardless of religion. Even if they are atheists, his love is the same. When the last day comes, and there is sufficient light to see things as they really are, we are going to find ourselves quite surprised". It is taken from the film *Pope Francis: A Man of His Word*, by Wim Wenders (2018).

indispensable for establishing peace without violence, saying no to war and a “globalised indifference”(FT 30). Total elimination of nuclear arms is “a moral and humanitarian imperative” (FT 262; cf. Francis, 2017: 394-396). No more injustices (just wars), instead use the fund for eliminating hunger in the world (FT 255-262). So too, the death penalty is inadmissible, and it is to be abolished (FT 263-270) precisely because of the respect for “the sacredness of life” (FT 283), which cannot be readily sacrificed, such as the unborn, the poor, the disabled and the elderly (FT 184).

The processes of renewed encounter are necessary on the path toward peace and they are: true reconciliation; common projects without denying individuality; recognizing, protecting and restoring the dignity of all; with option for the poor, the dispossessed and the marginalized; practising forgiveness. Jesus, who was against violence or intolerance, tells us to forgive “seventy times seven” (Mt 18:22). True forgiveness and reconciliation are achieved in conflict and are resolved through dialogue, by abstaining from enmities and mutual hatred. It facilitates an honest discussion of differences, founded on a desire for justice, without forgetting or impunity, so that the individuals or communities may not fall into the vicious circle of vengeance. Pope Francis, therefore says, “I ask God to prepare our hearts to encounter our brothers and sisters, so that we may overcome our differences rooted in political thinking, language, culture and religion” (FT 254, footnote 236; see also Francis, May 2014).

Peace and Justice through Inter-Faith Fraternal Dialogue

Peace-building is an “art” that “involves us all” with “a never-ending task” (FT 232). It is not absence of war but a “tireless commitment” for responsible leaders, “to recognize, protect and concretely restore the dignity” of brothers and sisters (FT 233). Peace, connected to truth, justice and mercy, is ‘proactively’ aims at forming a society based on service to others in the pursuit of reconciliation and mutual development (FT 227-229), where

everyone must feel “at home”. The peace process places the human person, his or her dignity and the common good at the centre of all activity (FT 230-232). Forgiveness without forgetting, is a precondition for peace. By not forgetting, one chooses “not to yield to the same destructive force that caused them so much suffering” (FT 251). Confronting injustice, one must defend his rights in order to safeguard his God-given dignity (241- 242). Forgiveness does not mean impunity, but rather, justice and remembrance, renouncing the destructive power of evil. Horrors of the past memory keep the flame of collective conscience alive so that we do not become anaesthetized, and remember the good, and those who have chosen forgiveness and fraternity (FT 246-252). It “enables us to pursue justice without falling into a spiral of revenge or the injustice of forgetting” (FT 252). A journey of peace among religions has to begin with God’s way of seeing things, for God sees with his heart. Fundamental religious convictions abhor violence. Sincere and humble worship of God, through diverse religious rituals and traditions, bears fruit in respect for life, dignity and freedom. Therefore, religious leaders are called to be true “people of dialogue” and “authentic mediators” (FT 284) in order to cooperate in building peace.

All *religions of the world* (Ch. 8, FT 271-287) will have to be at the service of enhancing fraternity in our world - the ultimate foundation of universal brotherhood and unity. As God’s creatures, with different religious affiliations, we are called to the *service of fraternity* (Ch. 8) by establishing social friendship. With an openness to the Father of all, we recognize our universal brotherhood and sisterhood. Jesus Christ and his message inspire all Christian actions and commitments towards fraternity, starting with the recognition that we are all brothers and sisters.

Violence has no basis in religious convictions, and terrorism is due to erroneous interpretations of religious texts, as well as “policies linked to hunger, poverty, injustice, oppression” (Ft 283). It is an

international crime against security and world peace, and it must be condemned (FT 282-283). With memory of injustice and violence inflicted upon different faith communities, the Christian identity must be purged of all hateful prejudices and superiority (FT 277-284), and establish social friendship with the members of other religions, in order to live as brothers and sisters under the same Creator, in an inter-faith and ecumenical spirit (FT 285-287). Religions are called to be at the service of fraternity in the world. Only with the awareness that we are all children of single Creator, can we live in peace within the society. The different religions do contribute to building fraternity. It is, therefore, necessary to guarantee religious freedom - a fundamental human right for all believers (FT 279). Seeking God helps us recognize one another as travelling companions. Instead, the denial of religious freedom and freedom of conscience leaves humanity impoverished and divided. In this context, the Catholic Church as a home, opens her doors, because She is a mother who builds, breaks down walls and sows seeds of reconciliation. She does not “restrict her mission to the private sphere” (FT 276), staying at the margin, renouncing the political dimension of life itself. The Church has to attend to the common good and to integral human development, according to evangelical principals (FT 278).

Dialogue and Friendship in Society means: approaching, speaking, and listening in order to know and understand one another, and find the common ground. Through a culture of encounter, each person can learn something from others, that no one is useless, and no one is expendable. A pluralist society that encourages dialogue, respects the dignity of others in all circumstances and integrates differences, thus guaranteeing a genuine and lasting peace. It recognizes other people’s right to be themselves, creating an atmosphere of friendliness. Certain attitudes or actions that do not help towards a genuine dialogue are: any aggression manifested, e.g. on social networks; monologues; humiliating and discrediting others. “Authentic

social dialogue involves the ability to respect the other's point of view" (FT 203).

Conclusion

Fratelli Tutti, "You are all brothers" (Mt 23:8) and sisters. Therefore, God is our Father. So together we pray, "Our Father", hallowed be your name." (Lk 11.1-4) implying that we might make it holy for us, that God might be honored above all. Everything else in the spiritual life flows from this prioritization. "Your Kingdom come." God's kingdom refers to God's way of ordering things. Jesus' teaching and his manner of life give us a very good idea of what this kingdom would look like: peace, nonviolence, forgiveness, healing, walking the path of compassion. In fact, while the Good Samaritan is proposed as a style of responding amid these epic times, Pope Francis recalls Martin Luther King, Desmond Tutu, Mahatma Gandhi and Blessed Charles de Foucauld, as models for everyone to imbibe these qualities, and to identify with the least in order to become "the universal brother" (FT 286-287). Recalling these great leaders, Pope Francis reminds the world religious leaders to be "authentic mediators" and makes appeal that, in the name of human fraternity, dialogue be adopted as the way, common cooperation as conduct, and mutual knowledge as method and standard (FT 285; see also Francis, 2019).¹⁵

Pope Francis is only a human being, *a fratello*, and he can be wrong. Criticizing his words and actions need not make one an ideologue. What is needed, is to forgive each other as brothers and sisters. We often pray, "Forgive us our sins for we ourselves forgive everyone in debt to us." Forgiveness is central to the teaching of Jesus and to the suffering of the world where people are incapable to forgive,

¹⁵ Pope Francis quotes from the *Document on Human Fraternity for World Peace and Living Together*, which he signed on 4 February 2019 in Abu Dhabi, along with the Grand Imam of Al-Azhar, Ahmad Al-Tayyib: a milestone of interreligious dialogue.

both on the smallest, most intimate level and on the grandest, geopolitical scale. Through the last two prayers, one to the Creator and one ecumenical, Francis teaches us to plead with God as brothers and sisters, that we be given the grace to forgive and be united to love, and live in fraternity and social friendship. God invites us to co-create with Him a new world built on love, justice, equality, and together inspire change of policies, practices, and behaviour at all levels, from government to grassroots communities. We, therefore, pray “to the Creator” in an inter-faith and ecumenical spirit, so that the heart of mankind may harbour “a spirit of fraternity” and friendship: “Trinity of love, from the profound communion of your divine life, pour out upon us a torrent of fraternal love (...) discovering Christ in each human being, recognizing him crucified in the sufferings of the abandoned and forgotten of our world, and risen in each brother or sister who makes a new start” (FT, ecumenical prayer).¹⁶

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Book Review

Xavier, Basis S. *Philosophies of Margins: Theoretical Foundations and Illustrative Models of Application*. Madurai: Shanlax Publications. ISBN: 978-93-90082-36-0 pp. xii+ 258. ₹ 650/-

This book, *Philosophies of Margins: Theoretical Foundations and Illustrative Models of Application*, is a collection of articles written during the philosophical journey of the author for more than two and half decades both as a student and a teacher of philosophy. His philosophical passion started towards Karl Marx, Ambedkar, Periyar and structuralism; then towards phenomenology, existentialism, hermeneutics and Wittgenstein and later the interest tuned towards critical theory, post-Marxism and postmodernism. His initial interest as a doctoral scholar on folk philosophy, popular consciousness, identity construction and post-colonialism has been slowly convergent towards ethnophilosophy – the current specialization of the author. Ethnophilosophy is the study of indigenous philosophical systems. The implicit concept is that a specific culture can have a philosophy that is not applicable and accessible to all peoples and cultures in the world; however, this concept is disputed by traditional philosophers.

This philosophical journey or movement is very obvious in all the sixteen papers found in this book. The first article deals with structuralism and Levi-Strauss. Reflective articles on critical theory, Habermass, Gramsci, phenomenology and ethnophilosophy of Africana philosophy are part of the articles. It also includes studies on epistemology of ancient Tamils, illustrative models on anthropological and folklore tools to Dalit consciousness and indigenous knowledge for the digital world. The article also focusses on identity construction of periphery, nomads and postcolonialism, drawn from the insights of Derrida, Foucault and Arunthathiyars. An insightful study on the liberation approaches of Ambedkar and Guitierrez is also included. The final article is tellingly titled, “You are and therefore I am,” focusing on the inclusive nature of ethnophilosophy.

The present author’s philosophical journey is always focused on the dialectics between theory and practice. Eventually when the author encountered with the problems of the poor and the exploited, he was searching for philosophical solutions. While doing philosophy, his mind always looked how to put them into practice. Hence this dialectics of theory-practice is very vital and very

fundamental. His immersion with the life of the subaltern and periphery and their continued suffering constantly provoke for new philosophical solutions. With these conceptual understanding, whenever a new philosophical thought or perspective is emerging, he all the time reflected on how these ideas can be used to unravel the agonies of the oppressed.

Some thinkers and their philosophy come to the rescue when there is a search for answers to some pertinent socio-cultural and philosophical questions. So their theories are briefly exposed in this book in order to understand their relevance to such problems. Some such authors are Habermas, Gramsci, Foucault, Gutierrez Derrida from the Western perspectives and Ambedkar and Arunthathiyars from the Indian soil. Thus theoretical foundations of philosophy (including critical theory, phenomenology and epistemology) are sought in these articles and some illustrative models of application are strived for the liberation of the margins.

The author acknowledges that the Western philosophical search is external whereas the Indian one is internal. That is why reason of the west dominates not only nature, but also other nations and colonies. The Indian reason, on the other hand, pays no attention to the external world of *maya* (p. 95).

The author also indicates the challenge of living in harmony with the other. The very notion of 'us' vs 'them' is dangerous. We tend naturally to include some as 'us' and exclude the rest as 'them,' the 'other'. (p. 250). Then he borrows from Sudhir Kakar's psychology of exclusion where the other may belong to different ethnic, language, race, caste and religious groups. The difference leads to the construction of the other and the difference becomes a reason for discrimination, oppression and domination (p. 252), instead of accepting, acknowledging and respecting the other. The other may be both physical and mental and is demonized (p. 252).

By promoting unity and not uniformity, communities can live in harmony. The relation between harmony and identity is explored in the last section of the book. This leads to a deeper understanding of the philosophy of the other, inspired by Nelson Mandela, Jean-Paul Sartre, Gabriel Marcel, Emmanuel Levinas and Martin Buber (pp. 254-255).

The theology of the other bases itself on the prophetic proclamation of God's interest in the other. It also recalls Jesus' commitment to the other when non-Jews were generally regarded as the other. The prophetic parable of the good Samaritan is brought up to indicate Jesus' desire "to include the excluded" (p. 256). Through his psychological, sociological, philosophical and theological analysis, the author attempts to provide a new vision of the other, especially from the perspectives of the poor, dalits, trials, women and minorities. Thus he shows the way to achieve harmony with the 'other' by the mantra, "You are, Therefore I am!" (p. 257).

–Kuruvilla Pandikattu

Pandikattu, Kuruvilla. (2021). *Finding God in Everything: Insights into Finding Everything in God*. New Delhi/Pune: ISPCK/Jnana Deepa. ISBN: 978-81-947592-3-2 pp. xvi + 250 ₹350/-

Some of the questions this book attempts to answer are: Who are we? How can we relate to other and thereby realise ourselves? What is the meaning of my life? Where do we find God? How do we relate to Him? How does genuine spirituality enable me to become truly human, joyous and authentic?

These are some of the issues the author takes up in this book on contemporary, creative spirituality. This book invites us to find God in everything. More, it invites us to find everything in God. It deals primarily with life as lived out in our daily lives in our interaction with things and God. Then it tries to draw spiritual insight from the events of daily life, so that we can life up our lives, to embrace the world, fellow-human beings and God. The approach that we take in this book is an inclusive and dialogical one, where we try to discern the divine in every aspect of the earthly life.

So, we normally begin with a concrete experience, person, book or experiment. From that we go to explore the larger dimensions of life and study the deeper values inherent in it. So, we move from the material to the spiritual, from the mundane to the perfect, without in any way sacrificing the material or the mundane.

The author believes that our spirituality emerges from the earthly, without in any way giving up the other-worldly. He holds that true joy and happiness comes from the simple pleasures of life. We hope that our fulfilment as human beings starts from our concrete experiences of joy, sadness, relationships and love.

In the First Part of this book, the author tries out different ways and means of reaching happiness and healing. He wants to show that our friends, relationships, memories and forgiving the harm others have done to us will enhance our well-being and bliss. The next Part talks of the spiritual dimensions of our day to day life, which allows us to experience genuine joy. Meditations, mindfulness and other means of spiritual experiences are referred to in this part.

The Third Part invites the readers to foster creativity through art, silence and music, which form part of the melodies of our lives. Here we realise that our spiritual life has be rooted in the earthly and bodily aspects of our lives. This takes us to the next Part, dealing with the spiritual practices leading to joy and optimism.

The abandonment that is critical to any spiritual life takes us to the next Part, nurturing the aesthetic dimension of our lives. Art, dance, curiosity as well as reading and writing can make our life more authentic and empathetic. The Sixth Part helps us to explore some of deepest human values and try to make the best

of the encounters that we human beings are capable of: encountering fellow human beings, the world and the whole of reality face to face. The next part describes the role of stories in healing, liberating and making our lives genuinely humane.

Part Eight talks of individual responsibility to the society and the need to pay attention to the joys and sorrows of the larger political, scientific and social dimension of our collective reality. The next part deals with our responsibility to make of this world a better one, recognising the larger (and at times, uncomfortable) truths of our social life.

The final Part of the book deals with meaning and integrity within myself and in the larger world and cosmos we live in. It talks about the human need to be true to one's own self and to lead a modest and human life, so that we can truly feel at home with ourselves.

Thus, this book believes that the God we seek (or conversely and even better, the God who seeks us continuously) is to be found in everyone and everything. He is present in everywhere and traces of Him can be found in all things at all times, if we are attentive enough. That loving God is always present to us. From this experience, everything and everyone gets a different value. Then everyone has to be seen in God and everything has to be experienced in the Divine. So, we are called to find Everyone and Everything in God. That is grace! Such a God is unconditional love and unqualified mercy.

This book indicates that the spiritual can be traced in all activities, earthly, mundane and secular. It assumes that we can only reach the spiritual in and through the secular, the ordinary experiences of normal human beings. All in all, this is a modest attempt to reflect on our contemporary lives and see the glimpse or traces of the Divine in our lives. It is an invitation to discern God's presence in everything and in everyone. It is a simple effort "to see God in everything." And further "to find everything in God" as St. Ignatius of Loyola would put it.

Though this book is derived from the Ignatian insight, it is a book on Ignatian spirituality or Spiritual Exercises. It is highly recommended for seekers of all spiritual traditions and students of philosophy and theology. **-Gini George**

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